

Air quality around airports

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Summary

This study assessed air quality at 23 European airports selected for their high traffic volumes, geographical distribution across EEA member countries, proximity to densely populated areas, and relevance to ongoing ultrafine particle monitoring activities. The airports include major hubs such as Frankfurt, Paris Charles De Gaulle, and Amsterdam Schiphol, representing diverse regions from northern to southern and eastern to western Europe. Several airports were chosen because more than one million people live within 10 km of their boundaries. Information on recent monitoring activities was gathered through EIONET's Thematic Group on Air and complemented by literature reviews and European research projects.

The analysis focused on three pollutants—NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃—using validated 2023 data reported by EEA member countries. Sampling points (SPOs) with sufficient data coverage were identified within airport areas and at varying distances to consider their different lifetime and distribution, 10 km for NO₂, 20 km for PM_{2.5} and up to 50 km for O₃. Wind direction frequencies were analysed to distinguish downwind conditions, and pollutant concentrations were compared under two scenarios: wind from the airport versus other directions. To address gaps in monitoring coverage, EEA high-resolution air quality maps with a spatial resolution of 1 km were used to estimate annual mean concentrations and ozone peak season levels, enabling comparisons between airport areas, surrounding regions, and land cover classes.

Monitoring coverage near airports was highly variable. Eleven airports lacked NO₂ SPOs within 5 km, and only three had SPOs inside airport areas. For PM_{2.5}, 15 airports had no SPOs within 5 km, and only Dublin had a station inside the airport. Coverage improved at larger distances, particularly for ozone, which reflects its regional nature. Wind-sector analysis revealed uneven directional coverage for NO₂ and PM_{2.5}, while O₃ monitoring benefited from broader representation.

Comparisons under downwind conditions indicated potential airport-related impacts. For NO₂, 18 airports showed increases above 10%. When considering wind sectors with frequency above 10%, notable increases were found in Amsterdam (113%), Rome (90%), Lisbon (88%) and Madrid (83%). For PM_{2.5}, 15 airports showed increases up to 57% (up to 50% when considering wind sectors with frequency above 10%). Ozone increases were observed at 17 airports, up to 95% in Rome (in a wind sector with a frequency of 15%). These patterns suggest that airport emissions may influence local air quality, although other sources and meteorological variability must be considered.

Due to limited and uneven monitoring coverage, deriving robust conclusions solely from measurements was challenging. The analysis based on the EEA air quality maps provided clearer evidence of spatial differences. NO₂ concentrations were consistently higher in airport areas than in regional backgrounds, with differences exceeding 10 µg/m³ in Madrid and Lisbon, reaching 13.4 µg/m³. In Milan the NO₂ annual mean concentration was above the revised Ambient Air Quality Directive (AAQD, EU 2024) limit value to be attained by 2030 (LV₂₀₃₀), while Lisbon and Madrid approached it. PM_{2.5} differences were smaller, above 2 µg/m³ only in five airports. Six airports were surpassing the 10 µg/m³ limit value to be attained by 2030 (LV₂₀₃₀) and four were just below this level, between 9.5 µg/m³ and 10 µg/m³. The largest annual mean PM_{2.5} concentrations in airport areas were found in Milan (19.3 µg/m³) and Bucharest (16.9 µg/m³). Ozone peak season concentrations were similar between airports and regional backgrounds, ranging from 72 to 113 µg/m³, well above WHO guidelines (WHO, 2021). Overall, the study highlights elevated NO₂ levels in airport areas compared to surrounding regions, while difference in PM_{2.5} levels are smaller. O₃ remains largely regional in nature.

Long-term trends from 2005 to 2023 confirm substantial reductions in NO₂ and PM_{2.5} concentrations with average declines of around 45% for NO₂ background SPOs at different distance ranges from the airports. The analysis of PM_{2.5} long-term trends was not conclusive due to the limited number of SPOs with trends available. In contrast, ozone concentrations have increased consistently across all

distance ranges, with rises of about 23% near airports and 15% at greater distances, reflecting broader regional patterns.

Ultrafine particles (UFP), measured as particle number concentration, are emerging pollutants of concern due to their ability to penetrate deep into the lungs and enter the bloodstream. A literature review highlighted that measurements at several major airports show annual averages exceeding 20 000 particles/cm³ within 1 km of airport operations with concentrations declining rapidly beyond 5–10 km. Wind direction strongly influences dispersion, with airport-related contributions detected up to 7–8 km downwind. These findings highlight aviation as a significant source of UFP and underscore the need for standardized monitoring protocols and strategic station placement to assess population exposure.

This report includes the links to a fiche for each airport. The fiches include a summary of the analysis for NO₂ and PM_{2.5} in smaller files downloadable separately for each airport. The maps in the fiches display the location of the sampling points (SPOs) around the airports. The tables include additional information on the annual mean concentrations of each SPO with available data (data coverage larger than 75%), distances of the SPOs from the airport area, location of the SPO in one of the eight wind sectors (WS) around the airport (WS: N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, NW), wind frequency blowing from the airport in that WS, population living in the WS within 10 km from the airport, and trends of annual mean concentrations (2005-2023) when available. This information has been complemented with the EEA air quality annual maps (1 km x 1 km), covering the whole area around the airport and showing in the boxplot the different levels concentrations over the airport area compared to the surrounding region, including the weighted area means for the different land cover classes.

List of additional fiches:

- Amsterdam (AMS): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-amsterdam-ams.pdf>
- Athens (ATH): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-athens-ath.pdf>
- Barcelona (BCN): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-barcelona-bcn.pdf>
- Berlin (BER): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-berlin-ber.pdf>
- Brussels (BRU): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-brussels-bru.pdf>
- Bucharest (OTP): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-bucharest-otp.pdf>
- Copenhagen (CPH): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-copenhagen-cph.pdf>
- Dublin (DUB): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-dublin-dub.pdf>
- Dusseldorf (DUS): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-dusseldorf-dus.pdf>

- Frankfurt (FRA): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-frankfurt-fra.pdf>
- Hamburg (HAM): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-hamburg-ham.pdf>
- Helsinki (HEL): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-helsinki-hel.pdf>
- Lisbon (LIS): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-lisbon-lis.pdf>
- Madrid (MAD): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-madrid-mad.pdf>
- Milan (LIN): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-milan-lin.pdf>
- Paris (CDG): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-paris-cdg.pdf>
- Paris (ORY): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-paris-ory.pdf>
- Prague (PRG): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-prague-prg.pdf>
- Rome (FCO): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-rome-fco.pdf>
- Vienna (VIE): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-vienna-vie.pdf>
- Vilnius (VNO): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-vilnius-vno.pdf>
- Warsaw (WAW): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-warsaw-waw.pdf>
- Zurich (ZRH): <https://www.eionet.europa.eu/etcs/etc-he/products/etc-he-products/etc-he-reports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports/etc-he-report-2025-7-air-quality-around-airports-zurich-zrh.pdf>

1 Introduction

Air pollution remains Europe's largest environmental health risk, causing cardiovascular and respiratory diseases that impact health, reduce quality of life and cause preventable deaths (EEA, 2025). The revised EU Ambient Air Quality Directive (EU, 2024) sets revised and new air quality standards, to be attained in 2030, aligned more closely with the 2021 World Health Organization recommendations (WHO, 2021) in order to mitigate air quality impacts on health and environment. For PM_{2.5} (particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5µm or less), the annual limit value for the protection of human health will drop from 25 µg/m³ to 10 µg/m³. Similarly, the annual limit value for NO₂ (nitrogen dioxide) will be reduced from 40 µg/m³ to 20 µg/m³. For ozone (O₃), the target value for protecting human health remains unchanged at a maximum daily 8-hour mean of 120 µg/m³. However, the permitted number of days exceeding this target—calculated as a three-year average—will be reduced from 25 to 18 per calendar year.

The revised directive (EU, 2024) introduces also the concept of 'air quality hotspots' concept. This highlights areas with particularly high pollution levels that require specific monitoring efforts. Air quality hotspots include locations where the pollution level is strongly influenced by the emissions from heavy pollution sources, such as nearby roads, industrial sources, ports, **airports**, intensive residential heating, or a combination thereof. This report focuses on the air quality in the vicinity of airports as they can have an impact on the air quality levels in the nearby cities, and as they have been pointed in the directive as possible air quality hotspots.

Air pollutants in airports are emitted from a variety of sources, emissions from aircraft engines, ground support vehicles, passenger transport, and on-site energy generation. These sources release pollutants such as nitrogen oxides (NO_x), particulate matter (PM), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), sulphur dioxide (SO₂), carbon monoxide (CO), and ultrafine particles (UFP). UFP, which are particles smaller than 100 nanometres (nm), are particularly concerning because they can penetrate deep into the lungs, reach the brain and potentially enter the bloodstream. UFP are also included in the revised Directive (EU, 2024) as a pollutant of emerging concern that should be measured in order to support scientific understanding of their effects on human health and the environment. UFP should be measured at a location where high concentrations are likely to occur, such as airports, and at monitoring supersites⁽¹⁾ at both rural background locations and urban background.

Although technological improvements, such as lean-burn engines, and the adoption of sustainable aviation fuels (SAF) are reducing emissions at their source, aviation remains a significant contributor to local and regional air quality challenges (EASA, 2025). Aviation (both domestic and international) is an important emitter of NO_x. In 2022 the share of aviation in transport emissions was equal to 14% (EEA, 2024a). Emissions from the aviation sector (mainly due to international aviation) increased (1990-2022) in the EU-27 for most pollutants — NO_x, SO_x (sulphur oxides), NH₃ (ammonia), PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} — except for CH₄ (methane), CO (carbon monoxide), NMVOCs (non-methane volatile organic compounds). Increases in emissions since 1990 ranged between 47% and 117%, depending on the compound considered (EEA, 2024b). The number of passengers transported by air increased by 19.3% in 2023 compared with 2022. In 2023, 973 million people in the EU travelled by air (EUROSTAT, 2023a).

Airports are identified as potential air quality "hotspots" due to the concentration of aviation-related activities. A recent modelling study showed that pollutant levels near airports can be substantially higher than in surrounding areas in particular for NO₂, with aviation contributing up to 38% at airport sites (CONCAWE, 2023). Exposure to high NO₂ concentrations from aviation could be significant in residential areas around airports.

¹ Monitoring station at an urban background location or rural background location that combines multiple sampling points to gather long-term data on several pollutants (EU, 2024)

The aim of this study is to evaluate air quality in and around airports and understand the contribution to local air pollution from airport activities. Specifically, the report examines how air quality is monitored within airport premises and in their vicinity, and it compares ambient concentrations of key pollutants—nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), and ozone (O₃)—between airports and nearby cities or regions. Long term trends of air pollutant concentrations are also analysed to identify patterns and changes. The analysis will focus on a selection of 23 European airports, and it is based on the latest validated air quality data (2023) reported by EEA member and cooperating countries and the EEA air quality maps. To address these questions, the study followed several steps using various datasets, including air pollutant concentrations, land cover, population and meteorology. The methodology and datasets are described in Section 2, following the same methodology that was used for the analysis of air quality around ports (Pozzoli et al., 2024 and 2025). The assessment of air quality monitoring around the 23 selected airports in Europe is presented in Section 3. The comparison of NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ concentrations between airport areas and nearby cities and surrounding regions is presented in Section 4, and their trends in Section 5. Section 6 presents an overview of UFP air concentrations measured at different European airports and nearby cities. This includes a review of most relevant studies to show how aviation emissions can contribute to UFP at the selected airport cities. Section 7 provides general conclusions. Annex 1 provides the complete analysis (graphics and maps) for each airport.

2 Methodology

2.1 Datasets

2.1.1 Air quality data

The data about air quality sampling points (SPOs) were downloaded from the EEA Air Quality data portal (<https://aqportal.discomap.eea.europa.eu/>). Three pollutants were analysed, NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃, for year 2023, corresponding to the latest validated data reported by EEA member and cooperating countries (E1a, validated data AQ e-Reporting). The metadata of the selected SPOs and the corresponding measurements were accessed and downloaded from the annual statistics data table calculated from air quality values originating both from AQ e-Reporting (data flow E1a, <https://discomap.eea.europa.eu/App/AirQualityStatistics/index.html>, downloaded on 22 August 2025). For each SPO the relevant metadata were extracted, including the country, the air quality station Eol code, latitude and longitude, data coverage in the selected year, observation frequency and the link to the raw data with measured concentrations. A total number of 2 935 SPOs were found for NO₂ hourly measurements, 1 423 SPOs for PM_{2.5} hourly measurements, 563 SPOs for PM_{2.5} daily measurements, 2 048 SPOs for O₃ hourly measurements, all with available measurements in 2023 and data coverage above 75%.

2.1.2 EEA air quality maps

The latest air quality maps of EEA member and cooperating countries for 2023 (Horalek et al., 2025) were also used in this analysis. The maps provide annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations at the horizontal resolution of 1 km x 1 km. The maps are based on the interpolation of the annual statistics of the 2023 observational data reported by the EEA member and cooperating countries and other voluntary reporting countries and stored in the Air Quality e-reporting database, complemented, when needed, with measurements from additional sources. The mapping method is the Regression – Interpolation – Merging Mapping (RIMM). It combines monitoring data, chemical transport model results and other supplementary data using linear regression model followed by kriging of its residuals (residual kriging). The maps can be downloaded in GeoTIFF format from the [European air quality data \(interpolated data\)- Series](#) in the EEA geospatial data catalogue, while the methodology used for the production of these maps is detailed in Horalek et al. (2025) and therein references.

2.1.3 Land cover classes

The CORINE Land Cover 2018 (CLC2018, <https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/corine-land-cover/clc2018>) dataset produced within the frame of the Copernicus Land Monitoring Service was used to identify airport areas. The dataset provides pan-European CORINE Land Cover inventory for 44 thematic classes for the 2018 reference year. The polygons identifying airport areas corresponds to the CLC Code 124. The CLC2018 dataset is also used as auxiliary data in the production of the EEA air quality maps.

2.1.4 Meteorology

The wind direction is an important parameter which is measured at every airport. Wind direction measurements were used in this report to determine the frequency of downwind conditions at the air quality SPOs located around the airports. The wind direction data were downloaded from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) Integrated Surface Database (ISD) meteorological observations (Smith et al., 2011; <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/land-based-station/integrated-surface-database>). The ISD contains detailed surface meteorological data from around the world for over 35 000 locations. Hourly wind directions at meteorological observing stations located inside the

airports were imported using the *worldmet* package, which is part of the *openair* toolkit (Carslaw and Ropkins, 2012).

2.1.5 Population

The JRC-GEOSTAT 2018 population distribution data (Batista e Silva, 2021) was used in this study in combination with the location of the airports and the surrounding SPOs. The JRC-GEOSTAT 2018 is a high-resolution (1 km x 1 km) grid map of resident population across 38 European countries for the year 2018. It was developed by the European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC) in collaboration with DG REGIO and Eurostat.

2.1.6 Air traffic

Air traffic data at different airports were extracted from EUROSTAT Air transport measurement – passengers and freight (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/cache/metadata/en/avia_pa_esms.htm). The sum of total annual number of passenger (EUROSTAT, 2023a) and freight (EUROSTAT, 2023b) flights by airport was extracted and considered as one of the criteria for the airport selection.

2.2 Airport selection

This study analyses air quality for a selection of European airports, 23 airports were selected considering the following criteria:

- air traffic (total number of passenger flights and freight flights in 2023);
- geographical distribution in the EEA member countries;
- population living in the vicinity of the airports;
- available studies regarding airports and UFP measurements from existing research EU projects and from EEA member and cooperating countries (EIONET consultation).

The list of the 23 selected airports is provided in Table 2.1. Airports are identified by their city name and the airport code from the International Air Transport Association (IATA). The list includes some of the European airports with largest traffic with over 400 000 flights (passenger and freight) in 2023, such as Frankfurt – Main (FRA), Paris - Charles De Gaulle (CDG) and Amsterdam – Schiphol (AMS). The airports are located in 17 different European and EEA member countries (Figure 2.1), from western (Lisbon, LIS) to eastern Europe (Bucharest, OTP), and from northern (Helsinki, HEL) to southern Europe (Athens, ATH). Some of the airports were selected for their vicinity to densely populated urban areas, thus with high population living in the vicinity of the airport. The airports of Hamburg (HAM), Lisbon (LIS), Madrid (MAD), Milan (LIN), Paris (ORY) and Warsaw (WAW) have more than 1 million inhabitants living within 10 km (or more than 240 000 inhabitants within 5 km for HAM, LIN, ORY and WAW; over 400 000 inhabitants for the airport of LIS). A number of ongoing activities and recent studies about monitoring air quality at airports were reported through an EIONET consultation by the experts of the EIONET Thematic Group on Air (TG-AIR). The EIONET consultation mainly focused on recent or ongoing monitoring activities of UFP. Additional studies were provided for six of the selected airports. This was also complemented by a preliminary literature review, which identified existing studies and European research projects (such as NET4CITIES⁽²⁾, OLGA⁽³⁾, KoPilot⁽⁴⁾, RI-URBANS⁽⁵⁾, STARGATE⁽⁶⁾ and ULTRAFLEB⁽⁷⁾) on UFP measurements. Such studies and projects were identified for 10 of the selected airports.

² <https://www.net4cities.eu/>

³ <https://www.olga-project.eu/olympics-innovations/air-quality-source-apportionment-study>

⁴ <https://www.uniklinik-duesseldorf.de/patienten-besucher/klinikeninstitutezentren/institut-fuer-arbeits-sozial-und-umweltmedizin/forschung/umweltepidemiologie/-/environmental-epidemiology/kopilot>

⁵ <https://riurbans.eu/>

⁶ <https://www.greendealstargate.eu/>

⁷ <https://www.tropos.de/en/research/projects-infrastructures-technology/joint-research-projects/ultrafleb>

Table 2.1: List of airports in Europe included in this study

Airports (City – IATA code)	Country code	# flights in 2023	Studies and projects on UFP	Population within 5 km	Population within 10 km
Amsterdam (AMS)	NL	436 967	Vogt et al., 2019, 2019; Dinther et al., 2019; Tromp et al., 2021; Hofman, 2016	67 805	656 614
Athens (ATH)	EL	218 524	RI-URBANS	13 885	114 669
Barcelona (BCN)	ES	310 073	NET4CITIES; RI-URBANS	73 838	913 168
Berlin (BER)	DE	166 100	Winkler et al., 2025; ULTRAFLEB; NET4CITIES	81 134	489 981
Brussels (BRU)	BE	180 376	Lefebvre et al., 2019; Garcia-Marles et al., 2025; STARGATE	91 796	647 575
Bucharest (OTP)	RO	103 776		29 617	135 464
Copenhagen (CPH)	DK	222 068	Ellermann et al., 2024	78 890	310 306
Dublin (DUB)	IR	229 755		125 961	594 831
Dusseldorf (DUS)	DE	143 567	Grosse Schute, 2025; KoPilot; NET4CITIES	133 403	596 132
Frankfurt (FRA)	DE	422 275	Gerwig et al., 2025; HLNUG, 2025	37 849	383 714
Hamburg (HAM)	DE	103 669		249 997	1 179 424
Helsinki (HEL)	FI	135 788	Korhonen et al, 2023	66 319	359 322
Lisbon (LIS)	PT	221 781		432 863	1 054 312
Madrid (MAD)	ES	377 513		64 306	1 097 811
Milan (LIN)	IT	97 753		245 983	1 219 035
Paris (CDG)	FR	446 185	AIRPARIF 2024; OLGA; RI-URBANS	14 870	375 974
Paris (ORY)	FR	205 679	RI-URBANS	260 312	1 439 945
Prague (PRG)	CZ	102 087		46 070	313 813

Rome (FCO)	IT	262 653		37 635	234 361
Vienna (VIE)	AT	219 339	Buxbaum et al., 2025	11 267	74 029
Vilnius (VNO)	LT	35 471		72 641	351 285
Warsaw (WAW)	PL	153 935		240 176	1 055 371
Zurich (ZRH)	CH	213 400	OSTLUFT, 2025; NET4CITIES	91 281	494 535

Figure 2.1: Location of the 23 European airports analysed in this study

2.3 Assessing air quality in the vicinity of the selected airports and surrounding regions

The first step was to identify the SPOs with available data in 2023 (with data coverage larger than 75%) inside the airport area (i.e. inside the CLC2018 polygon classified as airport, CLC Code 124) and within different distance ranges. Air quality SPOs located in the vicinity of airports were considered (i.e. inside the airport area or within 1 km) and other that could be affected by the airport activities in the vicinity of airport (within 5 km). The identified sampling points were then compared with SPOs in the nearby cities and surrounding areas. Different distance ranges from the airport areas were considered, 10 km for NO₂, 20 km for PM_{2.5} due to its longer lifetime in the atmosphere, 50 km for O₃ due to its secondary chemical production also far from the sources of its precursors (NO_x and NMVOCs).

Meteorology is an important factor in the analysis. To assess wind direction frequencies, hourly wind data from 2023 were collected from meteorological stations located within the airports. The data were used to calculate the percentage of time the wind blew from the airport toward each of eight surrounding sectors, each 45 degrees wide and centred at the following compass directions: 45° (Northeast, NE), 90° (East, E), 135° (Southeast, SE), 180° (South, S), 225° (Southwest, SW), 270° (West, W), 315° (Northwest, NW), and 360° (North, N).

The assessment of NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ concentrations in the vicinity of airports, relative to nearby urban and regional areas, was conducted through the analysis of hourly pollutant measurements obtained from the selected SPOs associated with each airport. Concentration distributions were evaluated under two distinct meteorological conditions: when the wind originated from the direction of the airport, and when it did not. This comparative analysis serves as a preliminary indicator of potential impacts from airport-related activities on ambient air quality across different wind sectors surrounding the airports. It is important to acknowledge, however, that observed differences in pollutant levels may also be influenced by other concurrent emission sources, which could confound the attribution of effects solely to airport operations.

Measurement data from SPOs are not consistently available across all airports, and where available, their spatial positioning relative to the airport may be suboptimal due to factors such as distance and local meteorological conditions. To complement the SPO-based analysis, the EEA high-resolution air quality maps for the year 2023 were utilized. These maps, with a spatial resolution of 1 km × 1 km, integrate model simulations, observational data, and supplementary inputs (Horalek et al., 2025), offering a more comprehensive spatial representation of ambient air quality in the regions surrounding the airports. They were employed to estimate differences in annual mean concentrations of NO₂, PM_{2.5} and the mean O₃ peak season concentration between airport areas and nearby cities and surrounding regions. The O₃ peak season concentration is related to the new long-term Air Quality Guideline (AQG) level for O₃ (set to 60 µg/m³; WHO, 2021). This corresponds to the average of daily maximum 8-hour mean O₃ concentration of the so-called peak season, defined as the six consecutive months of the year with the highest six-month running-average ozone concentration. Mean concentrations “in airport” were calculated for grid cells located within and up to 1 km from the airport polygon. These values were then compared with the mean concentrations “in surrounding regions”, computed over a broader reference area defined by a 0.5 degrees latitude (approximately 50 km) × 0.5 degrees longitude (approximately 45 km at 35°N and 28 km at 60°N) region surrounding each airport. This approach enables the estimation of concentration differences between the immediate airport vicinity and the surrounding regional background. Additionally, the mean concentrations "in airport" were compared with area-weighted mean concentrations associated with different land cover classes, as presented in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2: Land cover classes used as ancillary data in the EEA air quality maps

Label	General class description	CLC classes grid codes	CLC classes codes	CLC classes description
HDR	High density residential areas	1	111	Continuous urban fabric
LDR	Low density residential areas	2	112	Discontinuous urban fabric
IND	Industry	3, 7-9	121, 131-133	Industrial or commercial units, Mineral extraction sites, Dump sites, Construction sites
TRAF	Traffic	4-6	122-124	Road and rail networks and associated land, Ports, Airports
AGR	Agricultural areas	12-22	211-244	Agricultural areas
NAT	Natural areas	23-34	311-335	Forest and seminatural areas

A database of SPOs containing long-term trends in air pollutant concentrations at European and national levels for the period 2005–2021 (Gbangou and Colette, 2023) was updated to include data up to 2023. This extended dataset was used to assess trends in NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ concentrations at the

SPOs identified in earlier stages of the analysis. The objective of this comparison was to evaluate whether distinct trends in annual mean concentrations were observed in airports or their immediate surroundings, relative to other SPOs located in the broader regional context.

3 Air quality monitoring around European airports

3.1 NO₂

To assess the availability of NO₂ measurements in proximity to European airports, the number of SPOs within 5 km and 10 km from the meteorological station located inside each airport were evaluated. Figure 3.1 presents the number of NO₂ SPOs located within 5 km (red bars) and 10 km (blue bars) of selected airports. The plot reveals significant variation in monitoring coverage across locations. For instance, 11 airports don't have any SPO measuring NO₂ hourly concentrations within 5 km (ATH, BER, OTP, CPH, FRA, HAM, HEL, CDG, ORY, PRG, and VIE). The number of SPOs within 5 km for the other airports ranges between one (DUB, LIN, WAW and ZRH) and three (AMS, LIS and MAD). All the selected airports have at least one SPO measuring NO₂ within 10 km, but the total number of SPOs is highly variable between the airports. The number of SPOs within 10 km ranges between 1, found for five airports (ATH, OTP, CPH, HEL and PRG), and a maximum of 8, found for four airports (DUB, HAM, LIS and MAD).

Table 3.1 provides an overview of SPOs with available NO₂ hourly data in 2023 within a 10 km radius from the meteorological stations located inside the selected airports. The table includes information on the number and type of SPOs (Background, B; Traffic, T; Industrial, I), availability of long-term trend data, proximity to the airport polygon, and their distribution across wind sectors. This summary highlights the variability in monitoring coverage, SPO types, and wind sector representation across airports, which is critical for interpreting air quality data in relation to airport emissions and influences from other local and regional sources. The total number of SPOs within 10 km was already described in Figure 3.1 and discussed in the previous paragraph. In addition to that, the identified SPOs are grouped based on their monitoring context: Background (B), Traffic (T), or Industrial (I). The distribution of types provides insight into the dominant sources of pollution being monitored near each airport. Most of the selected airports have one or more background SPOs within 10 km, except for CPH and HEL, which have one traffic SPO. More than one of SPO type was identified for 12 of the selected airports, such background and traffic in AMS, DUB, HAM, LIS, MAD, LIN, WAW and ZRH, background and industrial in BRU and FCO, or all types in DUS and VNO. The mean distances of the identified SPOs from the airport area are ranging between approximately 2 km (FCO) and 8 km (OTP). The distance and distribution of SPO types are crucial for interpreting air quality data. Airports with a mix of SPO types offer more comprehensive insights into different pollution sources. In contrast, airports with only one SPO, background (ATH, OTP and PRG) or traffic (CPH and HEL), may lack the granularity needed to isolate airport-specific impacts.

At least one SPO with available long timeseries records (2005-2023) is available in 19 of the selected airports. The number of SPOs where trends of NO₂ are available is ranging between one (BCN, CPH, DUB, HEL and FCO) and six (HAM). Long timeseries records are not available for the airports of ATH, OTP, PRG and ZRH. Trends are discussed more in detail in Section 5.

Only three of the selected airports have one SPO located inside the airport area (identified as the polygons with CLC Code 124), one industrial SPO in the airport of Brussels (BRU), and one background SPO each in the airports of Dublin (DUB) and Madrid (MAD). Eight airports have at least one SPO located in the vicinity of the airport (i.e. within 1 km from the airport polygon), one background SPO each in the airports of Barcelona (BCN), Dublin (DUB), Dusseldorf (DUS) and Rome (FCO), one traffic SPO in the airport of Zurich (ZRH), one background and one industrial SPO in the airport of Brussels (BRU), and two background SPOs each in the airports of Amsterdam (AMS) and Madrid (MAD).

The distribution of SPOs across wind sectors and the associated cumulative wind frequency provide insight into how well the monitoring network captures air quality under prevailing wind conditions around each airport. SPOs are distributed across one to five wind sectors depending on the airport. This reflects the directional spread of monitoring coverage. Airports like Lisbon (LIS) and Madrid (MAD) have SPOs in five sectors, offering broader directional representation, 69% and 58%

respectively. The cumulative wind frequency is above 50% in four other airports (AMS, DUS, FRA and WAW), with at least one SPO in four or three wind sectors. The cumulative wind frequency at the airports which have SPOs in only one or two wind sectors is ranging between approximately 12% (HEL) and 34% (VNO).

Figure 3.1: Number of monitoring SPOs of NO₂ within 5 and 10 km around 23 European airports with validated measurements for year 2023

Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference. presents detailed examples for the airports of Madrid (MAD), Brussels (BRU), and Dublin (DUB). The maps illustrate the airport areas along with the location and type of NO₂ SPOs situated within 5 km and 10 km of the meteorological station located inside each airport. Additionally, population density around the airports is visualized using 1 km × 1 km grid cells: light blue indicates semi-densely populated areas (300–1 500 inhabitants/km²), while red represents densely populated areas (>1 500 inhabitants/km²).

Adjacent to the maps, wind frequency plots show the distribution of wind directions from the airport meteorological station toward surrounding sectors. All three airports in this example have one SPO located within the airport area and another SPO positioned nearby, aligned with the prevailing wind direction and situated close to densely populated zones. This configuration meets the macro-scale siting criteria for large emission sources as defined in the revised directive (EU, 2024).

Figure 3.2: Air quality NO₂ SPOs around the airports of Madrid (MAD, left), Brussels (BRU, centre) and Dublin (DUB, right). The distribution of wind directions from the airport meteorological station toward surrounding sectors is shown below each map.

Table 3.1: Number of SPOs within 10 km from the European airports. SPOs in the list are those with available data for NO₂ in 2023

Airport	Country code	SPO within 10 km (#)	SPO type	Mean distance from airport (km)	SPO within 10 km with trend (#)	SPO in airport (#, type)	SPO within 1 km from airport (#, type)	Wind sectors with at least one SPO (#)	Total wind frequency covered by all SPOs (%)
Amsterdam (AMS)	NL	7	5B;2T	4.00	4		2B	4	52.4
Athens (ATH)	EL	1	1B	3.70				1	20.7
Barcelona (BCN)	ES	5	5B	3.47	1		1B	3	36.7
Berlin (BER)	DE	2	2B	4.44				2	17.1
Brussels (BRU)	BE	7	3B;4I	3.26	3	1I	1B;1I	3	44.4
Bucharest (OTP)	RO	1	1B	7.93				1	22.0
Copenhagen (CPH)	DK	1	1T	6.02	1			1	13.5
Dublin (DUB)	IR	8	2B;6T	6.32	1	1B	1B	4	43.9
Dusseldorf (DUS)	DE	6	3B;1I;2T	4.53	4		1B	4	58.7
Frankfurt (FRA)	DE	3	3B	3.92	2			3	53.6
Hamburg (HAM)	DE	8	3B;5T	5.73	6			4	41.8
Helsinki (HEL)	FI	1	1T	3.01	1			1	11.9
Lisbon (LIS)	PT	8	4B;4T	4.34	5			5	69.0
Madrid (MAD)	ES	8	6B;2T	2.91	4	1B	2B	5	58.1
Milan (LIN)	IT	7	2B;5T	4.78	5			4	46.5
Paris (CDG)	FR	2	2B	3.94	2			2	19.0
Paris (ORY)	FR	2	2B	3.74	2			2	28.4
Prague (PRG)	CZ	1	1B	6.15				1	12.8

Rome (FCO)	IT	3	2B;1I	2.17	1	1B	3	39.1
Vienna (VIE)	AT	3	3B	4.04	3		1	16.9
Vilnius (VNO)	LT	4	2B;1I;1T	4.94	3		2	34.2
Warsaw (WAW)	PL	4	3B;1T	4.90	3		4	66.9
Zurich (ZRH)	CH	6	3B;3T	5.05		1T	2	26.4

3.2 PM_{2.5}

Figure 3.3 presents the number of PM_{2.5} SPOs located within 5 km (green bars), 10 km (red bars) and 20 km (blue bars) of selected airports. The PM_{2.5} SPOs includes both automatic measurements of hourly concentrations as well as gravimetric measurements of 24-hour daily concentrations. As for NO₂ SPOs, the plot reveals significant variation in monitoring coverage across locations. Only the airport of Dublin (DUB) has at least one SPO located inside the airport area. Four airports have at least one SPO located in the vicinity of the airport (i.e. within 1 km from the airport polygon), one background SPO each in the airports of Brussels (BRU), Dublin (DUB), Dusseldorf (DUS) and Rome (FCO). 15 airports don't have any SPO measuring PM_{2.5} hourly or daily concentrations within 5 km. The number of SPOs within 5 km for the other airports ranges between one (AMS, BRU, LIN and FCO) and two (DUB, DUS, LIS and WAW). All the selected airports, except for Vilnius (VNO), have at least one SPO measuring PM_{2.5} within 20 km, but the total number of SPOs is highly variable between the airports. The number of SPOs within 10 km ranges between 1, found for 5 airports (ATH, OTP, CPH, HEL and PRG), and a maximum of 8, found for four airports (DUB, HAM, LIS and MAD). Only two airports do not have any PM_{2.5} SPO also within 10 km, Athens (ATH) and Vilnius (VNO), and VNO does not have any PM_{2.5} SPO up to 20 km. Nine airports have 10 (WAW and DUS) or more (up to 18 for DUB) SPOs within 20 km.

Table 3.2 provides an overview of SPOs with available PM_{2.5} hourly and daily data in 2023 within a 20 km radius from the meteorological stations located inside the selected airports. The total number of SPOs within 20 km was already described in Figure 3.3 and discussed in the previous paragraph. Most of the selected airports have one or more background SPOs within 20 km, except for Vilnius (VNO), without any SPO within 20 km, and CPH, which have one traffic SPO. More than one of SPO type, background and traffic, was identified for 12 of the selected airports, and all three SPO types for seven airports (AMS, BCN, BRU, OTP, DUS, HAM and LIS). The mean distances of the identified SPOs from the airport area are ranging between approximately 6 km (CPH and ZRH) and 16 km (ATH).

At least one SPO with available long timeseries records (2005-2023) is available in 18 of the selected airports. The number of PM_{2.5} SPOs where trends are available is ranging between one (CPH, DUB, and ORY) and seven (BER and MAD). Long timeseries records are not available for the airports of AMS, ATH, OTP, VNO and ZRH. Trends are discussed more in details in Section 5.

Only the airport of Dublin (DUB) has at least one SPO located inside the airport area. Four airports have at least one SPO located in the vicinity of the airport (i.e. within 1 km from the airport polygon), 1 background SPO each in the airports of Brussels (BRU), Dublin (DUB), Dusseldorf (DUS) and Rome (FCO). The distribution of SPOs across wind sectors and the associated cumulative wind frequency provide insight into how well the monitoring network captures air quality under prevailing wind conditions around each airport. SPOs are distributed across one to six wind sectors depending on the airport. This reflects the directional spread of monitoring coverage. Airports like Madrid (MAD) and Warsaw (WAW) have SPOs in six sectors, offering broader directional representation, 75% and 87% respectively. The cumulative wind frequency is above 50% in eight other airports (AMS, BER, BRU, OTP, DUB, DUS, FRA and LIS), with at least one SPO in three to five wind sectors. The cumulative wind frequency at the airports which have SPOs in only one or two wind sectors is ranging between approximately 10% (ATH) and 28% (ORY).

Figure 3.4 presents detailed examples for the airports of Brussels (BRU), Dublin (DUB) and Dusseldorf (DUS). The maps illustrate the airport areas along with the location and type of PM_{2.5} SPOs situated within 5 km, 10 km and 20 km of the meteorological station located inside each airport, together with population density around the airports, and the distribution of wind directions from the airport meteorological station toward surrounding sectors. All three airports in this example have one SPO located within the airport area (DUB) or another SPO positioned nearby, aligned with the prevailing

wind direction and situated close to densely populated zones. This configuration meets the macro-scale siting criteria for large emission sources as defined in the revised directive (EU, 2024).

Figure 3.3: Number of monitoring SPOs of PM_{2.5} within 5, 10 and 20 km around 23 European airports and nearby cities with validated measurements for year 2023

Figure 3.4: Air quality PM_{2.5} SPOs around the airports of Brussels (BRU, left), Dublin (DUB, centre) and Dusseldorf (DUS, right). The distribution of wind directions from the airport meteorological station toward surrounding sectors is shown below each map.

Table 3.2: Number of SPOs within 20 km from the European airports. SPOs in the list are those with available data for PM_{2.5} in 2023

Airport	Country code	SPO within 20 km (#)	SPO type	Mean distance from airport (km)	SPO within 20 km with trend (#)	SPO in airport (#, type)	SPO within 1 km from airport (#, type)	Wind sectors with at least one SPO (#)	Total wind frequency covered by all SPOs (%)
Amsterdam (AMS)	NL	11	6B;1I;4T	8.64				4	55.9
Athens (ATH)	EL	3	2B;1T	15.99				2	9.8
Barcelona (BCN)	ES	9	4B;1I;4T	10.65	3			3	35.7
Berlin (BER)	DE	15	7B;8T	11.62	7			5	58.6
Brussels (BRU)	BE	9	6B;1I;2T	7.32	4		1B	5	71.5
Bucharest (OTP)	RO	12	8B;1I;3T	11.49				5	72.7
Copenhagen (CPH)	DK	1	1T	6.02	1			1	13.5
Dublin (DUB)	IR	18	11B;7T	8.86	1	1B	1B	5	54.2
Dusseldorf (DUS)	DE	10	6B;1I;3T	7.16	2		1B	5	75.3
Frankfurt (FRA)	DE	12	9B;3T	11.77	5			4	58.4
Hamburg (HAM)	DE	5	2B;1I;2T	7.70	4			2	17.0
Helsinki (HEL)	FI	6	3B;3T	10.66	5			4	44.8
Lisbon (LIS)	PT	5	3B;1I;1T	9.61	4			3	54.6
Madrid (MAD)	ES	12	5B;7T	8.95	7			6	74.8
Milan (LIN)	IT	5	2B;3T	6.98	2			2	20.2
Paris (CDG)	FR	4	3B;1T	10.57	2			3	25.0
Paris (ORY)	FR	7	3B;4T	11.51	1			2	28.4
Prague (PRG)	CZ	6	4B;2T	9.95	4			3	31.7

Rome (FCO)	IT	4	4B	7.13	2	1B	3	32.0
Vienna (VIE)	AT	12	10B;2T	9.85	3		3	32.8
Vilnius (VNO)	LT	0						
Warsaw (WAW)	PL	10	9B;1T	8.80	3		6	86.7
Zurich (ZRH)	CH	2	2B	6.25			2	26.4

3.3 O₃

The longer distance up to 50 km from the airports was considered for the analysis of O₃ SPOs due to its secondary chemical production also far from the sources of its precursors. Figure 3.5 presents the number of O₃ SPOs located within 5 km (purple bars), 10 km (green bars), 20 km (red bars) and 50 km (blue bars) of selected airports. As for NO₂ and PM_{2.5} SPOs, the plot reveals significant variation in monitoring coverage across different airports. 14 airports do not have any SPO measuring O₃ hourly concentrations within 5 km. Seven airports have one SPO within 5 km and two airports (MAD and DUS) have two SPOs. When considering a distance of 10 km there is only one airport without any SPO (HEL) and ranging between one to six SPOs in other airports. The total number of SPOs is increasing at larger distances, ranging between 2 and 18 within 20 km (two airports with more than 10 SPOs) and between 2 and 37 SPOs within 50 km (17 airports with more than 10 SPOs).

Table 3.3 provides an overview of SPOs with available O₃ hourly data in 2023 within a 50 km radius from the meteorological stations located inside the selected airports. The total number of SPOs within 50 km was already described in Figure 3.5 and discussed in the previous paragraph. The number of background SPOs within 50 km is ranging between 1 (VNO) to 25 (MAD). More than one traffic SPO was identified for 13 of the selected airports, and industrial SPOs for six of the selected airports. The mean distances of the identified SPOs from the airport area are ranging between approximately 7 km (VNO) and 28 km (LIN).

At least one SPO with available long timeseries records (2005-2023) is available for most of the selected airports, the only exceptions are the airports of Zurich (ZRH) and Bucharest (OTP). The number of O₃ SPOs where trends are available is ranging between 1 in Dublin (DUB) and 26 in Madrid (MAD). More than 10 SPOs with long timeseries records are available for 10 airports. Trends are discussed more in details in Section 5.

Only the airport of Dublin (DUB) has at least one O₃ SPO located inside the airport area. Five airports have one SPO located in the vicinity of the airport (i.e. within 1 km from the airport polygon), one background SPO each in the airports of Dublin (DUB), Dusseldorf (DUS), Madrid (MAD) and Rome (FCO), one traffic SPO in the airport of Zurich (ZRH).

Considering the distance of 50 km analysed for O₃ SPOs, larger than the distances considered for NO₂ and PM_{2.5}, and thus larger number of O₃ SPOs found around airports, the distribution of SPOs across wind sectors and the associated cumulative wind frequency are generally larger. Only four airports (ATH, OTP, DUB and VNO) have SPOs distributed across three or less wind sectors. Six airports (DUS, LIS, MAD, LIN, ORY and VIE) have SPOs in all the eight wind sectors. The cumulative wind frequency is above 50% in 16 airports. The cumulative wind frequency at the airports which have SPOs in three or less wind sectors is ranging between approximately 29% (DUB) and 47% (OTP).

Figure 3.5: Number of monitoring SPOs of O₃ within 5, 10, 20 and 50 km around 23 European airports and nearby cities with validated measurements for year 2023

Table 3.3: Number of SPOs within 50 km from the European airports. SPOs in the list are those with available data for O₃ in 2023

Airport	Country code	SPO within 50 km (#)	SPO type	Mean distance from airport (km)	SPO within 50 km with trend (#)	SPO in airport (#, type)	SPO within 1 km from airport (#, type)	Wind sectors with at least one SPO (#)	Total wind frequency covered by all SPOs (%)
Amsterdam (AMS)	NL	17	10B;7T	27.2	6			6	68.1
Athens (ATH)	EL	12	8B;2I;2T	20.0	2			3	30.5
Barcelona (BCN)	ES	13	13B	14.6	7			4	44.0
Berlin (BER)	DE	15	14B;1T	21.0	10			6	71.6
Brussels (BRU)	BE	13	11B;1I;1T	20.6	10			6	62.2
Bucharest (OTP)	RO	5	5B	11.7	0			3	47.3
Copenhagen (CPH)	DK	11	8B;3T	26.5	6			4	56.8
Dublin (DUB)	IR	6	5B;1T	10.0	1	1B	1B	2	28.8
Dusseldorf (DUS)	DE	19	15B;4I	25.8	15		1B	8	97.7
Frankfurt (FRA)	DE	15	14B;1T	21.5	13			6	76.6
Hamburg (HAM)	DE	8	8B	21.8	7			6	65.4
Helsinki (HEL)	FI	4	4B	16.8	2			4	44.9
Lisbon (LIS)	PT	15	14B;1I	16.9	13			8	95.1
Madrid (MAD)	ES	37	25B;2I;10T	19.0	26		1B	8	96.0
Milan (LIN)	IT	26	23B;1I;2T	28.0	17			8	86.1
Paris (CDG)	FR	16	16B	22.6	13			6	61.4
Paris (ORY)	FR	20	20B	23.6	16			8	99.3
Prague (PRG)	CZ	11	10B;1T	20.2	8			5	46.8

Rome (FCO)	IT	15	14B;1T	26.2	7	1B	5	58.0
Vienna (VIE)	AT	24	24B	25.9	23		8	99.9
Vilnius (VNO)	LT	2	1B;1T	6.6	2		2	34.2
Warsaw (WAW)	PL	9	9B	17.0	4		5	71.1
Zurich (ZRH)	CH	12	8B;4T	16.8	0	1T	4	53.0

4 Air quality in airport areas compared to the nearby cities and region

4.1 Analysis based on hourly measurements from available SPOs

An analysis was conducted using hourly wind direction data from meteorological stations located within the airports, along with hourly air pollutant concentrations measured at the available SPOs surrounding each airport. The study assessed changes in pollutant concentrations at these SPOs during downwind conditions and compared them to concentrations recorded during other wind directions. Hourly time series data for NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations in 2023 were analysed for each airport. The analysis was performed separately for each of the eight wind sectors around the airports.

An example is illustrated in Figure 4.1 for the airport of Madrid airport (MAD). This airport has three SPOs located in the southern (S) wind sector relative to the airport. All three SPOs provided valid NO₂ data, while only one had valid PM_{2.5} data. For these SPOs, the distribution of pollutant concentrations was compared under three conditions: when the wind was blowing from the airport (green line), when it was not (blue line), and across all wind directions (red line). In 2023, the wind blew from the airport toward these SPOs 29% of the time, making it the predominant wind direction for that year. During these downwind conditions, the frequency of NO₂ concentrations exceeding 20 µg/m³ increased compared to other wind directions. When considering all SPOs in the same wind sector up to a distance of 10 km, the median NO₂ concentration rose by approximately 80%, from 16 µg/m³ (non-airport wind directions) to 31 µg/m³ (from the airport). For PM_{2.5} in the same wind sector, only one SPO provided data. A smaller increase was observed: the median PM_{2.5} concentration rose by 38%, from 8 µg/m³ (non-airport wind directions) to 11 µg/m³ (from the airport). These differences in pollutant concentration distributions suggest a potential impact of airport emissions on air quality in specific areas—such as the southern sector of Madrid airport. However, it is important to note that this analysis does not provide a precise estimate of the airport’s contribution, as it cannot isolate emissions from other regional pollution sources.

Figure 4.1 Distribution of hourly NO₂ (left) and PM_{2.5} (right) concentrations for SPOs (three for NO₂, one for PM_{2.5}) located in the southern (S) wind sector relative to the airport of Madrid (MAD). Three distributions are shown, for “all” wind directions (WD), for WD “from airport” and for WD “not from airport”. The number of hourly concentration values (# records) for each distribution is indicated in the legend.

Table 4.1 presents the cases where median NO₂ concentrations at SPOs located within 10 km of selected European airports increased by more than 10% when the wind was blowing from the airport toward the monitoring SPOs. Among the 23 airports analysed, 18 exhibited at least one wind sector with an increase above this threshold. The table summarizes these variations by wind sector, wind frequency, distance range, and the difference in median concentrations between downwind and non-downwind conditions. For each airport and wind sector where SPOs reported data for 2023, the following parameters are reported: Wind Frequency (%) (the proportion of time during 2023 that the wind blew from the specified sector toward the SPOs); Distance Range (km) between the airport and the SPOs, grouped into two ranges 0–5 km and 5–10 km; Number of SPOs (#) with valid NO₂ data in the given sector; Median Concentrations (µg/m³) reported separately for conditions when the wind was blowing from the airport toward the SPOs (“Wind from airport”) and when it was not (“Wind not from airport”); The relative (%) increase in median NO₂ concentrations under downwind conditions compared to non-downwind conditions.

The difference in median concentrations varies substantially across airports and wind sectors, ranging from 14% (Zurich, SE) to 143% (Lisbon, W). Several airports exhibit increases above 80%, notably Lisbon (W 143% and NW 100%), Amsterdam (N 113%), but also Paris (CDG), Rome, Madrid and Brussels. The wind frequency in these cases is not always the highest; differences in NO₂ concentrations were also observed in wind sectors with relatively low wind frequency, such as those in Lisbon, Paris (CDG), and Brussels. Median NO₂ concentrations above 20 µg/m³, reaching up to 42 µg/m³ (Lisbon), were recorded in only nine wind sectors of seven airports when the air was not coming from the airport (Lisbon, Warsaw, Milan in two wind sectors, Frankfurt, Hamburg, Dublin in two wind sectors, and Madrid). This number increased to 25 wind sectors of 13 airports when the air was coming from the airport, with concentrations reaching up to 48 µg/m³ (Lisbon). The airports of Amsterdam and Madrid consistently show elevated NO₂ concentrations under downwind conditions across multiple sectors and at different distance ranges (0–5 km and 5–10 km).

Similarly, Table 4.2 presents the cases where median PM_{2.5} concentrations at SPOs located within 20 km of selected European airports increased by more than 10% when the wind was blowing from the airport toward the monitoring SPOs. Of the 23 airports analysed, 15 showed at least one wind sector where PM_{2.5} concentrations increased by more than 10%. The difference in PM_{2.5} median concentrations varies substantially across airports and wind sectors, ranging from 11% (Paris ORY, N) to 57% (Brussels, W). Only few airports exhibit increases above 50%, notably Brussels (W and NW from 50% to 57%), Frankfurt (W 54%), Helsinki (W 51%) and Prague (NW 50%). Median PM_{2.5} concentrations above 10 µg/m³, reaching up to 15 µg/m³ (Bucharest), were recorded in only seven wind sectors of six airports when the air was not coming from the airport (Bucharest, Warsaw in two wind sectors, Athens, Dusseldorf, Paris (ORY), and Berlin). This number increased to 15 wind sectors of 11 airports when the air was coming from the airport, with concentrations reaching up to 19 µg/m³ (Bucharest). The airports of Berlin, Brussels, Frankfurt, Helsinki, Madrid, Paris (CDG), and Vienna consistently show increased PM_{2.5} concentrations under downwind conditions across multiple sectors and at different distance ranges (0–5 km, 5–10 km, and 10–20 km).

Table 4.3 presents the cases where median O₃ concentrations at SPOs located within 50 km of selected European airports increased by more than 10% when the wind was blowing from the airport toward the monitoring SPOs. Of the 23 airports analysed, 17 airports exhibited at least one wind sector with an O₃ increase exceeding 10%. The difference in O₃ median concentrations varies substantially across airports and wind sectors, ranging from 11% (Hamburg SW, Milan S and Madrid SW) to 95% (Rome, E). Only few airports exhibit increases above 50%, notably Rome (E 95% and NE 64%), Barcelona (NW 85%, N from 60% to 72%) and Milan (NW 51%). Median PM_{2.5} concentrations above 60 µg/m³, reaching up to 72 µg/m³ (Athens), were recorded in only eight wind sectors of six airports when the air was not coming from the airport (Athens, Barcelona in two wind sectors, Rome, Prague Lisbon in two wind sectors and Madrid). This number increased to 46 wind sectors of 15 airports when the air was coming from the airport, with concentrations reaching up to 89 µg/m³

(Athens). Several airports consistently show increased O₃ concentrations under downwind conditions across multiple sectors and at different distance ranges (0–5 km, 5–10 km, 10–20 km and 20–50 km). The detailed analysis has been conducted for all airports and wind directions where measurement data were available. A summary for each airport and for each pollutant is presented in Table 4.4, while the detailed results are presented in Annex 1.

Table 4.1: Variation in median NO₂ concentrations at monitoring sampling points (SPOs) located within 10 km of selected European airports, stratified by wind sector and distance from the airport. The table includes only cases where the median concentration under downwind conditions (wind from the airport toward the SPOs) was more than 10% higher than under non-downwind conditions. For each case, wind frequency, distance range, number of SPOs, and the percentage difference in medians are reported.

Airport	Wind Sector	Wind Frequency	Pollutant	Distance		Median Concentration		Difference medians
				Range (km)	# SPOs	Wind from airport	Wind not from airport	
Amsterdam (AMS)	N	16.3 %	NO2	0-5	1	26.60	12.50	113 %
Amsterdam (AMS)	NW	8.6 %	NO2	0-5	1	21.30	10.80	97 %
Amsterdam (AMS)	N	16.3 %	NO2	5-10	1	18.00	9.20	96 %
Amsterdam (AMS)	S	6.3 %	NO2	0-5	1	14.10	11.50	23 %
Barcelona (BCN)	W	8.3 %	NO2	5-10	2	14.00	10.00	40 %
Berlin (BER)	SW	9.7 %	NO2	5-10	1	8.96	7.31	23 %
Brussels (BRU)	NW	5.1 %	NO2	5-10	3	18.00	10.00	80 %
Brussels (BRU)	NE	32.1 %	NO2	0-5	2	15.00	10.00	50 %
Brussels (BRU)	W	7.5 %	NO2	5-10	2	21.50	15.50	39 %
Copenhagen (CPH)	NW	13.5 %	NO2	5-10	1	23.43	18.43	27 %
Dublin (DUB)	SW	6.0 %	NO2	5-10	1	35.14	20.63	70 %
Dublin (DUB)	S	4.6 %	NO2	5-10	4	31.18	20.44	53 %
Dublin (DUB)	SE	9.1 %	NO2	5-10	2	19.67	16.87	17 %
Dusseldorf (DUS)	NW	13.2 %	NO2	5-10	1	26.22	19.76	33 %
Dusseldorf (DUS)	SW	13.4 %	NO2	5-10	1	20.68	18.50	12 %
Frankfurt (FRA)	W	6.6 %	NO2	5-10	1	20.50	12.59	63 %
Frankfurt (FRA)	N	23.4 %	NO2	5-10	1	29.42	24.29	21 %
Hamburg (HAM)	N	8.0 %	NO2	5-10	1	36.88	21.61	71 %
Lisbon (LIS)	W	6.1 %	NO2	5-10	1	24.80	10.20	143 %
Lisbon (LIS)	NW	1.9 %	NO2	5-10	1	19.80	9.90	100 %
Lisbon (LIS)	SW	13.3 %	NO2	5-10	2	33.70	17.90	88 %
Lisbon (LIS)	NW	1.9 %	NO2	0-5	1	20.50	14.70	39 %
Lisbon (LIS)	S	16.7 %	NO2	5-10	1	47.90	41.70	15 %
Madrid (MAD)	S	29.4 %	NO2	0-5	2	37.00	20.00	85 %
Madrid (MAD)	S	29.4 %	NO2	5-10	1	33.00	18.00	83 %
Madrid (MAD)	NW	9.2 %	NO2	5-10	1	20.00	14.00	43 %
Madrid (MAD)	W	4.7 %	NO2	5-10	1	20.00	15.00	33 %
Madrid (MAD)	SE	9.4 %	NO2	5-10	1	19.00	15.00	27 %
Milan (LIN)	S	12.5 %	NO2	5-10	1	33.24	26.45	26 %
Milan (LIN)	NE	13.3 %	NO2	5-10	1	28.27	22.70	25 %
Paris (CDG)	W	4.7 %	NO2	5-10	1	24.25	12.65	92 %
Paris (CDG)	S	14.3 %	NO2	5-10	1	16.70	14.80	13 %
Paris (ORY)	N	13.9 %	NO2	5-10	1	19.80	15.00	32 %
Rome (FCO)	SW	18.7 %	NO2	0-5	1	17.79	9.35	90 %
Rome (FCO)	S	12.2 %	NO2	0-5	1	23.73	19.24	23 %
Vilnius (VNO)	N	21.1 %	NO2	0-5	1	15.30	11.85	29 %
Vilnius (VNO)	NW	13.3 %	NO2	5-10	1	12.24	10.71	14 %
Warsaw (WAW)	NW	19.3 %	NO2	5-10	1	22.40	13.80	62 %
Warsaw (WAW)	W	9.6 %	NO2	5-10	1	17.85	13.30	34 %
Warsaw (WAW)	NE	12.2 %	NO2	5-10	1	46.85	38.00	23 %
Zurich (ZRH)	SE	16.2 %	NO2	5-10	1	19.16	11.41	68 %
Zurich (ZRH)	S	10.5 %	NO2	5-10	4	16.51	14.49	14 %

Table 4.2: Variation in median PM_{2.5} concentrations at monitoring sampling points (SPOs) located within 20 km of selected European airports, stratified by wind sector and distance from the airport. The table includes only cases where the median concentration under downwind conditions (wind from the airport toward the SPOs) was more than 10% higher than under non-downwind conditions. For each case, wind frequency, distance range, number of SPOs, and the percentage difference in medians are reported.

Airport	Wind Sector	Wind Frequency	Pollutant	Distance		# SPOs	Median Concentration		Difference medians
				Range (km)			Wind from airport	Wind not from airport	
Amsterdam (AMS)	W	8.9 %	PM2.5	10-20		1	9.69	6.81	42 %
Athens (ATH)	NW	3.1 %	PM2.5	10-20		2	14.00	12.00	17 %
Berlin (BER)	SW	9.7 %	PM2.5	5-10		1	9.11	7.09	29 %
Berlin (BER)	NW	10.1 %	PM2.5	10-20		8	11.87	9.54	24 %
Berlin (BER)	N	10.1 %	PM2.5	10-20		1	11.75	10.10	16 %
Brussels (BRU)	SW	11.4 %	PM2.5	10-20		3	10.50	7.00	50 %
Brussels (BRU)	W	7.5 %	PM2.5	10-20		1	10.85	7.10	53 %
Brussels (BRU)	W	7.5 %	PM2.5	5-10		2	12.85	8.20	57 %
Brussels (BRU)	NW	5.1 %	PM2.5	5-10		1	8.93	7.05	27 %
Bucharest (OTP)	NE	16.4 %	PM2.5	5-10		1	19.37	15.49	25 %
Dusseldorf (DUS)	SW	13.4 %	PM2.5	5-10		1	12.30	10.82	14 %
Frankfurt (FRA)	SE	5.0 %	PM2.5	10-20		2	7.60	6.55	16 %
Frankfurt (FRA)	W	6.6 %	PM2.5	10-20		1	9.86	6.39	54 %
Frankfurt (FRA)	W	6.6 %	PM2.5	5-10		1	8.73	6.39	37 %
Helsinki (HEL)	S	10.7 %	PM2.5	10-20		2	5.52	4.54	22 %
Helsinki (HEL)	SW	13.4 %	PM2.5	10-20		1	5.07	4.14	23 %
Helsinki (HEL)	W	8.8 %	PM2.5	10-20		1	4.35	2.87	51 %
Lisbon (LIS)	W	6.1 %	PM2.5	10-20		1	8.90	6.90	29 %
Madrid (MAD)	SE	9.4 %	PM2.5	5-10		1	9.00	8.00	13 %
Madrid (MAD)	S	29.4 %	PM2.5	5-10		1	11.00	8.00	38 %
Madrid (MAD)	W	4.7 %	PM2.5	5-10		1	8.00	7.00	14 %
Paris (CDG)	SW	13.0 %	PM2.5	10-20		2	11.70	8.30	41 %
Paris (CDG)	W	4.7 %	PM2.5	5-10		1	9.65	7.80	24 %
Paris (CDG)	NW	7.3 %	PM2.5	10-20		1	7.80	5.50	42 %
Paris (ORY)	SW	14.6 %	PM2.5	10-20		1	12.40	10.40	19 %
Paris (ORY)	N	13.9 %	PM2.5	10-20		5	9.70	8.70	11 %
Prague (PRG)	SE	10.1 %	PM2.5	10-20		1	9.00	8.00	13 %
Prague (PRG)	NW	8.8 %	PM2.5	10-20		1	12.00	8.00	50 %
Vienna (VIE)	W	4.9 %	PM2.5	10-20		1	9.73	7.39	32 %
Vienna (VIE)	NW	16.9 %	PM2.5	5-10		3	9.54	7.00	36 %
Vienna (VIE)	NW	16.9 %	PM2.5	10-20		5	10.27	7.63	35 %
Vienna (VIE)	N	11.0 %	PM2.5	10-20		1	9.31	7.10	31 %
Warsaw (WAW)	NW	19.3 %	PM2.5	5-10		1	17.60	13.80	28 %
Warsaw (WAW)	N	10.9 %	PM2.5	10-20		1	13.50	12.10	12 %

Table 4.3: Variation in median O₃ concentrations at monitoring sampling points (SPOs) located within 50 km of selected European airports, stratified by wind sector and distance from the airport. The table includes only cases where the median concentration under downwind conditions (wind from the airport toward the SPOs) was more than 10% higher than under non-downwind conditions. For each case, wind frequency, distance range, number of SPOs, and the percentage difference in medians are reported.

Airport	Wind Sector	Wind Frequency	Pollutant	Distance Range (km)	# SPOs	Median Concentration		Difference medians
						Wind from airport	Wind not from airport	
Amsterdam (AMS)	S	6.3 %	O3	10-20	1	66.04	52.55	26 %
Amsterdam (AMS)	SE	9.6 %	O3	10-20	1	57.20	47.42	21 %
Amsterdam (AMS)	SW	13.5 %	O3	20-50	6	62.20	50.46	23 %
Amsterdam (AMS)	SE	9.6 %	O3	20-50	3	62.09	50.58	23 %
Amsterdam (AMS)	S	6.3 %	O3	20-50	1	61.74	51.08	21 %
Athens (ATH)	SW	24.4 %	O3	5-10	1	89.50	72.00	24 %
Athens (ATH)	W	8.5 %	O3	20-50	4	72.00	50.00	44 %
Barcelona (BCN)	N	7.4 %	O3	0-5	1	83.00	52.00	60 %
Barcelona (BCN)	W	8.3 %	O3	5-10	2	73.00	62.00	18 %
Barcelona (BCN)	NW	7.3 %	O3	10-20	1	74.00	40.00	85 %
Barcelona (BCN)	N	7.4 %	O3	10-20	3	84.00	69.00	22 %
Barcelona (BCN)	NE	21.1 %	O3	10-20	1	59.00	49.00	20 %
Barcelona (BCN)	N	7.4 %	O3	20-50	2	79.00	46.00	72 %
Barcelona (BCN)	W	8.3 %	O3	20-50	1	69.00	53.00	30 %
Barcelona (BCN)	NE	21.1 %	O3	20-50	2	72.00	57.00	26 %
Berlin (BER)	SE	7.8 %	O3	5-10	1	62.56	52.66	19 %
Brussels (BRU)	SW	11.4 %	O3	10-20	2	59.50	51.50	16 %
Brussels (BRU)	S	6.5 %	O3	20-50	1	61.00	53.00	15 %
Brussels (BRU)	SE	7.7 %	O3	20-50	1	64.00	56.50	13 %
Bucharest (OTP)	SW	22.2 %	O3	5-10	1	42.66	36.34	17 %
Dusseldorf (DUS)	SE	6.7 %	O3	20-50	2	64.65	53.97	20 %
Frankfurt (FRA)	NE	26.4 %	O3	5-10	1	53.34	46.85	14 %
Frankfurt (FRA)	SE	5.0 %	O3	10-20	1	56.64	50.03	13 %
Frankfurt (FRA)	E	7.9 %	O3	20-50	2	60.15	51.30	17 %
Hamburg (HAM)	E	17.7 %	O3	5-10	1	60.94	48.31	26 %
Hamburg (HAM)	SE	14.4 %	O3	10-20	1	63.21	53.70	18 %
Hamburg (HAM)	SE	14.4 %	O3	20-50	1	64.26	56.64	13 %
Hamburg (HAM)	SW	10.9 %	O3	20-50	1	62.02	56.03	11 %
Lisbon (LIS)	SE	34.7 %	O3	0-5	1	65.00	55.00	18 %
Lisbon (LIS)	SE	34.7 %	O3	10-20	1	71.00	62.00	15 %
Lisbon (LIS)	SE	34.7 %	O3	20-50	2	70.00	60.00	17 %
Madrid (MAD)	SW	7.8 %	O3	0-5	1	70.00	61.00	15 %
Madrid (MAD)	SW	7.8 %	O3	5-10	1	65.00	56.00	16 %
Madrid (MAD)	E	9.0 %	O3	10-20	1	71.00	55.00	29 %
Madrid (MAD)	SW	7.8 %	O3	10-20	5	63.00	56.00	13 %
Madrid (MAD)	E	9.0 %	O3	20-50	1	67.50	50.00	35 %
Madrid (MAD)	NE	17.6 %	O3	20-50	1	69.00	59.00	17 %
Madrid (MAD)	SW	7.8 %	O3	20-50	7	63.00	57.00	11 %
Milan (LIN)	NW	12.1 %	O3	0-5	1	62.36	48.30	29 %
Milan (LIN)	W	16.1 %	O3	5-10	1	60.75	54.93	11 %
Milan (LIN)	NW	12.1 %	O3	10-20	1	65.68	44.76	47 %
Milan (LIN)	N	11.4 %	O3	10-20	2	53.88	41.66	29 %
Milan (LIN)	NW	12.1 %	O3	20-50	3	66.13	43.75	51 %
Milan (LIN)	N	11.4 %	O3	20-50	5	67.32	55.86	21 %
Paris (ORY)	W	5.6 %	O3	20-50	1	68.85	58.70	17 %
Prague (PRG)	E	12.9 %	O3	5-10	1	62.80	56.30	12 %
Prague (PRG)	E	12.9 %	O3	10-20	3	57.70	50.50	14 %
Prague (PRG)	SW	5.9 %	O3	20-50	1	79.00	63.40	25 %
Rome (FCO)	N	9.0 %	O3	5-10	1	79.59	67.37	18 %
Rome (FCO)	NE	11.5 %	O3	10-20	2	67.03	47.24	42 %
Rome (FCO)	E	15.5 %	O3	20-50	2	79.99	40.94	95 %
Rome (FCO)	NE	11.5 %	O3	20-50	4	64.14	39.14	64 %
Warsaw (WAW)	E	26.5 %	O3	10-20	1	49.42	43.40	14 %
Zurich (ZRH)	E	14.3 %	O3	10-20	1	61.07	48.76	25 %
Zurich (ZRH)	E	14.3 %	O3	20-50	1	66.71	58.69	14 %

Table 4.4: Summary for all airports with main percentage changes in median NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ concentrations for measurements when air is blowing from the airport

Airport	NO₂	PM_{2.5}	O₃	Maps and figures
Amsterdam (AMS)	Data available in 4 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors from 23% (S) to 113% (N).	Data available in 4 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, from 3% (N) to 42% (W).	Data available in 6 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 21% (SE) to 26% (S).	Annex 1.1
Athens (ATH)	Data available in 1 wind sectors (SW). No increase detected.	Data available in 2 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 7% (W) to 17% (NW).	Data available in 3 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 6% (NW) to 44% (W).	Annex 1.2
Barcelona (BCN)	Data available in 3 wind sectors. Increase detected in 1 sector, 40% (W).	Data not available.	Data available in 5 wind sectors. Increase detected in 5 sectors, from 18% (W) to 85% (NW).	Annex 1.3
Berlin (BER)	Data available in 2 wind sectors. Increase detected in 1 sector, 23% (SW).	Data available in 5 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 16% (N) to 29% (SW).	Data available in 6 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 5% (W) and 19% (SE).	Annex 1.4
Brussels (BRU)	Data available in 3 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors from 39% (W) to 80% (NW).	Data available in 5 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 27% (NW) to 57% (W).	Data available in 6 wind sectors. Increase detected in 4 sectors, from 6% (W) to 16% (SW).	Annex 1.5
Bucharest (OTP)	Data available in 1 wind sectors (SW). No increase detected.	Data available in 5 wind sectors. Increase detected in 1 sector, 25% (NE).	Data available in 3 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 5% (S) and 17% (NWW).	Annex 1.6
Copenhagen (CPH)	Data available in 1 wind sector (NW) with 27% increase detected.	Data available in 1 wind sector (NW) with 8% Increase detected.	Data available in 4 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 4% (NW) and 6% (E).	Annex 1.7
Dublin (DUB)	Data available in 4 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors from 17% (SE) to 70% (SW).	Data available in 5 wind sectors. Increase detected in 1 sector, 25% (NE).	Data available in 2 wind sectors. No increase detected.	Annex 1.8

Dusseldorf (DUS)	Data available in 4 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors from 12% (SW) to 33% (NW).	Data available in 5 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 8% (S and NW) to 14% (SW).	Data available in 8 wind sectors. Increase detected in 4 sectors, from 6% (NE) to 20% (SE).	Annex 1.9
Frankfurt (FRA)	Data available in 2 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 21% (N) to 63% (W).	Data available in 4 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 16% (SE) and 54% (W).	Data available in 6 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 8% (SE) to 17% (E).	Annex 1.10
Hamburg (HAM)	Data available in 4 wind sectors. Increase detected in 1 sector, 71% (N).	Data available in 2 wind sectors. No increase detected.	Data available in 6 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 11% (SW) to 26% (E).	Annex 1.11
Helsinki (HEL)	Data available in 1 wind sector (SE). No increase detected.	Data available in 4 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 22% (S) and 51% (W).	Data available in 4 wind sectors. Increase detected in 1 sector, 8% (E).	Annex 1.12
Lisbon (LIS)	Data available in 5 wind sectors. Increase detected in 4 sectors from 15% (S) to 143% (W).	Data available in 3 wind sectors (W) with 29% increase detected.	Data available in 8 wind sectors. Increase detected in 4 sectors, from 5% (S and W) to 15% (SE).	Annex 1.13
Madrid (MAD)	Data available in 5 wind sectors. Increase detected in 4 sectors from 27% (SE) to 85% (S).	Data available in 7 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 13% (SE) to 38% (S).	Data available in 8 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 8% (NE) to 35% (E).	Annex 1.14
Milan (LIN)	Data available in 4 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 25% (NE) and 26% (S).	Data not available.	Data available in 8 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 11% (W) to 51% (NW).	Annex 1.15
Paris (CDG)	Data available in 2 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 13% (S) and 92% (W).	Data available in 3 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 24% (W) to 42% (NW).	Data available in 7 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 7% (S and SW).	Annex 1.16
Paris (ORY)	Data available in 2 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 4% (E) and 32% (N).	Data available in 2 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 6% (N) and 19% (SW).	Data available in 8 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 7% (SW) to 17% (W).	Annex 1.17

Prague (PRG)	Data available in 1 wind sectors (E). No increase detected.	Data available in 3 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 13% (SE) and 50% (NW).	Data available in 5 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 8% (SE) to 25% (SW).	Annex 1.18
Rome (FCO)	Data available in 3 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 23% (S) and 90% (SW).	Data not available.	Data available in 5 wind sectors. Increase detected in 4 sectors, from 2% (NW) to 95% (E).	Annex 1.19
Vienna (VIE)	Data available in 1 wind sectors (NW). No increase detected.	Data available in 3 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 31% (N) to 36% (NW).	Data available in 8 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 3% (E and NW) to 10% (S).	Annex 1.20
Vilnius (VNO)	Data available in 2 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 14% (NW) and 29% (N).	Data not available.	Data available in 2 wind sectors. No increase detected.	Annex 1.21
Warsaw (WAW)	Data available in 4 wind sectors. Increase detected in 3 sectors, from 23% (NE) to 62% (NW).	Data available in 6 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 12% (N) and 28% (NW).	Data available in 5 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 10% (S) and 14% (E).	Annex 1.22
Zurich (ZRH)	Data available in 2 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 14% (S) and 68% (SE).	Data not available.	Data available in 4 wind sectors. Increase detected in 2 sectors, 3% (SW) to 25% (E).	Annex 1.23

4.2 Analysis based on the EEA air quality maps

Most of the airports analysed do not have air quality SPOs inside the airport areas. Furthermore, most of the SPOs in the nearby cities are too sparse and often not located downwind of the airports. Thus, it was difficult to derive strong conclusions from the previous analysis based uniquely on measurements. The analysis of the EEA air quality maps (Horalek et al, 2025) may represent better the differences between NO_2 , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and O_3 concentrations in airports compared to the nearby cities and regional background levels. The EEA air quality maps are created as a data fusion between a chemistry transport model simulation, thus considering the impact of meteorology for a specific year, measurements reported by the EEA members and cooperating countries and other ancillary data, such as land cover. The maps are used to downscale the model results, which have a rather coarse resolution, to a finer resolution of 1 km by 1km, and better geographical distribution of pollutants concentrations.

The EEA air quality maps give also the possibility to show a comparison between the mean concentrations in airports and area-weighted mean concentrations for different land covers (i.e. the sum of the concentrations multiplied by the area fraction covered by a specific land cover class, divided by the total area of that land cover). The land cover classes which are used as ancillary data to create the maps are listed in Table 2.2, and are also based on the CORINE CLC 2018 dataset used in this study to identify the airport areas (CLC code 124). The airport areas in the EEA air quality maps are included in a new class, traffic (TRAF), which includes the codes 122-124, road and rail networks and associated land, ports and airports. One example of more detailed comparisons is presented in Figure 4.2 for the airport where the largest NO_2 concentrations were identified in airport areas and above the LV_{2030} for NO_2 ($20 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) annual mean concentrations set by the revised directive (EU, 2024) to be attained by 2030. The NO_2 annual mean concentration over the airport of Milan (LIN) is $24.7 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ compared to an annual mean of $16.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in the surrounding region, but slightly larger than area weighted mean concentrations over traffic (TRAF), low-density residential (LDR) and industrial (IND) areas, lower than area weighted mean concentrations over high-density residential areas (HDR). The maps of annual mean NO_2 , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ and O_3 peak concentrations along with comparisons between the mean concentrations over airport areas and mean area-weight concentrations across different land cover classes are provided for each airport in Annex 1.

Figure 4.2: EEA air quality map of NO_2 concentrations in Milan (LIN) airport and box-plot distribution of the concentrations over the port (grey shaded grid cells), compared to the surrounding region and area-weighted means for different land cover classes (Table 2.2)

The differences between annual mean concentrations over airport areas compared to the surrounding regions are presented in Figure 4.3 for NO₂, Figure 4.4 for PM_{2.5} and Figure 4.5 for O₃ peak season. The «Airport» concentrations are calculated as the mean concentrations of all the grid cells, in the 1 km x 1 km air quality map, which are intersecting or within 1 km from the airport area polygons. The «Non airport» concentrations are calculated as the mean concentrations over all other grid cells around the port over a region within 0.5 degrees latitude (approximately 50 km) × 0.5 degrees longitude (approximately 45 km at 35°N and 28 km at 60°N).

NO₂ concentrations in “Airport” areas were larger than the “Non airport” regional levels for all the airports analysed (Figure 4.3a), except in Rome (difference below 1 µg/m³). The differences in annual mean NO₂ concentrations ranges from 1.3 µg/m³ (Athens, ATH) to 13.4 µg/m³ (Lisbon, LIS). The differences were above 10 µg/m³ in two airports, Lisbon (LIS) and Madrid (MAD). The annual mean NO₂ concentrations were above 20 µg/m³ (the LV₂₀₃₀ for the protection of human health set in the revised directive (EU, 2024), to be attained by 1/1/2030) in one airport, Milan (LIN) with 24.7 µg/m³. Other airports which are very close to this LV₂₀₃₀ were 20.0 µg/m³ in Lisbon (LIS) and 18.2 µg/m³ in Madrid (MAD). When compared to mean area-weighted concentrations over different land cover classes (Figure 4.3b), only the airport of Lisbon (LIS) showed higher concentrations than high-density residential (HDR) area. Nine airports, Milan (LIN), Lisbon (LIS), Madrid (MAD), Dusseldorf (DUS), Paris (ORY), Warsaw (WAW), Hamburg (HAM) and Frankfurt (FRA) showed higher NO₂ concentrations compared to both industry (IND) and traffic (TRAF) land cover classes.

PM_{2.5} concentrations in “Airport” areas were larger than the “Non airport” regional levels for 19 of the airports analysed (Figure 4.4a). Compared to NO₂, the PM_{2.5} differences were smaller, ranging from 0.1 µg/m³ (Berlin, BER) to 2.9 µg/m³ (Warsaw, WAW). Only five airports stand out from the others with differences larger than 2 µg/m³, Bucharest (OTP), Lisbon (LIS), Milan (LIN), Madrid (MAD) and Warsaw (WAW). The annual mean PM_{2.5} concentrations were above or equal to 10 µg/m³ (the LV₂₀₃₀ for the protection of human health set in the revised directive (EU, 2024) to be attained by 1/1/2030) in six airports, 19.3 µg/m³ in Milan (LIN), 16.9 µg/m³ in Bucharest (OTP), 15.8 µg/m³ in Warsaw (WAW), 13.8 µg/m³ in Athens (ATH), 10.8 µg/m³ in Barcelona (BCN), 10.6 µg/m³ in Rome (FCO). Other airports which are very close to this LV₂₀₃₀ (between 9.5 µg/m³ and 10 µg/m³) are Madrid (MAD), Prague (PRG), Paris (ORY) and Viena (VIE). Figure 4.4b showed that six airports have PM_{2.5} concentrations larger than or equal to mean area-weighted concentrations over HDR land cover class, Lisbon (LIS), Milan (LIN), Frankfurt (FRA), Madrid (MAD), Dusseldorf (DUS) and Zurich (ZRH). PM_{2.5} concentrations in 13 airports were above the mean area-weighted concentrations for both IND and TRAF land cover classes.

O₃ peak season concentrations in “Airport” areas were in general similar to the “Non airport” regional levels (Figure 4.5a). The differences were ranging from -3.8 µg/m³ (Dublin, DUB) to 4.3 µg/m³ (Rome, FCO). The annual mean O₃ peak concentrations were ranging between 72.1 µg/m³ and 113.2 µg/m³ in airport areas, compared to regional levels ranging between of 75.9 µg/m³ and 111.6 µg/m³. O₃ peak annual mean concentrations are also very similar between different land cover classes (Figure 4.5). The O₃ peak season concentrations in airports and regional levels are all above the new long-term Air Quality Guideline (AQG) level for O₃ (set to 60 µg/m³; WHO, 2021). The TV₂₀₃₀ for the protection of human health set for O₃ in the revised directive (EU, 2024), to be attained by 1/1/2030, is the maximum daily 8-hour mean of 120 µg/m³ not to be exceeded on more than 18 days per calendar year averaged over 3 years.

Figure 4.3: Annual mean NO₂ concentrations in airport areas (“Mean Airport”) and surrounding regions (“Mean Not in airport”). The dashed red line represents the LV₂₀₃₀ for NO₂ annual mean concentrations set by the revised directive (EU, 2024).

Figure 4.4: Annual mean PM_{2.5} concentrations in airport areas (“Mean Airport”) and surrounding regions (“Mean Not in airport”). The dashed red line represents the LV₂₀₃₀ for PM_{2.5} annual mean concentrations set by the revised directive (EU 2024).

Figure 4.5: Annual mean O₃ peak season concentrations in airport areas (“Mean Airport”) and surrounding regions (“Mean Not in airport”). The dashed black line represents the WHO guideline for O₃ peak season concentrations (WHO 2021).

5 Differences between air pollution trends in airport areas and nearby cities

Long-term trends (2005-2021) of air pollutants at European and national level have been studied in Gbangou and Colette (2023) by analysing the observations through linear statistics. This dataset was extended to cover the period until year 2023. These trends have been investigated to highlight the differences of the evolution of NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ concentrations in the vicinity of airport areas and surrounding regions.

The number of SPOs with available long timeseries records (2005-2023) were summarized in Table 3.1 for NO₂, Table 3.2 for PM_{2.5} and Table 3.3 for O₃. From one to six SPOs with long-term trend within a 10 km radius of the airport were identified for NO₂ at 19 airports. For PM_{2.5}, from one to seven SPOs with long-term trend within a 20 km radius from the airport were identified at 18 airports. For O₃, from 1 to 25 SPOs with long-term trend within a 50 km radius from the airport were identified in 21 airports.

Table 5.1: Number of SPOs, associated airports, and percentage long-term trends for NO₂ by station type (Background and Traffic) within two distance ranges from airports (0–5 km and 5–10 km).

SPO type	0 – 5 km			5 – 10 km		
	#SPOs	#Airports	Trend (%)	#SPOs	#Airports	Trend (%)
Background	22	12	-44.3	20	14	-45.3
Traffic	10	6	-45.7	24	13	-53.8

As shown in Table 5.1, considering all NO₂ background SPOs with long-term trends for all the 23 airports, significant differences were not found between SPOs near the airports (within 5 km from the airport area) and more distant SPOs (from 5 to 10 km), with mean decrease between 2005 and 2023 around -45%. This analysis is based on about 22 background SPOs within 5 km (in 12 different airports), 20 background SPOs between 5 and 10 km (in 14 different airports). Long-term trends at traffic SPOs located near airports are comparable to those observed at background SPOs, approximately -46%, although based on a smaller number of SPOs. In contrast, traffic SPOs situated farther from airports exhibit a greater mean reduction, with a trend of -54%. Industrial SPOs were not considered as only few were identified in the considered distance ranges (two in 0 - 5 km and two in the 5 - 10 km).

Table 5.2: Number of SPOs, associated airports, and percentage long-term trends for PM_{2.5} by station type (Background and Traffic) within three distance ranges from airports (0–5 km, 5–10 km and 10–20 km).

SPO type	0 – 5 km			5 – 10 km			10 – 20 km		
	#SPOs	#Airports	Trend (%)	#SPOs	#Airports	Trend (%)	#SPOs	#Airports	Trend (%)
Background	10	8	-54.6	6	5	-34.5	31	13	-49.9
Traffic	3	3	-44.0	6	4	-35.7	13	9	-47.5

Long-term trends in PM_{2.5} concentrations near airports show substantial reductions across all distance ranges and station types, though the robustness of these estimates varies with sample size (Table 5.2). Within 0–5 km, background SPOs exhibit the largest decline (-54.6%) based on 10 SPOs

across eight airports, while traffic SPOs show a smaller reduction (-44.0%) from only three SPOs at three airports, indicating higher uncertainty for traffic sites close to airports. At 5–10 km, both station types display lower decreases (-34.5% for background, -35.7% for traffic), but challenging to interpret due to limited coverage (6 SPOs each). The most extensive dataset is for 10–20 km, where 31 background SPOs and 13 traffic SPOs confirm continued reductions (-49.9% and -47.5%, respectively), lending greater confidence to these estimates. Overall, while the downward trends are consistent and substantial, interpretations for categories with few SPOs—particularly near airports—should be made cautiously, whereas patterns supported by larger samples are more robust.

Table 5.3: Number of SPOs, associated airports, and percentage long-term trends for O₃ background SPOs within three distance ranges from airports (0–5 km, 5–20 km and 20–50 km).

SPO type	0 – 5 km			5 – 20 km			20 – 50 km		
	#SPOs	#Airports	Trend (%)	#SPOs	#Airports	Trend (%)	#SPOs	#Airports	Trend (%)
Background	15	10	23.8.6	67	20	22.7	102	18	15.2

Analysis of long-term trends in O₃ concentrations indicates a consistent increase across all distance ranges from airports (Table 5.3). Only few traffic SPOs were identified for O₃, thus not included in the table. Background SPOs located within 0–5 km of airports exhibit a mean increasing trend of 23.8%, while those in the 5–20 km range show a slightly lower increase of 22.7%. At greater distances (20–50 km), the mean trend remains positive but is comparatively lower at 15.2%. The number of SPOs and airports is much higher in the intermediate and outer ranges, which may improve statistical confidence. These results suggest that O₃ concentrations have generally risen over time, with the similar relative increase near the airports (0 – 5 km) and at intermediate distance (5 – 20 km).

6 Ultra fine particles around European airports

Ultrafine Particles (UFP) are defined as airborne particles with a diameter less than or equal to 100 nm, where UFP are measured as the particle number concentrations (PNC) per cubic centimetre for a size range with a lower limit of 10 nm and for a size range with no restriction on the upper limit (EU, 2024). WHO defines UFP as a total PNC with a lower size limit of 10 nm or lower, and an open upper end (WHO, 2021).

UFP are formed in almost any kind of combustion process and are emitted either directly as particles or are formed through nucleation and condensation in the plume of the combustion processes. Furthermore, UFP are formed in the atmosphere from gaseous precursors (biogenic and anthropogenic) as a result of photochemical processes. Particularly high concentrations of UFP occur at traffic-polluted sites and in the vicinity of airports, but are also caused by power plants, domestic furnaces and small and medium-sized combustion plants. Thus, characteristic for UFP is a high spatial-temporal variation and consequently different, selectively exposure levels that must be characterised and defined. Ultrafine particles are currently mostly measured and described by the total number of particles (or particle number concentration, PNC) and particle number size distribution (PNSD) (Hellack et al., 2022). Box 6.1 presents a short summary of ongoing research on health outcomes from exposure to UFP.

Box 6.1 UFP and Health

Compared to larger particles, UFP can penetrate deeper into the lungs, the brain (via the olfactory nerve) and presumably even directly into the blood circulation system via the inhalation uptake pathway. This results in a possible distribution and deposition of UFP in various organs. Consequently, current research indicates that the health impacts of ultrafine particles (UFP) are distinct from those associated with fine particulate matter (PM₁₀ or PM_{2.5}). This hypothesis is particularly supported by toxicological studies. While the number of epidemiological long-term studies has increased in recent years, many still lack sufficient adjustment for confounding variables (Hellack et al., 2022).

The evidence suggests adverse short-term associations with inflammatory and cardiovascular changes, which may be at least partly independent of other pollutants. For the other studied health outcomes, the evidence on independent health effects of UFP remains inconclusive or insufficient (Ohlwein et al., 2019). In the last years, there has been a substantial increase in the number of epidemiological studies examining long-term exposure to UFP and health outcomes. These studies cover diverse outcomes, though evidence remains sparse for most specific diseases. Positive associations have been identified for cardiovascular outcomes (e.g., stroke, hypertension), metabolic outcomes (e.g., diabetes, diabetes biomarkers), and inflammatory markers (e.g. cancers). However, associations with respiratory (e.g., asthma, lung cancer mortality), neurological (e.g., cognitive development), and pregnancy outcomes (e.g., low birth weight) remain unclear and warrant further research (preliminary findings from KoPilot study, currently in progress, with publication forthcoming, Thielke, 2024).

In the latest global air quality guidelines of 2021, the World Health Organization (WHO) considers UFP to be a parameter of particular interest, even if the data situation does not support the development of an air quality guideline level yet. WHO considers 24-hour-means of PNC below 1 000 particles/cm³ as “low concentrations”, 24-hour-means of PNC above 10 000 particles/cm³ and 1-hour mean of PNC above 20 000 particles/cm³ as “high concentrations (WHO, 2021). The European Commission has introduced a measurement requirement for UFP in the revised Directive (EU, 2024). This will improve the data situation and allow the characterization of UFP exposure and to verify the effects of UFP in epidemiological studies (Hellack et al., 2022).

6.1 Sources and distribution of UFP

In this section it is shown an overview of UFP air concentrations on the current state of air quality in European airports and nearby cities. This includes a review of most relevant studies to show how emissions from airport activities (e.g. aviation and traffic) can contribute to UFP at the selected airport cities. The temporal variability of PNSD and UFP concentrations (PNC) is complex due to dynamic processes such as meteorology, emissions and atmospheric processes such as new particle formation (NPF), nucleation, evaporation, condensation, coagulation and deposition (Bousiotis et al., 2021; Yao et al., 2018).

UFP may have a high spatial and temporal variability in urban areas, as shown by mobile and stationary measurements (Trechera et al., 2023; von Schneidemesser et al., 2019). The major factors influencing UFP concentrations include time of day, wind direction, wind speed, season, temperature, solar radiation (von Bismarck-Osten et al., 2013) and the mixing layer height (Emeis et al., 2008). The diurnal trend of UFP from traffic was described to be higher on weekdays with maximum concentration of nucleation mode particles (NUC, 5-25 nm), in the morning rush hour (Wehner et al., 2005). As evidenced from the evaluation of concurrent background and roadside measurements in Germany, NPF can contribute up to 30% of the NUC, relative to other sources including residential heating and car traffic (Ma and Birmili, 2015). Particles originating from secondary NPF contain relevant amounts of sulphate, amines and various organic compounds (Kerminen et al., 2018). Airborne measurements suggest that plumes from industrial plants contribute to 10-40% of background UFP in Germany (Junkermann et al., 2016). At six European countries (Italy, Ireland, France, Finland, Great Britain, and Germany) mobile three-dimensional distributions of power plant emissions at altitudes between 200 and 300 m above ground level found very high PNC, above $100\,000\text{ cm}^{-3}$ at 10 km distance, but no source allocation of its share was performed (Junkermann and Hacker, 2018). Several studies discuss the source apportionment of UFP (Garcia-Marlès et al., 2024; Hopke et al., 2022; Trechera et al., 2023; Vörösmarty et al., 2024). A review including six studies from Europe indicated different sources, mainly traffic. Other sources include secondary inorganic aerosol (SIA), between 10 and 40% found in Hopke et al. (2022). In Budapest, among six identified source types, road vehicles accounted for the largest share (60%, including solid and vapor phases), followed by nucleation processes (24%) and diffuse urban sources, while secondary inorganic aerosols (SIA) contributed less than 10% (Vörösmarty et al., 2024).

From the EU project RI-URBANS a recent study of 18 European sites identified ten different sources and factors in urban Europe to PNSD: nucleation (traffic-nucleation and photo nucleation), domestic heating, urban and regional background among others. The main contributors were traffic (56% - 95%) and photonucleation, mostly by NPF, was relevant (4-41%). NPF was attributed to shipping, plumes from combustion plants and regional nucleation. A Statistically significant decreasing trend for the total traffic--related UFP was found with $2\text{-}5\% \text{ yr}^{-1}$ for traffic and urban background (Garcia-Marlès et al., 2024).

Aircraft emit a large fraction of the UFP in the size of NUC particles (Brock et al., 2000). These NUC particles originated mainly from volatile organic compounds (VOC) emissions (Rivas et al., 2020). In the UFP mass fraction, jet engine lubricants were found (Ungeheuer et al., 2021). Airports have been identified as a source of elevated UFP, especially in the 10-30 nm range, both in measurements and models (Lorentz et al., 2019; Stacey, 2019). Take-off emissions were found to be generally coarser (20 nm) than taxiing (12 nm) (Garcia-Marles et al. 2025). Atmospheric observations downwind from airports typically show elevated UFP especially in the 10-30 nm range at about 5 – 10 km changing to slightly higher particle diameter in Aitken Mode (30 -100 nm) at more than 20 km distance observed from tower measurements, probably due to particle growth over some hours (Harrison et al., 2019; Keuken et al., 2015). Numerous observations report an enhancement of UFP in downwind air: Los Angeles (USA), 4-fold at 10 km (Hudda et al., 2014); Amsterdam (Netherlands), 3-fold at 7 km (Keuken et al., 2015); Boston (USA), 1.6 to 3-fold at 5 km (Hudda et al., 2018); Zurich (Switzerland), using a dispersion model, 2 to 10-fold at 3 km (Zhang et al., 2020); London (UK), 10-fold at 1.2 km (Masiol et

al., 2017). Other studies used positive matrix factorisation and cluster analysis to determine airport contributions to UFP (Hopke et al., 2022; Masiol et al., 2017; Garcia-Marles et al., 2025).

Data on atmospheric UFP have been collected over time periods long enough to detect trends. Long-term observations in North America suggest an increase in UFP over time (Chen et al., 2022). In Europe, however, a decrease was found (Sun et al., 2020; Trechera et al., 2023). This decrease was associated with efforts on air quality control, however the studies did not dive deeper into the influence of emissions from aviation.

6.2 Review of recent European studies regarding UFP at airports

In this section an overview of UFP measurements found in recent scientific publications and research projects is presented. A number of airports in Europe are listed in Table 6.1, for which it was possible to find measured values of PNCs. In the table the airports are sorted in alphabetical order, if more than one PNC value is available for the same airport (Copenhagen, Frankfurt and Paris), these are sorted by ascending distance of the sampling point from the airport.

Large values of PNC were measured (averages over different time periods, Table 6.1) inside or in the very near proximity of the airports (i.e. distance below 1 km). For example, in the airport of Copenhagen (CPH) annual mean PNC of 27 000 particles/cm³ was measured. High PNC values were measured also in the airport of Paris (CDG), 23 000 and 17 900 particles/cm³, and Zurich (ZRH), 24 000 particles/cm³. High values were also measured at larger distances from the airport of Brussels (BRU), 18 000 particles/cm³ at 2 km distance, and Vienna (VIE), 15 000 particles/cm³ at 2.5 km distance. Lower PNC values, below 10 000 particles/cm³, were measured at distances larger than 3 km, ranging from 5 100 particles/cm³ measured at 3 km from the airport of Berlin (BER) and 9 200 particles/cm³ measured at 6 km from the airport of Frankfurt (FRA).

However, it is not possible to directly compare the measured PNC values from different airports as long as these measurements are taken at different particle size ranges. Among the studies listed in Table 6.1, the lower limit of the size range is varying from 4 nm to 10 nm, while the upper limit is varying from 100 nm to 1 000 nm. Only measurements with same lower size range limit and preferable similar upper size range limit are comparable. The lower the size range limit is, the higher number concentrations are expected. Some caution should also be used when interpreting the impact of distance from airports on the UFP concentration levels, as these depends also by the location of the monitoring sampling point, in the main wind direction (md) or in a side wind direction (sd). More details are provided below for some of the airports in Table 6.1. Some of the measurements listed in Table 6.1 were also used to validate, derive or improve models for UFP exposure. Model results are useful tools in combination with measurements to estimate exposure at different locations around the airport, and to assess the possible contribution to the overall UFP concentrations in the region from the airport activities. Some examples of modelling studies are provided in Box 6.2.

Table 6.1: Measurements of UFP (particle number concentrations, PNC) near selected airports in Europe. The size range of the PNC measurements is indicated together with distances in km and location (in the main wind direction, md; on side wind direction, sd) of the sampling points from the airports.

Airport	PNC in 1/cm³	Averaging period	Size range in nm	Distance in km	Wind direction	References
Amsterdam (AMS)	10 000 – 38 000	6 months average (2017-2018)	7 -	0.4 – 5.1	-	Vogt et al., 2019, Dinther et al., 2019
Amsterdam (AMS)	11 700 – 16 300	2 months average (2021)	7 -	1.3 – 5.1	-	Tromp et al., 2021
Amsterdam (AMS)	9 070	2 years average	10 – 1 000	8	sd	Hofman, 2016
Berlin (BER)	5 100	Annual average	10 - 800	3	sd	Winkler et al., 2025
Brussels (BRU)	18 000	2 months average (2021)	10 -294	< 1 km	md	Lefebvre et al., 2019; Garcia-Marles et al., 2025
Copenhagen (CPH)	27 000	Annual average 2023	7 – 100	0 - 1	md	Ellermann et al., 2024
Copenhagen (CPH)	11 000 - 19 000	Annual average 2023	7 – 100	0 - 1	-	Ellermann et al., 2024
Copenhagen (CPH)	5 000 - 8 000	Annual average 2023	7 – 100	3	-	Ellermann et al., 2024
Frankfurt (FRA)	9 400	2015-2021	10 - 500	6	sd	Gerwig et al., 2025
Frankfurt (FRA)	13 600	Annual average (May 2023-April 2024)	10 - 500	2.5	md	HLNUG, 2025

Helsinki (HEL)	22 700	Annual average 2022	<10 –	0	-	Korhonen et al, 2023
Paris (CDG)	23 000	4 months average (Sep-Dec 2024)	5 - 400	0	-	AIRPARIF, 2024
Paris (CDG)	17 900	4 months average (Sep-Dec 2024)	5 - 400	1	md	AIRPARIF, 2024
Paris (CDG)	6 200	4 months average (Sep-Dec 2024)	5 -400	5	md	AIRPARIF, 2024
Paris (CDG)	7 400	4 months average (Sep-Dec 2024)	5 –400	10	md	AIRPARIF, 2024
Vienna (VIE)	15 000-16 400	Annual average 2022-2024	4 -300	2.5	-	Buxbaum et al., 2025
Vienna (VIE)	10 500-11 300	Annual average 2022-2024	4 -300	0.8	-	Buxbaum et al., 2025
Zurich (ZRH)	24 000	Annual average 2023	5 - 100	1	md	OSTLUFT, 2025

Amsterdam Schiphol airport (AMS) is one of the largest airports in Table 2.1 with 436 967 flights in 2023. A project by TNO (Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research) with a grant of RIVM (National Institute for Public Health and the Environment) conducted a measurement campaign of UFP at 10 locations near Amsterdam airport from 2017 – 2018, with mostly six month duration at the single stations for PNC and for some weeks for Mobility Particle Size Spectrometers (MPSS). It was important for this study to document the comparability of Condensation Particle Counter (CPC), to validate and improve a model to map UFP exposure concentrations around AMS airport. Measurements showed that the closer the sampling point was to the airport, the higher was the recorded UFP concentration, with a maximum average for the monitoring period above 35 000 particles/cm³ (Vogt et al., 2019). Particularly, UFP smaller than 20 nm were found when the main source was the airport (Dinther et al., 2019). During the May–July 2021 measurement campaign, background ultrafine particle (UFP) concentrations near Schiphol averaged around 10 000 particles/cm³, significantly lower than levels measured on the airport terrain, confirming that local emissions dominate. At the Oude Meer station (about 1 km from Schiphol), 2-months mean concentrations reached 16 300 particles/cm³ when wind came from the airport, while Oorkmeer (about 5 km away) recorded 11 700 particles/cm³ under similar conditions (Tromp et al., 2021). The measurements of UFP at 8 km distance from AMS showed an average of about 9 000 particles/cm³, over the 2 years monitoring period. The total PNC was observed to increase by 34% when the wind was blowing from AMS compared to all other wind directions. The AMS airport potentially contributed up to 5% of total PNC and 16% of 10–20 nm particles 8 km downwind of the airport (2 years sampling 2013-2014, Hofman et al. 2016).

With 166 100 flights per year in 2023 (Table 2.1), the Berlin Brandenburg airport (BER) is a middle sized airport among those selected in this report, the 2nd largest airport in Germany. Federal State Agency Brandenburg (Landesamt für Umwelt Brandenburg, LfU) conducted measurements with CPC and MPSS, which are the standard methods for determining the PNC and the PNSD. CPC measurements are conducted since 2021 in Mahlow, 4 km SW of the airport, both CPC and MPSS measurements were made in Wildau, 7.5 km SW of the airport, for 2024 until middle 2025 (Brauer, 2025). Also, the airport company has been conducting CPC and MPSS measurements 1 km NE of the runway since 2020. Measurements showed that the BER airport contribution to the total UFP concentration was significantly higher than the contribution of motor vehicle traffic up to around 7 km downwind of the terminal, even when measuring on busy roads (Gerling and Weber, 2023). Innovative drone measurements up to an altitude of 700 metres were able to validate the airport dispersion-model. The airport influence was visible for particles with diameter below 40 nm. At 10-20 nm particle concentrations with wind from the airport was approx. 3-4 times higher compared to wind from other directions. Most of the UFP from the airport are volatile, for example 56% in the Mahlow monitoring station. No clear influence of the airport was found for larger particle diameters as well as for soot mass and PM₁₀.

Brussels airport (BRU) is a middle-sized airport in table 2.1 with 180 376 flights in 2023. VMM (Vlaamse Milieumaatschappij) performed measurements of UFP at four sites for two months on a linear transect upwind and downwind in the prevailing wind direction of the Airport of Brussels. Two measurement sites were located close to the airport (< 750 m), while two others were farther away (at 5 km and at 7 km). The highest average particle concentration was observed near the airport, 18 000 particles/cm³ and 17 000 particles/cm³, followed by 10 000 particles/cm³ and 8 000 particles/cm³ measured at the more distant sites. These measurements were later used by modeling studies to gain more insight into the exposure of residents near Brussels Airport to UFP, and the contribution of air traffic to this exposure (Lefebvre et al., 2019; Garcia-Marles et al., 2025; see also Box 6.2 for more details).

Copenhagen airport (CPH) is a middle-sized airport with 222 068 flights in 2023 (Table 2.1). During a project of the Danish Centre for Environment and Energy (DCE) 2022-2024 using a measurement vehicle, air concentrations of ultrafine particles and nitrogen dioxide were monitored along a fixed

route near the airport. The estimated annual mean value directly north of the airport was 27 000 particles/cm³. The maximum 15-minutes average reached 200 000 particles/cm³. The measurements indicated that the airport accounted for 50-90% of UFP near the measuring stations (Ellermann et al., 2024).

Düsseldorf (DUS) has with 143 567 flights per year in 2023 almost the same flight amount as BER. Federal state agency LANUK (Landesamt für Natur, Umwelt und Klima Nordrhein-Westfalen) has been conducting UFP measurements since 2020 at 2 km SW of the airport in a residential area (Düsseldorf-Lohhausen) (Grosse Schute, 2025).

Frankfurt/Main airport (FRA) is the 3rd largest airport by number of flights in Europe in 2023 with 422 275 flights per year (Table 2.1). Continuous CPC and MPSS measurements are conducted since 2017 by the federal State Agency for Nature Conservation, Environment and Geology (HLNUG). Nowadays one active site is measuring at the airport and two within 10 km around the airport of the main wind directions (Schwanheim, Raunheim) (HLNUG 2025). In the city of Frankfurt, another three stations are measuring UFP inside a circle of 20 km from the airport. Measurements (HLNUG, 2020) showed that the concentration of particles in the main wind direction from the airport decreased during the COVID19 pandemic by 58% in the nearest sampling point to the airport (Schwanheim, 20 900 particles/cm³ and 8 800 particles/cm³), with a 64% decrease in the number of passenger flights in 2020 compared to 2019 (Eurostat). The reduction of UFP when wind was blowing from the airport correlated with the reduction in flight movements. The characteristics of emissions from flight operations, such as particle size distribution and concentration variations, have been clearly identified at monitoring sites, showing a significant impact on UFP levels, particularly near the airport. These distinctive features in UFP emissions are influenced by wind direction, with a notable peak for particles smaller than 30 nm. The 'fingerprint' of emissions can be detected up to 14 km away from the airport, with the influence diminishing exponentially (HLNUG, 2022). One-year measurements east of the airport (in Neu-Isenburg during 2022 and 2023) showed PNC (10-500 nm) of 7 400 particles/cm³. Analysis of flight operations' impact on particle concentration revealed higher levels (approx. 10 200 particles/cm³) when the wind was coming from the airport. A cluster analysis of measured air pollutants and particle distribution identified two primary sources of particles from air traffic: ground-level emissions from taxi-operations and partly take-offs; emissions from landing aircraft. Ground-level emissions, especially in westerly winds, led to high concentration values and a broad distribution in the 10-30 nm size range, whereas emissions from landing aircraft above 400 metres contributed less to particle concentration. In Neu-Isenburg, the WHO reference level (WHO, 2021) of high hourly concentrations (20 000 particles/cm³) was exceeded 3% and the reference level of high daily concentrations (10 000 particles/cm³) 22% of the time (HLNUG, 2024). Over the 12-month period from May 2023 to April 2024, the Schwanheim station, about 2.5 km north of Frankfurt Airport recorded a mean PNC of 13 600 particles/cm³, with peaks reaching up to 33 000 particles/cm³ under prevailing south to southwest winds, which frequently transport emissions from the airport. These values are substantially higher than those measured at more distant sites, highlighting the strong influence of airport operations on local UFP levels (HLNUG, 2025). The impact in the communities in the immediate vicinity of the airport is primarily dominated by the horizontal displacement of ground-level emissions on the airport site and along the low approach routes (below 400 m flight altitude) (HLNUG, 2025).

Helsinki-Vantaa airport (HEL) is a small to middle-sized airport of the selected 23 airports with 135 788 flights in 2023. HSY (Helsinki Region Environmental Services Authority), a Finnish network in the Helsinki capital region, has measured AQ at the airport, near the passenger terminal, every 5 years. The latest measurement was in 2022 at the airport station (Lentoasema) situated at a kerb side of a road to the terminal halls. Measurements of indicative PNC were conducted with low-cost sensor, for which the lower size limit of the particles is not precisely defined, but measurements begin at particle sizes slightly below 10 nm. Largest indicative PNC values were recorded near the airport with annual average of 22 700 particles/cm³. Measurements of indicative PNC in traffic environment

ranged between 7 000 and 18 700 particles/cm³, between 5 000 and 5 900 particles/cm³ in residential areas, 5 200 particles/cm³ at urban background station, and 3 600 particles/cm³ at rural background station. Beside PNC, also an alternative metric for health effect of particles lung deposable surface area (LDSA) was measured. The LDSA measured the surface area of particles in the 10 – 400 nm size range. At the airport, concentrations varied greatly in line with flights and car traffic frequency at and around the airport, with high concentrations on both weekdays and weekends. The annual average LDSA concentration was highest in the busy traffic area near the airport, 18.3 µm²/cm³, compared to 10.7 – 17.6 µm²/cm³ in traffic areas, 7.7 – 9.4 µm²/cm³ in residential areas, and 6.2 µm²/cm³ at a background station (Korhonen et al., 2023).

Paris Charles de Gaulle (CDG) airport is the biggest airport of the 23 selected airports in this assessment, with 446 185 flights in 2023. In a project by AIRPARIF, which started in 2019 measurement sites inside the airport and at distances of 1 km, 5 km and 10 km in a NE direction. Measured annual averages of UFP resulted respectively in 23 000; 17 900; 6 200 and 7 400 particles/cm³. The average concentration of ultrafine particles at the airport is comparable with levels along the ring road (AIRPARIF, 2024). An air quality source apportionment study is currently ongoing in the frame of the OLGA European project to identify the various sources of airport emissions and their contribution to urban air quality at CDG. This study includes 6 to 8 three-months campaigns at two air quality monitoring sites at CDG, including UFP.

Vienna airport (VIE) is a middle-sized airport of the selected 23 airports with 219 339 flights in 2023. Umweltbundesamt Austria measures UFP since 2022 by MPSS (4-300 nm). Two measuring stations are installed, one at 2.5 km NW of the airport at a refinery and chemical industry and another 800 m SE in a rural residential area. Annual means in 2022 were respectively 15 000 and 10 900 particles/cm³ (Buxbaum et al., 2025). Maximum of 30-minutes average larger than 100 000 particles/cm³ was measured when the wind came from the airport. In 2023 and 2024 similar annual mean concentrations were measured, around 16,000 and 11,000 particles/cm³ respectively. The UFP concentrations measured near the airport of Vienna (VIE) are higher than in the urban background in Vienna and Graz and significantly higher than in Illmitz (rural background). The measurement results show that emissions from air traffic at both measuring points determine the UFP concentrations (Buxbaum et al., 2025).

Zurich (ZRH) is also a middle-sized airport of the selected airports with 213 400 flights in 2023 (Table 2.1). Since 2020 permanent measurements of CPC and MPSS (5 – 100 nm) take place at Kloten inside of a residential area about 1 km east of the airport with annual reports and data available via website (OSTLUFT, 2025; Kanton Zurich, 2025). On average 24 000 particles/cm³ were found in the year 2023 of which 48 % were attributed to the airport. Maximum 10-minutes average concentration up to 500 000 particles/cm³ was measured.

Apart from the selected airport in this report, there are more examples showcasing the increasing concern of UFP levels around airports. For example, the Free State of Bavaria the University Bayreuth measured UFP at 2 km SE and 3 km NW of the airport of Munich (MUC). In a one-year period between 2021 and 2022, the annual mean of 7 900 cm⁻³ (10-800 nm) and a maximum 5-minute average of 190 000 cm⁻³ were measured (Nölscher, 2025; Seidler et al., 2024)

Box 6.2 Modelling UFP concentrations

Different types of models can be used for calculating UFP concentrations:

- **Dispersion** (Gaussian models, Lagrangian models, Eulerian models / Chemical Transport Models (CTMs): Spatially resolved, need detailed emission inventories and meteorological data.
- **Statistical** (Land-use regression (LUR): Needs spatial predictors (e.g. distance to runways). Has limited insight into transport or transformation processes.
- **Receptor** (Source-Apportionment Models) Positive Matrix Factorisation (PMF), Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Trajectory-based models: Use air mass history to assess source regions.
- **Hybrid.** Combining different models and/or measurements. i.e. PMF with airport data or CTM with local dispersion models.

For modelling the dispersion of UFP from airports often dispersion models are used. The Lagrangian model LASPORT is used in the EU research project AVIATOR for the dispersion modelling of non-volatile and volatile UFP (Winkler et al., 2025). Also, combinations of different model types are used, i.e. Chemical transport model (CTM), using chemical transformations and physical processes, for resolutions down to 0.5 km x 0.5 km combined with dispersion models of lower resolution of typically 50 m x 50 m (Lorentz et al., 2019; Winkler et al., 2025). Additionally, UFP background concentrations from measurements can be added (Manders et al., 2025).

Other examples are Zurich, Mesoscale Eulerian weather model and Lagrangian dispersion model (Zhang et al., 2020), Brussel, Gaussian Plume model (Lefebvre et al., 2019) and Amsterdam, Gaussian Plume model (Keuken et al., 2015). Receptor-modelling techniques operate at measurement sites (receptors) and attribute pollution to sources based on measured chemical/physical profile. (i.e Brussels: Garcia-Marlès et al., 2025).

The “Ultra-fine dust pollution from airports in Berlin” (ULTRAFLEB) Project made stationary and mobile measurements as well as a model evaluation of UFP in the vicinity of Berlin Brandenburg Airport BER. The CTM-Lagrange hybrid model was applied to an area of 60 km x 60 km at a resolution of 500 m and partly down to 50 m for annual means for years 2019-2023 (Winkler et al., 2025). Model results are delivered to the epidemiologic study BEAR (The Berlin Airport Study – a natural experiment investigating health effects from changes in airport-related exposures, KoPilot).

In ULTRAFLEB project, modeling results show continuous decrease in UFP concentrations with increasing distance from the airport. The example below shows the impact of Tegel airport in Berlin on UFP in 2019, before the COVID19 pandemic (smaller impact is visible from the Brandenburg airport, which became the single airport in Berlin in 2020). In 2022 the impact of Tegel airport disappears after its closure in 2020, while it is possible to see the impact on UFP concentrations from the renovated Brandenburg airport (BER) in the south east of the city, with simulated annual mean concentrations above 10 000 particles/cm³ in the vicinity of the airport, declining to 4 000 particles/cm³ within about 5 km (Map 6.1).

Airport contribution to UFP concentrations can be up to up to 50% in the vicinity of the airport and falls after a few kilometres distance from the airport significantly below the contribution of the other sources (Map 6.2). The validation resulted in a deviation of 10% to 200% between station measurements and model results if compared on monthly basis.

Map 6.1 Results from ULTRAFLEB: Total UFP concentrations in a region of 60 km x 60 km at 500 m x 500 m resolution around Berlin for 2019 with airport Tegel in operation (left) and 2022 (right) with Tegel closed (Winkler et al., 2025).

Map 6.2 Average percentage contribution to UFP concentrations from car traffic (a) and airport (b) in a region of 60 km x 60 km at 500 m x 500 m resolution around Berlin (Winkler and et al., 2025).

Other modeling studies were conducted for example for the airports of Frankfurt (FRA), Brussels (BRU) and Zurich (ZRH).

Frankfurt (FRA): a modelling study (Lorentz et al., 2019) was carried out at this airport using a hybrid model (combination of a Chemical Transport Models (CTM) and a Lagrangian model) with an area of 35 km x 35 km and a horizontal resolution from 500 meters down to 100 meters to simulate the annual mean UFP concentrations of the year 2015. It showed that the main source of UFP from airports stem from the main engines on the ground i.e. by taxi movements of the aircraft on the runways. The results underestimated the UFP, because for flight operations, only the non-volatile particles (essentially soot) were considered. Airport operations outside the airport premises, within 1 km, are responsible for up to 25% of the total number of particles, especially in main wind directions in NE and SW, but dropping to below 10% at 2.5 km away.

Brussels (BRU): VITO (Vlaamse Instelling voor Technologisch Onderzoek) modelled UFP from 10 - 100 nm in an area of 20 km around Brussels Airport on base of 2 months measurements in 2015 at four stations (Table 6.1). It was found that the airport is a major contributor to UFP, but UFP were also elevated along busy roads such as the Brussels Ring Road. The calculated contributions of air traffic and local road traffic to UFP depend on the location of a site in relation to the airport and roads. Results show that aviation contributes up to 62% of UFP concentrations in certain areas. The study also notes similar daily cycles for road traffic and aviation, with air traffic playing a more crucial role during times of elevated UFP concentrations. In general, at times of high UFP concentrations, the relative contribution of air traffic is more important (up to 78%), while the relative contribution of local road traffic remained about the same (Lefebvre et al., 2019). It was also found that airport sources contributed 6 500–14 000 cm⁻³ near the airport and take-off emissions were generally coarser (20 nm) than taxiing (12 nm). Near the airport 65% of the total PNC particles were dominated by smallest measured particles (10-20 nm). The airport's contribution to UFP was noticeable to at least 7 km especially for the smallest particles, with 30-min peak contributions ranging from 4 000 to 9 000 particles/cm³ (Garcia-Marles et al., 2025, STARGATE and RI-URBANS EU projects). VITO works together with Brussels Airport Company on air quality modelling, source apportionment and impact of measures. Besides AQ modelling, UFP measurement campaigns have been conducted and will be repeated. Only limited material is currently available, however.

Zurich (ZRH): the atmospheric dispersion model system GRAMM (meteorology at 300 m horizontal resolution) /GRAL (atmospheric transport at 20 m horizontal resolution) was offline coupled with the aerosol dynamics model MAFOR to calculate the hourly particle number concentrations induced by the aircraft emissions for the surrounding communities. The number concentrations attributable to the airport were 10⁴–10⁵ particles/cm³ for the communities close to the airport. The output analysed with a statistical model trained with measurements, showed an annual mean particle number concentration in Zurich of about 8 000 particles/cm³; the particle number concentrations in communities close to the airport were increased by a factor of 2–10 compared to the background level (Zhang et al., 2020).

7 Conclusions

This study examined air quality at 23 European airports chosen based on air traffic volume in 2023, geographical coverage across EEA member countries, population density near airports, and information on ongoing and recent UFP monitoring activities. The selected airports include major hubs such as Frankfurt (FRA), Paris Charles De Gaulle (CDG), and Amsterdam Schiphol (AMS), representing diverse regions from northern to southern and eastern to western Europe. Several airports were prioritized due to their proximity to densely populated areas, with some exceeding one million inhabitants within 10 km. Information on ongoing and recent UFP monitoring activities was gathered through EIONET's Thematic Group on Air, complemented by literature reviews and European research projects.

The analysis combined observational data, meteorological information, and high-resolution air quality maps to assess air quality near European airports. Three pollutants were analysed, NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃, for year 2023, corresponding to the latest validated data reported by EEA members and cooperating countries (E1a, validated data AQ e-Reporting). Sampling points (SPOs) with sufficient data coverage were identified within airport areas and at varying distances (up to 50 km, depending on the air pollutant). Wind direction frequencies were analysed to distinguish conditions when air pollution levels measured at the SPOs could originate from airports. Hourly pollutant measurements were compared under two scenarios: wind from the airport versus other directions, providing preliminary indications of airport-related impacts. To address gaps in monitoring coverage, EEA high-resolution air quality maps (1 km × 1 km) were used to evaluate annual mean concentrations of NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak season levels within airport areas and surrounding regions. Comparisons were made between airport areas, regional backgrounds, and different land cover classes to quantify spatial differences.

The assessment revealed substantial variability in monitoring air quality near European airports:

- 11 airports lack any NO₂ monitoring sites within 5 km distance, while others had between one and three. Only three airports had stations inside the airport area, and eight had sites within 1 km. All airports had at least one station within 10 km, but coverage ranged widely—from a single site to eight. Monitoring sites included different area types (Background, Traffic, Industrial), with most airports having at least one background station. Wind-sector analysis showed uneven directional coverage: some airports (e.g., Lisbon, Madrid) had stations in up to five sectors, while others had minimal representation, reducing the ability to capture airport-related impacts under varying wind conditions.
- 15 airports lack any PM_{2.5} monitoring sites within 5 km distance, while others have only one–two sites. Only Dublin has a station inside the airport, and four airports have sites within 1 km. Coverage improves at larger distances: most airports have at least one station within 10 km, and nine airports have 10 or more SPOs within 20 km (up to 18 for Dublin). Vilnius (VNO) is the only airport without any PM_{2.5} monitoring within 20 km. Most airports have background SPOs within 20 km, and several have mixed types (background, traffic, industrial). Wind-sector analysis shows airports like Madrid and Warsaw have SPOs in six sectors, covering up to 87% of wind frequency, while others have minimal representation (10–28%).
- 14 airports lack any O₃ monitoring within 5 km, while most have at least one station within 10 km. Only Dublin has a station inside the airport, and five airports have sites within 1 km. Coverage increases significantly at larger distances: up to 18 SPOs within 20 km and as many as 37 within 50 km for some airports. Background SPOs dominate reflecting O₃ secondary formation and its regional nature. Due to the larger distance analysed for O₃ SPOs, wind-sector analysis indicates strong directional coverage: six airports have SPOs in all eight sectors, and 16 airports achieve more than 50% cumulative wind frequency, enhancing representativeness.

The study examined hourly pollutant data (NO₂, PM_{2.5}, O₃) and wind directions for 2023 to assess potential airport-related impacts. Concentrations at monitoring sites were compared under downwind versus non-downwind conditions across eight wind sectors:

- For NO₂, 18 of 23 airports showed at least one sector with more than 10% increase under downwind conditions, with differences ranging from 14% (Zurich) to 143% (Lisbon). Several airports (Lisbon, Amsterdam, Paris CDG, Madrid, Rome, Brussels) exhibited consistent and significant increases, in some cases exceeding 80%.
- For PM_{2.5}, 15 airports showed increases above 10%, with the highest differences reaching 57% (Brussels). Notable cases include Brussels, Frankfurt, Helsinki, and Prague, with multiple sectors showing elevated concentrations.
- For O₃, 17 airports exhibited increases above 10%, with extreme cases up to 95% (Rome). Airports such as Rome, Barcelona, and Milan showed frequent and substantial increases across multiple wind sectors.

Overall, the analysis indicates that pollutant concentrations are potentially higher under downwind conditions for many airports, suggesting possible contributions from airport-related activities. However, variability across wind sectors and distances, as well as influence from other pollution sources in the area, must be considered when interpreting these results.

Due to limited and uneven monitoring coverage inside and near airports, deriving robust conclusions solely from measurements was challenging. To address this, EEA high-resolution air quality maps (1 km × 1 km), which integrate chemistry transport model simulations, reported measurements, meteorology, and land cover data, were used to compare pollutant concentrations in airport areas with surrounding regions and for different land cover classes. Overall, the map-based analysis provides evidence of elevated NO₂ and PM_{2.5} levels in airport areas compared to surrounding regions, while O₃ remains largely regional in nature:

- The maps reveal that NO₂ concentrations were consistently higher in airport areas than in regional backgrounds, with differences larger than 10 µg/m³ in Milan (LIN) and Madrid (MAD), up to 13.4 µg/m³ in Lisbon (LIS). The NO₂ annual mean concentration in Milan (24.7 µg/m³) was above the limit value to be attained by 2030 (LV₂₀₃₀) set in the revised Directive (EU, 2024), while Lisbon and Madrid approach it.
- For PM_{2.5}, airport concentrations exceed regional levels in most cases, though differences are smaller (up to 2.9 µg/m³). Six airports had levels above 10 µg/m³, the revised annual limit value to be attained in 2030 (LV₂₀₃₀), with Milan (19.3 µg/m³) and Bucharest (16.9 µg/m³) among the highest. Some airports also had levels above this threshold typical of high-density residential areas.
- O₃ peak season concentrations are similar between airports and regional backgrounds, ranging from 72 to 113 µg/m³, well above the updated WHO guidelines (WHO, 2021).

Long-term trends (2005-2023) of NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ levels were analysed at the identified SPOs in European airports and nearby cities. From one to six SPOs with long-term trend (2005-2023) within a 10 km radius of the airport were identified for NO₂ at 19 airports. For PM_{2.5}, from one to seven SPOs with long-term trend within a 20 km radius from the airport were identified at 18 airports. For O₃, from 1 to 25 SPOs with long-term trend within a 50 km radius from the airport were identified in 21 airports. In general, for NO₂ the mean decrease from 2005 to 2023 was around 45% for both nearby (within 5km) and more distant monitoring locations. Long-term trends in PM_{2.5} concentrations near airports show substantial reductions across all distance ranges and station types, though the robustness of these estimates varies with sample size. Analysis of long-term trends in O₃ concentrations indicates a consistent increase across all distance ranges from airports, around 23% between 0-5 km and 5-20 km distance ranges, 15% between 20-50 km.

UFP, measured as particle number concentration (PNC), are emerging pollutants of concern due to their ability to penetrate deep into the lungs and potentially enter the bloodstream, posing distinct health risks. Although formal guideline values are lacking, WHO considers concentrations above 10,000 particles/cm³ (24-hour mean) or 20,000 particles/cm³ (hourly) as high. The revised EU directive now mandates UFP monitoring at supersites and in high-concentration areas, including airports. Measurements at several major European airports show annual averages exceeding 20,000 particles/cm³ within 1 km of airport operations, well above the WHO's daily and hourly reference levels. Concentrations decline rapidly with distance, typically falling below 10,000 particles/cm³ beyond 5–10 km. However, WHO reference levels apply to UFP measured with a minimum size of 10 making direct comparisons problematic for some of the airports analysed in this report. Wind direction significantly influences dispersion, with airport-related contributions detected up to 7–8 km downwind. These findings highlight airport activities as a significant source of UFP at local level and underscore the need for standardized monitoring protocols and strategic station placement to assess population exposure.

List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Name	Reference
AAQD	Ambient air quality directive	
AGR	Agricultural areas	
AMS	IATA code of Amsterdam airport	
AQ	Air quality	
AQG	Air Quality Guidelines	
ATH	IATA code of Athens airport	
BCN	IATA code of Barcelona airport	
BER	IATA code of Berlin airport	
BRU	IATA code of Brussels airport	
CDG	IATA code of Paris Charles de Gaulle airport	
CH ₄	Methane	
CLC2018	CORINE Land Cover 2018	https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/corine-land-cover/clc2018
CO	Carbon monoxide	
CPC	Condensation particle counter	
CPH	IATA code of Copenhagen airport	
CTM	Chemical transport model	
DUB	IATA code of Dublin airport	
DUS	IATA code of Dusseldorf airport	
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency	https://www.easa.europa.eu/en
EEA	European Environment Agency	www.eea.europa.eu
EIONET	European Environment Information and Observation Network	https://www.eionet.europa.eu/
FCO	IATA code of Rome Fiumicino airport	
FRA	IATA code of Frankfurt airport	
HAM	IATA code of Hamburg airport	
HDR	High density residential areas	
HEL	IATA code of Helsinki airport	
IATA	International Air Transport Association	
IND	Industry	
ISD	Integrated Surface Database	https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/products/land-based-station/integrated-surface-database
JRC	Joint Research Centre	
LDR	Low density residential areas	
LDSA	Lung deposable surface area	
LIN	IATA code of Milan Linate airport	
LIS	IATA code of Lisbon airport	
LV ₂₀₃₀	Limit value to be attained by 2030	
MAD	IATA code of Madrid airport	
MPSS	Mobility Particle Size Spectrometers	
NAT	Natural areas	

NH ₃	Ammonia
NMVOOC	Non methane volatile organic compound
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration https://www.noaa.gov/
NO ₂	Nitrogen dioxide
NO _x	Nitrogen oxides
NPF	New particle formation
NUC	Nucleation mode particles
O ₃	Ozone
ORY	IATA code of Paris Orly airport
OTP	IATA code of Bucharest airport
PM ₁₀	Particulate matter which passes through a size-selective inlet with a 50% efficiency cut-off at 10 µm aerodynamic diameter
PM _{2.5}	Particulate matter which passes through a size-selective inlet with a 50% efficiency cut-off at 2.5 µm aerodynamic diameter
PNC	Particle number concentration
PNSD	Particle number size distribution
PRG	IATA code of Prague airport
SO ₂	Sulphur dioxide
SO _x	Sulphur oxides
SPO	Sampling point observation
TG AIR	Thematic Group on Air
TV ₂₀₃₀	Target value to be attained by 2030
TRAF	Traffic
UFP	Ultrafine particles
VIE	IATA code of Vienna airport
VNO	IATA code of Vilnius airport
WAW	IATA code of Warsaw airport
WHO	World Health Organization
WS	Wind sectors: North (N); Northeast (NE); East (E); Southeast (SE); South (S); Southwest (SW); West (W); Northwest (NW)
ZRH	IATA code of Zurich airport

References

- AIRPARIF, 2024, 'Mesure de particules ultrafines autour de l'aéroport de Paris-Charles-de-Gaulle', (<https://www.airparif.fr/etudes/2024/etude-mesure-de-particules-ultrafines-autour-de-laeroport-de-paris-charles-de-gaulle>) accessed 5 June 2025.
- Batista e Silva, F., 2021, 'JRC-GEOSTAT 2018 Population Grid Dataset. Version 2021.02.10', European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC), DG REGIO (https://gisco-services.ec.europa.eu/pub/population-grid/2018/v2021.02.10/JRC-GEOSTAT_2018_TechnicalFactsheet.pdf) accessed 23 November 2025
- Bousiotis, D., et al., 2021, 'The effect of meteorological conditions and atmospheric composition in the occurrence and development of new particle formation (NPF) events in Europe', Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics 21(5), pp. 3345-3370 (DOI: 10.5194/acp-21-3345-2021).
- Brauer, H. 2025, Brandenburger Pilotmessung der UFP-Größenverteilung mit MPSS und CPC im Vergleich zu Handheld (DCAM)-Geräten, 60. Messtechnisches Kolloquium, LANUK, Karlsruhe.
- Brock, C. A., et al., 2000, 'Ultrafine particle size distributions measured in aircraft exhaust plumes', Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres 105(D21), pp. 26555-26567 (DOI: 10.1029/2000JD900360).
- Buxbaum, I., et al., 2025, 'UFP-Messungen Flughafen Wien: Messergebnisse 2022 bis 2024', Umweltbundesamt, Wien (<https://www.umweltbundesamt.at/fileadmin/site/publikationen/rep0977.pdf>) accessed 23 November 2025
- Carslaw, D. C. and Ropkins, K., 2012, 'openair --- an R package for air quality data analysis', Environmental Modelling & Software. Volume 27-28, 52-61 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2011.09.008>)
- Chen, Y., et al., 2022, 'Long-term trends of ultrafine and fine particle number concentrations in New York State: Apportioning between emissions and dispersion', Environmental Pollution 310, p. 119797 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envpol.2022.119797).
- CONCAWE, 2023, 'The impact of aviation emissions to urban air quality in Europe' (https://www.concawe.eu/wp-content/uploads/Rpt_23-10.pdf) accessed 23 November 2025.
- Dinther, D. van, et al., 2019, 'Metingen van aantallen ultrafijnstofdeeltjes rond Schiphol gedurende ruim één jaar', No TNO R.10591, TNO (<https://open.overheid.nl/documenten/ronl-083e86f0-2266-45e2-bf11-9eb14841ca15/pdf>) accessed 23 November 2025.
- EASA, 2025, 'European Aviation Environmental Report 2025' (<https://www.easa.europa.eu/en/light/topics/european-aviation-environmental-report-2025>) accessed 23 November 2025.
- EEA, 2024a, 'Sustainability of Europe's mobility systems -Air pollution' (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/sustainability-of-europes-mobility-systems/air-pollution>) accessed 14 July 2025.
- EEA, 2024b, 'Emissions of air pollutants from transport in Europe' (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/indicators/emissions-of-air-pollutants-from>) accessed 14 July 2025.
- EEA, 2025, 'Air quality status report 2025' (<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/publications/air-quality-status-report-2025>) accessed 2 July 2025.

- Ellermann, T. et al., 2024, 'MÅLING AF PARTIKELFORURENINGEN OMKRING KØBENHAVNS LUFTHAVN I KASTRUP', Universitet, DCE – Nationalt Center for Miljø og Energi, 82 s. - Videnskabelig rapport nr. 599 (https://dce.au.dk/fileadmin/dce.au.dk/Udgivelser/Videnskabelige_rapporter_500-599/SR599.pdf) accessed 23 November 2025.
- Emeis, S., et al., 2008, 'Surface-based remote sensing of the mixing-layer height a review', Meteorologische Zeitschrift, pp. 621-630 (DOI: 10.1127/0941-2948/2008/0312).
- EU, 2024, Directive (EU) 2024/2881 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 23 October 2024 on ambient air quality and cleaner air for Europe (recast) (OJ L, 2024/2881, 20.11.2024).
- EUROSTAT, 2023a, 'Air passenger transport statistics' (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Air_passenger_transport_statistics) accessed 4 September 2025.
- EUROSTAT, 2023b, 'Air freight transport statistics' (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Air_freight_transport_statistics) accessed 4 September 2025.
- Garcia-Marlès, M., et al., 2024, 'Source apportionment of ultrafine particles in urban Europe', Environment International 194, p. 109149 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2024.109149).
- Garcia-Marlès, M., et al., 2025, 'Spatiotemporal variation and source apportionment of ultrafine particles near Brussels Airport (Belgium)', Atmospheric Environment 359, p. 121375 (DOI: 10.1016/j.atmosenv.2025.121375).
- Gbangou, T. and Colette, A., 2023, 'Long-term trends of air pollutants at European and national level 2005-2021' (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2023/8). European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10624581>) accessed 13/12/2024.
- Gerling, L. and Weber, S., 2023, 'Mobile measurements of atmospheric pollutant concentrations in the pollutant plume of BER airport', Atmospheric Environment 304, p. 119770 (DOI: 10.1016/j.atmosenv.2023.119770).
- Gerwig, H., et al., 2025, 'Six-Year Trend of Concentrations of Ultrafine Particles Six Kilometres Away from a Major German Airport', Aerosol Research Discuss. 2025, pp. 1-21 (DOI: 10.5194/ar-2025-32).
- Grosse Schute, L., 2025, QM bei UFP-Messungen, 60. Messtechnisches Kolloquium, LANUK, Karlsruhe.
- Harrison, R. M., et al., 2019, 'Interpretation of particle number size distributions measured across an urban area during the FASTER campaign', Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics 19(1), pp. 39-55 (DOI: 10.5194/acp-19-39-2019).
- Hellack, B., et al., 2022, 'Ultrafeine Partikel Verursacher, Messung und Wirkungsbewertung', UBA-Texte No 126/2022 (https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/479/publikationen/texte_126-2022_ultrafeine-partikel_0.pdf) accessed 27 June 2025.
- HLNUG, 2020, '3. Bericht zur Untersuchung der regionalen Luftqualität auf ultrafeine Partikel im Bereich des Flughafens Frankfurt', Landesamt für Naturschutz, Umwelt und Geologie (HLNUG), (https://www.hlnug.de/fileadmin/dokumente/luft/sonstige_berichte/ufp/UFP_Bericht_Teil3_2020_1016.pdf) accessed 23 November 2025.
- HLNUG, 2022, '4. Bericht zur Untersuchung der regionalen Luftqualität auf ultrafeine Partikel im Bereich des Flughafens Frankfurt', Hessisches Landesamt für Naturschutz, Umwelt und Geologie (HLNUG), (<https://www.hlnug.de/fileadmin/dokumente/luft/luftqualitaet/sondermessprogramme/ufp/UFP-Bericht-4.pdf>) accessed 23 November 2025.

HLNUG, 2024, 'Temporäre Luftschadstoffmessungen in Neu-Isenburg', Hessisches Landesamt für Naturschutz, Umwelt und Geologie (HLNUG), (https://www.hlnug.de/fileadmin/dokumente/luft/luftqualitaet/sondermessprogramme/ufp/Kurzbericht_UFP-Messungen_Neu-Isenburg.pdf) accessed 23 November 2025.

HLNUG, 2025, 'Abschlussbericht Temporäre Luftschadstoffmessungen in Mainz-Hechtsheim', Hessisches Landesamt für Naturschutz, Umwelt und Geologie (HLNUG), (https://www.hlnug.de/fileadmin/dokumente/luft/luftqualitaet/sondermessprogramme/ufp/Abschlussbericht_Mainz_Hechtsheim.pdf) accessed 23 November 2025.

Hofman, J., et al., 2016, 'Ultrafine particles in four European urban environments: Results from a new continuous long-term monitoring network', Atmospheric Environment, Volume 136, July 2016, Pages 68-81 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2016.04.010>).

Hopke, P. K., et al., 2022, 'Source apportionment of particle number concentrations: A global review', Science of The Total Environment 819, p. 153104 (DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.153104).

Horalek et al., 2025, 'Air quality maps of EEA member and cooperating countries for 2023. PM10, PM2.5, O3, NO2, NOx and BaP spatial estimates and their uncertainties', (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2025/5). European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17427294>) accessed 21 November 2025.

Hudda, N., et al., 2014, 'Emissions from an International Airport Increase Particle Number Concentrations 4-fold at 10 km Downwind', Environmental Science & Technology 48(12), pp. 6628-6635 (DOI: 10.1021/es5001566).

Hudda, N., et al., 2018, 'Aviation-Related Impacts on Ultrafine Particle Number Concentrations Outside and Inside Residences near an Airport', Environmental Science & Technology 52(4), pp. 1765-1772 (DOI: 10.1021/acs.est.7b05593).

Junkermann, W., et al., 2016, 'Ultrafine particles over Germany – an aerial survey', Tellus B: Chemical and Physical Meteorology 68(1), p. 29250 (DOI: 10.3402/tellusb.v68.29250).

Junkermann, W. and Hacker, J. M., 2018, 'Ultrafine Particles in the Lower Troposphere: Major Sources, Invisible Plumes, and Meteorological Transport Processes', (DOI: 10.1175/BAMS-D-18-0075.1).

Kanton Zurich, 2025, 'Datenkatalog', Kanton Zürich (<https://www.zh.ch/de/politik-staat/statistik-daten/datenkatalog.html>) accessed 5 June 2025.

Kerminen, V.-M., et al., 2018, 'Atmospheric new particle formation and growth: review of field observations', Environmental Research Letters 13(10), p. 103003 (DOI: 10.1088/1748-9326/aadf3c).

Keuken, M. P., et al., 2015, 'Total and size-resolved particle number and black carbon concentrations in urban areas near Schiphol airport (the Netherlands)', Atmospheric Environment 104, pp. 132-142 (DOI: 10.1016/j.atmosenv.2015.01.015).

Korhonen, S., et al., 2023, 'Ilmanlaatu pääkaupunkiseudulla vuonna 2022', No HSY:n julkaisuja 1/2023, Helsinki Region Environmental Services Authority (<https://julkaisu.hsy.fi/pdf/ilmanlaatu-paakaupunkiseudulla-vuonna-2022.pdf>). accessed 23 November 2025.

Lefebvre, W., et al., 2019, 'Modellering van ultrafijn stof door luchtverkeer en wegverkeer rond Brussels Airport', 2019/RMA/R/1916, p. 49.

Lorentz, H., et al., 2019, 'Ultrafine particle dispersion modelling at and around Frankfurt airport (FRA), GERMANY' (<https://www.harmo.org/Conferences/Proceedings/Bruges/publishedSections/H19-082%20Helmut%20Lorentz.pdf>). Accessed 23 November 2025.

- Ma, N. and Birmili, W., 2015, 'Estimating the contribution of photochemical particle formation to ultrafine particle number averages in an urban atmosphere', *Science of The Total Environment* 512-513, pp. 154-166 (DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.01.009).
- Manders, A. and et al., 2025, 'Ultrafine particle concentrations in Berlin: results from the ULTRAFLEB project', conference paper presented at: EAC, Lecce, Italy, 2025.
- Masiol, M., et al., 2017, 'Sources of sub-micrometre particles near a major international airport', *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 17(20), pp. 12379-12403 (DOI: 10.5194/acp-17-12379-2017).
- Nölscher, A., 2025, 'Atmosphärische Chemie: Forschung: UFP-MUC', BAYCEER (https://www.bayceer.uni-bayreuth.de/atmos/de/forschung/proj/detail.php?id_obj=160172) accessed 4 June 2025.
- Ohlwein, S., et al., 2019, 'Health effects of ultrafine particles: a systematic literature review update of epidemiological evidence', *International Journal of Public Health* 64(4), pp. 547-559 (DOI: 10.1007/s00038-019-01202-7).
- OSTLUFT, 2025, 'Ultrafeine Partikel in Kloten - OSTLUFT', Ostluft – Die Luftqualitätsüberwachung der Ostschweizer Kantone und des Fürstentums Liechtenstein (<https://www.ostluft.ch/ultrafeine-partikel-in-kloten-1>) accessed 5 June 2025.
- Pozzoli et al., 2024, 'Air quality around ports', (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2024/12 version 1). European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14710615>) accessed 8 October 2025.
- Pozzoli et al., 2025, 'Air quality around ports', (Eionet Report – ETC HE 2024/12 version 2). European Topic Centre on Human Health and the Environment (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17416089>) accessed 8 October 2025.
- Rivas, I., et al., 2020, 'Source apportionment of particle number size distribution in urban background and traffic stations in four European cities', *Environment International* 135, p. 105345 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2019.105345).
- Seidler, J., et al., 2024, 'Introducing the novel concept of cumulative concentration roses for studying the transport of ultrafine particles from an airport to adjacent residential areas', *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 24(1), pp. 137-153 (DOI: 10.5194/acp-24-137-2024).
- Smith, A., et al., 2011, 'The Integrated Surface Database: Recent Developments and Partnerships', *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, 92, 704–708, (<https://doi.org/10.1175/2011BAMS3015.1>).
- Stacey, B., 2019, 'Measurement of ultrafine particles at airports: A review', *Atmospheric Environment* 198, pp. 463-477 (DOI: 10.1016/j.atmosenv.2018.10.041).
- Sun, J., et al., 2020, 'Decreasing trends of particle number and black carbon mass concentrations at 16 observational sites in Germany from 2009 to 2018', *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 20(11), pp. 7049-7068 (<https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-20-7049-2020>).
- Thoelke, P.H., 2024, 'Systematic Review on Long-term Exposure to UFP and Health Effects', NPC 24 – 13/06/2024 (https://www.nanoparticles.ch/archive/2024_Haddad_Thoelke_PR.pdf) accessed 23 November 2025.
- Trechera, P., et al., 2023, 'Phenomenology of ultrafine particle concentrations and size distribution across urban Europe', *Environment International* 172, p. 107744 (DOI: 10.1016/j.envint.2023.107744).

Tromp, C.D., et al., 2021, 'Verkennd onderzoek ultrafijnstof op het Schiphol terrein met behulp van mobiele metingen', TNO-rapport, TNO 2021 R11745 (<https://publications.tno.nl/publication/34638736/PX7myT/TNO-2021-R11745.pdf>) accessed 23 November 2025.

Ungeheuer, F., et al., 2021, 'Identification and source attribution of organic compounds in ultrafine particles near Frankfurt International Airport', *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 21(5), pp. 3763-3775 (DOI: 10.5194/acp-21-3763-2021).

von Bismarck-Osten, C., et al., 2013, 'Characterization of parameters influencing the spatio-temporal variability of urban particle number size distributions in four European cities', *Atmospheric Environment*, Volume 77, October 2013, Pages 415-429 (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2013.05.029>).

von Schneidemesser, E., et al., 2019, 'Air pollution at human scales in an urban environment: Impact of local environment and vehicles on particle number concentrations', *Science of The Total Environment* 688, pp. 691-700 (DOI: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.06.309).

Voogt, M., et al., 2019, 'Metingen en berekeningen van ultrafijn stof van vliegverkeer rond Schiphol – Voor onderzoek naar gezondheid van omwonenden'. Bilthoven: RIVM rapport 2019-0074. (<https://www.rivm.nl/bibliotheek/rapporten/2019-0074.pdf>) accessed 23 November 2025.

Vörösmarty, M., et al., 2024, 'Attribution of aerosol particle number size distributions to main sources using an 11-year urban dataset', *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 24(9), pp. 5695-5712 (DOI: 10.5194/acp-24-5695-2024).

Wehner, B., et al., 2005, 'The contribution of sulfuric acid and non-volatile compounds on the growth of freshly formed atmospheric aerosols', *Geophysical Research Letters* 32(17) (DOI: 10.1029/2005GL023827).

WHO, 2021, WHO global air quality guidelines: particulate matter (PM2.5 and PM10), ozone, nitrogen dioxide, sulfur dioxide and carbon monoxide, World Health Organization (<https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/345329>) accessed 26 October 20.

Winkler, et al., 2025, 'Einfluss der Großflughäfen auf zeitliche und räumliche Verteilungen von Ultrafeinstaub kleiner als 100 nm im Großraum Berlin (ULTRAFLEB)', Abschlussbericht No REFOPLAN FKZ 3720 52 201 0, Umweltbundesamt, Dessau (<https://www.tropos.de/en/research/projects-infrastructures-technology/joint-research-projects/ultrafleb#c7257>) accessed 23 November 2025.

Yao, L., et al., 2018, 'Atmospheric new particle formation from sulfuric acid and amines in a Chinese megacity', *Science* 361(6399), pp. 278-281 (DOI: 10.1126/science.aao4839).

Zhang, X., et al., 2020, 'Influence of Aviation Emission on the Particle Number Concentration near Zurich Airport', *Environmental Science & Technology* 54(22), pp. 14161-14171 (DOI: 10.1021/acs.est.0c02249).

Annex 1 Maps and tables for each airport

This Annex contains the full analysis with all plots for each airport with the following structure:

- Map of the airport area (CL20218, code 124 polygon) and map with location of identified air quality SPOs within radius of 10 km for NO₂, 20 km for PM_{2.5} and 50 km for O₃ from the airport (the location of the meteorological station is used as centre of the airport). The frequency of wind directions blowing from the airport towards eight different sectors (45 degrees wide sectors centred at directions NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, NW, N) is also displayed.
- Tables with identified air quality SPOs of NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃. The tables include additional information on the annual mean concentrations of each SPO with available data (data coverage larger than 75%), distances of the SPOs from the airport area, location of the SPO in one of the eight wind sectors around the airport (WS: N, NE, E, SE, S, SW, W, NW), wind frequency blowing from the airport in that WS, population living in the WS within 10 km from the airport, and trends of annual mean concentrations (2005-2023) when available.
- Distribution of hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ concentrations for monitoring SPOs located in the eight wind sectors relative to the airport. Three distributions are displayed for each direction if data are available: hourly concentration corresponding to wind from all directions (red); hourly concentration corresponding to wind blowing from the airport (green); hourly concentration corresponding to wind not blowing from the airport (blue). In the centre of the figure the wind frequency in each sector is reported.
- A series of tables summarise median concentrations of NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ under downwind conditions compared to non-downwind conditions, grouped by wind sector and distance range from the airport. Left panels show pollutant concentrations (µg/m³) when wind originates from the airport toward monitoring SPOs, along with wind frequency (%) for each sector. Grey cells indicate missing data. Right panels present relative changes (%) in median concentrations under downwind conditions versus non-downwind conditions, calculated separately for each distance range. Positive values (highlighted in red) indicate increased concentrations when air flows from the airport, while negative values (blue) indicate reductions. This analysis provides preliminary evidence of wind directional influence of airport emissions on local air quality.
- EEA air quality maps of NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak annual mean concentrations at the resolution of 1 km by 1km for 2023. Next to each map the box-plot distribution of NO₂, PM₁₀ and O₃ concentrations over the airport (grey shaded grid cells), compared to the surrounding region, including area-weighted means for different land cover classes (High density residential, Low density residential, Industry, Traffic, Agricultural areas, Natural areas).

Annex 1.1: Airport of Amsterdam (AMS)

Figure A1.1: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.1: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Netherlands	NL00564	Background	52.33	4.71	15.06		0.19	NW	8.60	37,708
Netherlands	NL00565	Background	52.28	4.77	15.24		0.86	S	6.28	30,312
Netherlands	NL00561	Background	52.33	4.77	18.68		1.12	N	16.24	65,541
Netherlands	NL00022	Background	52.37	4.79	14.11	-40.65	4.78	N	16.24	65,541
Netherlands	NL00014	Background	52.36	4.87	14.75	-56.94	6.22	NE	21.27	282,181
Netherlands	NL00020	Traffic	52.37	4.86	25.34	-55.59	7.35	NE	21.27	282,181
Netherlands	NL00007	Traffic	52.38	4.85	30.42	-54.66	7.46	NE	21.27	282,181

Table A1.2: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Netherlands	NL00561	Background	52.33	4.77	8.37		1.12	N	16.24	177,626
Netherlands	NL00703	Background	52.40	4.73	7.96		3.58	N	16.24	177,626
Netherlands	NL00014	Background	52.36	4.87	7.71		6.22	NE	21.27	675,124
Netherlands	NL00007	Traffic	52.38	4.85	8.79		7.46	NE	21.27	675,124
Netherlands	NL00017	Traffic	52.36	4.90	9.25		7.66	NE	21.27	675,124
Netherlands	NL00704	Industrial	52.43	4.77	8.35		7.90	N	16.24	177,626
Netherlands	NL00016	Background	52.39	4.87	6.78		9.51	NE	21.27	675,124
Netherlands	NL00012	Traffic	52.39	4.89	8.71		9.80	NE	21.27	675,124
Netherlands	NL00701	Background	52.45	4.82	8.77		11.42	N	16.24	177,626
Netherlands	NL00444	Background	52.30	4.51	7.92		13.66	W	8.84	151,896
Netherlands	NL00641	Traffic	52.20	4.99	8.78		16.75	SE	9.58	102,013

Table A1.3: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Netherlands	NL00550	Traffic	52.37	4.64	52.63		4.60	NW	8.60	288,854
Netherlands	NL00014	Background	52.36	4.87	54.68		6.22	NE	21.27	914,330
Netherlands	NL00012	Traffic	52.39	4.89	52.48		9.80	NE	21.27	914,330
Netherlands	NL00003	Background	52.39	4.94	55.63		12.21	NE	21.27	914,330
Netherlands	NL00444	Background	52.30	4.51	62.07	23.11	13.66	W	8.84	178,314
Netherlands	NL00641	Traffic	52.20	4.99	47.72	73.97	16.75	SE	9.58	951,431
Netherlands	NL00633	Background	52.14	4.84	52.12	19.96	17.08	S	6.28	827,072
Netherlands	NL00636	Traffic	52.10	5.12	48.53		30.97	SE	9.58	951,431
Netherlands	NL00643	Background	52.10	5.13	54.81		31.44	SE	9.58	951,431
Netherlands	NL00639	Traffic	52.07	5.12	50.82	54.67	33.69	SE	9.58	951,431
Netherlands	NL00644	Background	51.97	4.92	50.79		36.13	S	6.28	827,072
Netherlands	NL00446	Background	52.04	4.36	54.53		37.57	SW	13.47	1,799,079
Netherlands	NL00450	Traffic	52.06	4.32	47.82		37.70	SW	13.47	1,799,079
Netherlands	NL00404	Background	52.08	4.29	57.61	29.99	38.19	SW	13.47	1,799,079
Netherlands	NL00493	Traffic	51.93	4.46	42.73		44.12	SW	13.47	1,799,079
Netherlands	NL00418	Background	51.91	4.48	52.06	48.53	44.91	SW	13.47	1,799,079
Netherlands	NL00494	Background	51.92	4.40	46.80		46.55	SW	13.47	1,799,079

Figure A1.2: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

SPO not available in this wind sector

SPO not available in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW
SPO not available in this wind sector

Wind sector 3: SE
SPO not available in this wind sector

Figure A1.3: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 8: N
Amsterdam-AMS, Wind sector 8 (4 SPOs)

Wind sector 1: NE
Amsterdam-AMS, Wind sector 1 (5 SPOs)

Wind sector 6: W
Amsterdam-AMS, Wind sector 6 (1 SPOs)

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 4: S

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 3: SE
Amsterdam-AMS, Wind sector 3 (1 SPOs)

Figure A1.4: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Table A1.4: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	21.3%		17.0
E	15.6%		
SE	9.6%		
S	6.3%	14.1	
SW	13.5%		
W	8.9%		
NW	8.6%	21.3	
N	16.3%	26.6	18.0

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	21.3%		-13.3%
E	15.6%		
SE	9.6%		
S	6.3%	22.6%	
SW	13.5%		
W	8.9%		
NW	8.6%	97.2%	
N	16.3%	112.8%	95.7%

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	21.3%		6.4	6.2
E	15.6%			
SE	9.6%			6.0
S	6.3%			
SW	13.5%			
W	8.9%			9.7
NW	8.6%			
N	16.3%	7.0		6.7

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	21.3%		-9.9%	-13.9%
E	15.6%			
SE	9.6%			-21.6%
S	6.3%			
SW	13.5%			
W	8.9%			42.4%
NW	8.6%			
N	16.3%	4.5%		3.1%

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	21.3%		54.0	54.4	
E	15.6%				
SE	9.6%			57.2	62.1
S	6.3%			66.0	61.7
SW	13.5%				62.2
W	8.9%			50.6	
NW	8.6%			31.2	
N	16.3%				

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	21.3%		-4.4%	-2.7%	
E	15.6%				
SE	9.6%			20.6%	22.8%
S	6.3%			25.7%	20.9%
SW	13.5%				23.3%
W	8.9%			-23.1%	
NW	8.6%			-44.5%	
N	16.3%				

Figure A1.5: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.2: Airport of Athens (ATH)

Figure A1.6: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.5: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Greece	GR0120A	Background	37.90	23.88	13.21		3.70	SW	20.70	15,400

Table A1.6: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Greece	GR0039A	Background	38.00	23.82	11.43		11.61	NW	2.62	642,098
Greece	GR0003A	Traffic	37.99	23.73	18.91		18.01	W	7.21	891,671
Greece	GR0035A	Background	38.07	23.79	18.72		18.34	NW	2.62	642,098

Table A1.7: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Greece	GR0120A	Background	37.90	23.88	73.94		3.70	SW	20.70	125,305
Greece	GR0039A	Background	38.00	23.82	78.05		11.61	NW	2.62	1,380,732
Greece	GR0022A	Background	38.03	23.79	62.05		16.06	NW	2.62	1,380,732
Greece	GR0031A	Background	37.93	23.71	54.05		17.73	W	7.21	2,059,724
Greece	GR0032A	Traffic	38.00	23.73	13.29		18.15	W	7.21	2,059,724
Greece	GR0035A	Background	38.07	23.79	58.72		18.34	NW	2.62	1,380,732
Greece	GR0029A	Industrial	37.98	23.71	51.27	46.30	19.65	W	7.21	2,059,724
Greece	GR0028A	Background	38.02	23.69	61.28		22.71	NW	2.62	1,380,732
Greece	GR0030A	Traffic	37.94	23.65	37.83		23.78	W	7.21	2,059,724
Greece	GR0027A	Background	38.08	23.70	56.56	13.03	25.40	NW	2.62	1,380,732
Greece	GR0037A	Background	38.14	23.76	84.89		26.31	NW	2.62	1,380,732
Greece	GR0038A	Industrial	38.05	23.54	58.60		36.01	W	7.21	2,059,724

Figure A1.7: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

Figure A1.8: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

Wind sector 8: N

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 4: S

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.9: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 8: N

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 4: S

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Table A1.8: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	12.1%		
E	12.8%		
SE	8.2%		
S	21.8%		
SW	24.4%		5.5
W	8.5%		
NW	3.1%		
N	9.1%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	12.1%		
E	12.8%		
SE	8.2%		
S	21.8%		
SW	24.4%		-50.0%
W	8.5%		
NW	3.1%		
N	9.1%		

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	12.1%			
E	12.8%			
SE	8.2%			
S	21.8%			
SW	24.4%			
W	8.5%			16.0
NW	3.1%			14.0
N	9.1%			

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	12.1%			
E	12.8%			
SE	8.2%			
S	21.8%			
SW	24.4%			
W	8.5%			6.7%
NW	3.1%			16.7%
N	9.1%			

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	12.1%				
E	12.8%				
SE	8.2%				
S	21.8%				
SW	24.4%		89.5		
W	8.5%			4.0	72.0
NW	3.1%			74.0	69.0
N	9.1%				

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	12.1%				
E	12.8%				
SE	8.2%				
S	21.8%				
SW	24.4%		24.3%		
W	8.5%			-20.0%	44.0%
NW	3.1%			5.7%	-4.2%
N	9.1%				

Figure A1.10: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.3: Airport of Barcelona (BCN)

Figure A1.11: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.9: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Spain	ES1929A	Background	41.32	2.10	24.97		0.88	NE	21.09	231,616
Spain	ES1983A	Background	41.32	2.08	24.77		1.33	N	7.36	412,887
Spain	ES1903A	Background	41.31	2.01	18.60		3.74	W	8.27	136,818
Spain	ES1910A	Background	41.30	1.99	9.76		5.16	W	8.27	136,818
Spain	ES0692A	Background	41.37	2.12	22.98	-40.52	6.24	N	7.36	412,887

Table A1.10: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Spain	ES0692A	Background	41.37	2.12	10.29		6.24	N	7.36	623,589
Spain	ES0567A	Background	41.38	2.12	12.94		7.88	N	7.36	623,589
Spain	ES1438A	Traffic	41.39	2.15	14.61		8.84	NE	21.09	1,725,820
Spain	ES0559A	Traffic	41.39	2.16	16.41	-23.76	9.50	NE	21.09	1,725,820
Spain	ES1480A	Traffic	41.40	2.15	11.55	-45.56	10.23	NE	21.09	1,725,820
Spain	ES1663A	Industrial	41.40	2.00	12.35		11.64	NW	7.24	238,576
Spain	ES1856A	Background	41.43	2.15	10.29	-38.63	12.88	N	7.36	623,589
Spain	ES0691A	Background	41.40	2.20	15.24		12.93	NE	21.09	1,725,820
Spain	ES1148A	Traffic	41.43	2.22	12.73		15.74	NE	21.09	1,725,820

Table A1.11: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Spain	ES1983A	Background	41.32	2.08	52.61		1.33	N	7.36	1,568,729
Spain	ES1903A	Background	41.31	2.01	62.48		3.74	W	8.27	469,048
Spain	ES1910A	Background	41.30	1.99	60.94		5.16	W	8.27	469,048
Spain	ES1992A	Background	41.39	2.12	62.15		8.12	N	7.36	1,568,729
Spain	ES1679A	Background	41.39	2.19	49.31	32.91	10.52	NE	21.09	2,593,651
Spain	ES0694A	Background	41.39	2.01	45.04	22.73	10.70	NW	7.24	491,599
Spain	ES2090A	Background	41.42	2.12	81.59		11.67	N	7.36	1,568,729
Spain	ES1856A	Background	41.43	2.15	64.23	20.95	12.88	N	7.36	1,568,729
Spain	ES1231A	Background	41.48	2.09	46.16	26.34	18.05	N	7.36	1,568,729
Spain	ES1892A	Background	41.44	2.24	52.70		18.16	NE	21.09	2,593,651
Spain	ES1684A	Background	41.49	2.04	51.69	16.68	20.35	N	7.36	1,568,729
Spain	ES1815A	Background	41.35	1.69	54.37	-2.76	31.07	W	8.27	469,048
Spain	ES1816A	Background	41.55	2.44	65.81	18.03	38.25	NE	21.09	2,593,651

Figure A1.12: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 8: N

Barcelona-BCN, Wind sector 8 (2 SPOs)

Wind sector 1: NE

Barcelona-BCN, Wind sector 1 (1 SPOs)

Wind sector 6: W

Barcelona-BCN, Wind sector 6 (2 SPOs)

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 4: S

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.13: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Table A1.12: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	21.1%	13.0	
E	8.7%		
SE	23%		
S	18.8%		
SW	5.5%		
W	8.3%		14.0
NW	7.3%		
N	7.4%	14.0	14.0

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	21.1%	-45.8%	
E	8.7%		
SE	23%		
S	18.8%		
SW	5.5%		
W	8.3%		40.0%
NW	7.3%		
N	7.4%	-36.4%	-22.2%

SPOs with hourly concentrations
not available for PM_{2.5}

SPOs with hourly concentrations
not available for PM_{2.5}

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	21.1%			59.0	72.0
E	8.7%				
SE	23%				
S	18.8%				
SW	5.5%				
W	8.3%		73.0		69.0
NW	7.3%			74.0	
N	7.4%	83.0		84.0	79.0

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	21.1%			20.4%	26.3%
E	8.7%				
SE	23%				
S	18.8%				
SW	5.5%				
W	8.3%		17.7%		30.2%
NW	7.3%			85.0%	
N	7.4%	59.6%		21.7%	71.7%

Figure A1.14: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.4: Airport of Berlin (BER)

Figure A1.15: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.13: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Germany	DEBB086	Background	52.35	13.42	8.97		1.96	SW	9.53	13,184
Germany	DEBB112	Background	52.32	13.62	11.27		6.92	SE	7.61	22,519

Table A1.14: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Germany	DEBB086	Background	52.35	13.42	8.78	-61.68	1.96	SW	9.53	34,499
Germany	DEBB112	Background	52.32	13.62	8.30		6.92	SE	7.61	68,344
Germany	DEBE069	Traffic	52.44	13.39	11.81		9.69	NW	9.92	1,192,712
Germany	DEBE063	Traffic	52.47	13.44	12.26		9.86	NW	9.92	1,192,712
Germany	DEBE127	Traffic	52.47	13.44	12.33		9.88	NW	9.92	1,192,712
Germany	DEBE056	Background	52.45	13.65	8.22		10.35	NE	21.58	190,572
Germany	DEBE126	Traffic	52.48	13.43	12.31		11.84	NW	9.92	1,192,712
Germany	DEBE034	Background	52.49	13.43	10.28	-44.41	12.36	NW	9.92	1,192,712
Germany	DEBE034	Background	52.49	13.43	10.92	-44.41	12.36	NW	9.92	1,192,712
Germany	DEBE065	Traffic	52.51	13.47	12.15	-47.54	13.97	N	9.91	846,674
Germany	DEBE065	Traffic	52.51	13.47	11.78	-47.54	13.97	N	9.91	846,674
Germany	DEBE061	Traffic	52.46	13.32	10.87		14.88	NW	9.92	1,192,712
Germany	DEBE068	Background	52.51	13.42	10.41	-54.36	15.12	NW	9.92	1,192,712
Germany	DEBE068	Background	52.51	13.42	10.26	-54.36	15.12	NW	9.92	1,192,712
Germany	DEBE125	Traffic	52.51	13.38	11.40		15.99	NW	9.92	1,192,712

Table A1.15: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Germany	DEBB086	Background	52.35	13.42	53.39		1.96	SW	9.53	90,181
Germany	DEBB112	Background	52.32	13.62	54.43		6.92	SE	7.61	95,317
Germany	DEBE027	Background	52.40	13.37	55.37	11.61	7.74	W	13.06	578,016
Germany	DEBE056	Background	52.45	13.65	56.62	8.71	10.35	NE	21.58	295,170
Germany	DEBE034	Background	52.49	13.43	52.54	21.63	12.36	NW	9.92	2,319,616
Germany	DEBE065	Traffic	52.51	13.47	46.88		13.97	N	9.91	1,282,119
Germany	DEBE010	Background	52.54	13.35	52.03	25.48	20.30	NW	9.92	2,319,616
Germany	DEBE032	Background	52.47	13.23	49.50	17.53	20.38	NW	9.92	2,319,616
Germany	DEBB075	Background	52.48	13.12	52.49	18.78	26.85	NW	9.92	2,319,616
Germany	DEBB021	Background	52.40	13.06	57.22	11.33	27.30	W	13.06	578,016
Germany	DEBE051	Background	52.64	13.48	46.05	-10.78	28.11	N	9.91	1,282,119
Germany	DEBE062	Background	52.65	13.30	50.48	6.81	32.72	NW	9.92	2,319,616
Germany	DEBB109	Background	52.09	13.17	53.54		33.77	SW	9.53	90,181
Germany	DEBB110	Background	52.54	13.05	59.02		34.39	NW	9.92	2,319,616
Germany	DEBB053	Background	52.56	14.02	57.47	-1.23	38.08	NE	21.58	295,170

Figure A1.16: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

Wind sector 8: N

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.17: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 6: W

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.18: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Table A1.16: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	22%		
E	20.6%		
SE	7.8%		7.5
S	6.4%		
SW	9.7%		9.0
W	13.3%		
NW	10.1%		
N	10.1%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	22%		
E	20.6%		
SE	7.8%		-14.6%
S	6.4%		
SW	9.7%		22.6%
W	13.3%		
NW	10.1%		
N	10.1%		

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	22%			5.9
E	20.6%			
SE	7.8%		5.7	
S	6.4%			
SW	9.7%		9.1	
W	13.3%			
NW	10.1%			11.9
N	10.1%			11.8

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	22%			-19.3%
E	20.6%			
SE	7.8%		-18.1%	
S	6.4%			
SW	9.7%		28.5%	
W	13.3%			
NW	10.1%			24.4%
N	10.1%			16.3%

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	22%			52.9	51.6
E	20.6%				
SE	7.8%		62.6		
S	6.4%				
SW	9.7%		52.5		53.5
W	13.3%			57.9	54.9
NW	10.1%			44.8	45.7
N	10.1%			31.8	32.0

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	22%			-8.5%	-10.8%
E	20.6%				
SE	7.8%		18.8%		
S	6.4%				
SW	9.7%		-1.0%		1.3%
W	13.3%			4.8%	-3.9%
NW	10.1%			-15.5%	-14.0%
N	10.1%			-34.8%	-32.3%

Figure A1.19: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.5: Airport of Brussels (BRU)

Figure A1.20: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.17: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Belgium	BELSZ01	Industrial	50.91	4.50	16.23		0.00	NE	31.87	18,846
Belgium	BELSZ05	Background	50.92	4.52	13.03		0.60	NE	31.87	18,846
Belgium	BETMEU1	Background	50.90	4.40	16.95	-45.74	3.17	W	7.41	125,345
Belgium	BETE008	Industrial	50.93	4.40	12.44		4.29	NW	5.08	49,540
Belgium	BETN043	Industrial	50.88	4.38	22.27	-41.82	4.39	W	7.41	125,345
Belgium	BETR020	Background	50.94	4.44	15.94	-54.87	4.48	NW	5.08	49,540
Belgium	BETE009	Industrial	50.95	4.44	11.14		5.91	NW	5.08	49,540

Table A1.18: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Belgium	BELSZ05	Background	50.92	4.52	9.67		0.60	NE	31.87	76,760
Belgium	BETMEU1	Background	50.90	4.40	10.35		3.17	W	7.41	400,820
Belgium	BETN043	Industrial	50.88	4.38	10.61	-57.68	4.39	W	7.41	400,820
Belgium	BETR020	Background	50.94	4.44	9.63		4.48	NW	5.08	115,303
Belgium	BETREG1	Traffic	50.84	4.37	9.77		8.07	SW	11.28	957,679
Belgium	BETR001	Background	50.85	4.33	9.64	-67.70	9.29	SW	11.28	957,679
Belgium	BETR842	Traffic	51.02	4.48	10.19		11.48	N	15.86	147,428
Belgium	BETB011	Background	50.86	4.29	9.49	-49.07	11.61	W	7.41	400,820
Belgium	BETR012	Background	50.80	4.36	8.54	-66.28	12.76	SW	11.28	957,679

Table A1.19: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Belgium	BETMEU1	Background	50.90	4.40	50.66		3.17	W	7.41	874,528
Belgium	BETN043	Industrial	50.88	4.38	48.55	69.00	4.39	W	7.41	874,528
Belgium	BETR001	Background	50.85	4.33	48.70	47.31	9.29	SW	11.28	1,222,691
Belgium	BETR842	Traffic	51.02	4.48	51.04		11.48	N	15.86	1,169,903
Belgium	BETB011	Background	50.86	4.29	54.21	40.68	11.61	W	7.41	874,528
Belgium	BETR012	Background	50.80	4.36	55.06	28.76	12.76	SW	11.28	1,222,691
Belgium	BETN064	Background	50.72	4.49	52.95		18.19	S	6.49	521,099
Belgium	BETN040	Background	50.77	4.23	58.77	29.52	21.02	SW	11.28	1,222,691
Belgium	BETN035	Background	50.98	4.84	58.44	34.87	23.35	E	13.57	417,768
Belgium	BETR801	Background	51.21	4.43	50.31	47.72	32.81	N	15.86	1,169,903
Belgium	BETR811	Background	51.25	4.49	53.45	38.21	37.19	N	15.86	1,169,903
Belgium	BETN051	Background	50.80	3.93	54.73	29.62	37.51	W	7.41	874,528
Belgium	BETN054	Background	50.71	5.10	57.70	37.93	45.42	SE	7.62	221,020

Figure A1.21: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Figure A1.22: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Figure A1.23: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 8: N
Brussels-BRU, Wind sector 8 (3 SPOs)

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W
Brussels-BRU, Wind sector 6 (4 SPOs)

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E
Brussels-BRU, Wind sector 2 (1 SPOs)

Wind sector 5: SW
Brussels-BRU, Wind sector 5 (3 SPOs)

Wind sector 4: S
Brussels-BRU, Wind sector 4 (1 SPOs)

Wind sector 3: SE
Brussels-BRU, Wind sector 3 (1 SPOs)

Table A1.20: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	32.1%	15.0	
E	13.7%		
SE	7.7%		
S	6.5%		
SW	11.4%		
W	7.5%		21.5
NW	5.1%		18.0
N	16%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	32.1%	50.0%	
E	13.7%		
SE	7.7%		
S	6.5%		
SW	11.4%		
W	7.5%		38.7%
NW	5.1%		80.0%
N	16%		

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	32.1%	6.1		
E	13.7%			
SE	7.7%			
S	6.5%			
SW	11.4%			10.5
W	7.5%		12.8	10.8
NW	5.1%		8.9	
N	16%			7.0

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	32.1%	-23.5%		
E	13.7%			
SE	7.7%			
S	6.5%			
SW	11.4%			50.0%
W	7.5%		56.7%	52.8%
NW	5.1%		26.7%	
N	16%			-11.8%

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	32.1%				
E	13.7%				58.5
SE	7.7%				64.0
S	6.5%				61.0
SW	11.4%			59.5	61.5
W	7.5%		51.8	57.5	48.8
NW	5.1%				
N	16%			45.2	41.5

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	32.1%				
E	13.7%				0.9%
SE	7.7%				13.3%
S	6.5%				15.1%
SW	11.4%			15.5%	5.1%
W	7.5%		3.5%	5.5%	-13.7%
NW	5.1%				
N	16%			-13.8%	-23.9%

Figure A1.24: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.6: Airport of Bucharest (OTP)

Figure A1.25: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.21: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Romania	RO0229A	Background	44.49	26.03	25.27		7.93	SW	21.98	35,897

Table A1.22: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Romania	RO0247A	Background	44.50	26.14	16.43		7.24	SE	6.43	272,956
Romania	RO0072A	Background	44.65	26.14	18.62		7.54	NE	16.24	13,388
Romania	RO0229A	Background	44.49	26.03	17.16		7.93	SW	21.98	119,026
Romania	RO0251A	Traffic	44.56	25.95	16.78		9.25	W	18.93	37,525
Romania	RO0248A	Background	44.49	26.18	18.82		9.92	SE	6.43	272,956
Romania	RO0235A	Traffic	44.45	26.07	15.95		12.10	S	9.11	1,384,740
Romania	RO0065A	Background	44.45	26.04	14.26		12.38	S	9.11	1,384,740
Romania	RO0065A	Background	44.45	26.04	13.19		12.38	S	9.11	1,384,740
Romania	RO0230A	Background	44.46	25.99	16.46		12.71	SW	21.98	119,026
Romania	RO0233A	Traffic	44.43	26.09	15.86		14.40	S	9.11	1,384,740
Romania	RO0069A	Industrial	44.42	26.03	12.30		15.44	S	9.11	1,384,740
Romania	RO0245A	Background	44.41	26.11	15.87		16.62	S	9.11	1,384,740

Table A1.23: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Romania	RO0072A	Background	44.65	26.14	54.19		7.54	NE	16.24	73,236
Romania	RO0072A	Background	44.65	26.14	54.19		7.54	NE	16.24	73,236
Romania	RO0229A	Background	44.49	26.03	43.37		7.93	SW	21.98	214,685
Romania	RO0065A	Background	44.45	26.04	49.88		12.38	S	9.11	1,771,539
Romania	RO0071A	Background	44.35	26.03	44.27		23.16	S	9.11	1,771,539

Figure A1.26: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

Wind sector 8: N

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.27: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 8: N

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 1: NE

Wind sector 6: W

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

Figure A1.28: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 8: N

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 1: NE

Wind sector 6: W

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Table A1.24: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	16.4%		
E	18.4%		
SE	6.5%		
S	9.2%		
SW	22.2%		14.7
W	19.1%		
NW	4.8%		
N	3.4%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	16.4%		
E	18.4%		
SE	6.5%		
S	9.2%		
SW	22.2%		-25.9%
W	19.1%		
NW	4.8%		
N	3.4%		

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	16.4%		19.4	
E	18.4%			
SE	6.5%		11.0	11.5
S	9.2%			12.1
SW	22.2%	11.1	10.1	12.5
W	19.1%			10.2
NW	4.8%			
N	3.4%			

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	16.4%		25.1%	
E	18.4%			
SE	6.5%		-5.1%	-4.3%
S	9.2%			1.5%
SW	22.2%	-9.5%	-10.2%	-6.0%
W	19.1%			-14.6%
NW	4.8%			
N	3.4%			

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	16.4%		41.8		
E	18.4%				
SE	6.5%				
S	9.2%			47.6	42.9
SW	22.2%		42.7		
W	19.1%				
NW	4.8%				
N	3.4%				

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	16.4%		-19.2%		
E	18.4%				
SE	6.5%				
S	9.2%			3.2%	5.0%
SW	22.2%		17.4%		
W	19.1%				
NW	4.8%				
N	3.4%				

Figure A1.29: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.7: Airport of Copenhagen (CPH)

Figure A1.30: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.25: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Denmark	DK0034A	Traffic	55.67	12.57	21.64	-60.40	6.02	NW	13.47	243,839

Table A1.26: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Denmark	DK0034A	Traffic	55.67	12.57	8.57	-46.68	6.02	NW	13.47	693,432

Table A1.27: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Denmark	DK0034A	Traffic	55.67	12.57	52.32	62.95	6.02	NW	13.47	1,005,001
Denmark	DK0045A	Background	55.70	12.56	65.11	22.05	8.81	NW	13.47	1,005,001
Sweden	SE0001A	Background	55.61	13.00	49.29	7.08	20.10	E	20.89	519,634
Sweden	SE0058A	Traffic	55.58	13.01	44.95	-0.01	20.61	E	20.89	519,634
Sweden	SE20484	Background	55.87	12.83	52.53		27.91	N	12.90	331,126
Sweden	SE20484	Background	55.87	12.83	52.45		27.91	N	12.90	331,126
Sweden	SE38350	Traffic	55.70	13.18	48.97		32.38	E	20.89	519,634
Sweden	SE0054A	Background	55.70	13.20	52.71	-4.42	33.56	E	20.89	519,634
Denmark	DK0012R	Background	55.69	12.09	64.50		33.84	W	9.51	405,228
Sweden	SE0110A	Background	55.65	13.22	58.73		34.12	E	20.89	519,634
Sweden	SE0053A	Background	56.05	12.69	45.75	-16.30	45.96	N	12.90	331,126

Figure A1.31: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

Wind sector 8: N

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available in this wind sector

SPO not available in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available in this wind sector

SPO not available in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available in this wind sector

SPO not available in this wind sector

SPO not available in this wind sector

Figure A1.32: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 8: N

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 4: S

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.33: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Table A1.28: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	20.8%		
E	20.9%		
SE	6.6%		
S	7%		
SW	8.8%		
W	9.5%		
NW	13.5%		23.4
N	12.9%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	20.8%		
E	20.9%		
SE	6.6%		
S	7%		
SW	8.8%		
W	9.5%		
NW	13.5%		27.1%
N	12.9%		

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	20.8%			
E	20.9%			
SE	6.6%			
S	7%			
SW	8.8%			
W	9.5%			
NW	13.5%		8.0	
N	12.9%			

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	20.8%			
E	20.9%			
SE	6.6%			
S	7%			
SW	8.8%			
W	9.5%			
NW	13.5%		8.1%	
N	12.9%			

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	20.8%				
E	20.9%				52.8
SE	6.6%				
S	7%				
SW	8.8%				
W	9.5%				55.8
NW	13.5%		55.2	68.8	
N	12.9%				48.1

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	20.8%				
E	20.9%				5.7%
SE	6.6%				
S	7%				
SW	8.8%				
W	9.5%				-16.3%
NW	13.5%		3.2%	4.4%	
N	12.9%				-5.0%

Figure A1.34: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.8: Airport of Dublin (DUB)

Figure A1.35: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.29: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Ireland	IE027D	Background	53.43	-6.23	20.50		0.00	NE	24.27	46,981
Ireland	IE0140A	Background	53.46	-6.22	10.33		3.11	NE	24.27	46,981
Ireland	IE0131A	Traffic	53.39	-6.37	25.39	-18.61	5.84	SW	6.00	94,799
Ireland	IE028D	Traffic	53.35	-6.20	23.10		7.44	SE	9.10	122,244
Ireland	IE006AP	Traffic	53.34	-6.25	38.80		8.04	S	4.57	236,487
Ireland	IE005AP	Traffic	53.35	-6.29	32.15		8.14	S	4.57	236,487
Ireland	IE004AP	Traffic	53.34	-6.21	19.23		8.55	SE	9.10	122,244
Ireland	IE001AP	Traffic	53.34	-6.31	17.32		9.41	S	4.57	236,487

Table A1.30: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Ireland	IE027D	Background	53.43	-6.23	6.18		0.00	NE	24.27	82,358
Ireland	IE003AP	Background	53.39	-6.31	6.55		3.45	SW	6.00	291,472
Ireland	IE0106A	Background	53.37	-6.23	7.20	-26.83	5.53	SE	9.10	187,808
Ireland	IE0131A	Traffic	53.39	-6.37	7.12		5.84	SW	6.00	291,472
Ireland	IE002AP	Background	53.37	-6.17	6.52		6.48	SE	9.10	187,808
Ireland	IE0095A	Background	53.36	-6.35	5.56		6.99	SW	6.00	291,472
Ireland	IE028D	Traffic	53.35	-6.20	7.78		7.44	SE	9.10	187,808
Ireland	IE006AP	Traffic	53.34	-6.25	7.39		8.04	S	4.57	578,169
Ireland	IE005AP	Traffic	53.35	-6.29	7.10		8.14	S	4.57	578,169
Ireland	IE004AP	Traffic	53.34	-6.21	6.62		8.55	SE	9.10	187,808
Ireland	IE001AP	Traffic	53.34	-6.31	6.96		9.41	S	4.57	578,169
Ireland	IE0036A	Background	53.34	-6.35	5.90		9.55	SW	6.00	291,472
Ireland	IE0028A	Background	53.32	-6.27	7.16		10.56	S	4.57	578,169
Ireland	IE0127A	Background	53.31	-6.24	6.42		11.75	S	4.57	578,169
Ireland	IE0030D	Traffic	53.35	-6.45	6.95		12.51	SW	6.00	291,472
Ireland	IE007KE	Background	53.37	-6.49	6.45		13.19	W	10.26	94,165
Ireland	IE0132A	Background	53.29	-6.13	7.36		15.97	SE	9.10	187,808
Ireland	IE0136A	Background	53.28	-6.36	5.90		16.10	S	4.57	578,169

Table A1.31: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Ireland	IE027D	Background	53.43	-6.23	40.27		0.00	NE	24.27	86,564
Ireland	IE0140A	Background	53.46	-6.22	54.05		3.11	NE	24.27	86,564
Ireland	IE006AP	Traffic	53.34	-6.25	31.68		8.04	S	4.57	631,067
Ireland	IE0028A	Background	53.32	-6.27	50.38	23.46	10.56	S	4.57	631,067
Ireland	IE0127A	Background	53.31	-6.24	51.98		11.75	S	4.57	631,067
Ireland	IE0141A	Background	53.19	-6.12	58.17		26.60	S	4.57	631,067

Figure A1.36: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 8: N

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 1: NE

Wind sector 6: W

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

Figure A1.37: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 8: N

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 1: NE

Wind sector 6: W

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Table A1.32: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	24.3%	16.8	
E	24%		
SE	9.1%		19.7
S	4.6%		31.2
SW	6%		35.1
W	10.3%		
NW	13.5%		
N	8.2%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	24.3%	-3.3%	
E	24%		
SE	9.1%		16.6%
S	4.6%		52.6%
SW	6%		70.4%
W	10.3%		
NW	13.5%		
N	8.2%		

SPOs with hourly concentrations
not available for PM_{2.5}

SPOs with hourly concentrations
not available for PM_{2.5}

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	24.3%	40.8			
E	24%				
SE	9.1%				
S	4.6%		32.6	47.1	54.0
SW	6%				
W	10.3%				
NW	13.5%				
N	8.2%				

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	24.3%	-5.1%			
E	24%				
SE	9.1%				
S	4.6%		-18.9%	-14.2%	-11.0%
SW	6%				
W	10.3%				
NW	13.5%				
N	8.2%				

Figure A1.38: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.9: Airport of Dusseldorf (DUS)

Figure A1.39: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.33: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Germany	DENW431	Background	51.28	6.74	17.41		0.12	SW	13.11	46,586
Germany	DENW078	Background	51.30	6.82	15.65	-45.30	1.82	NE	24.23	22,879
Germany	DENW071	Background	51.25	6.73	15.90	-42.43	2.96	SW	13.11	46,586
Germany	DENW082	Traffic	51.21	6.78	31.88	-46.04	6.74	S	8.49	235,836
Germany	DENW116	Industrial	51.34	6.67	19.60	-43.01	7.72	NW	12.91	25,824
Germany	DENW430	Traffic	51.20	6.78	31.34		7.83	S	8.49	235,836

Table A1.34: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Germany	DENW431	Background	51.28	6.74	8.11		0.12	SW	13.11	188,836
Germany	DENW078	Background	51.30	6.82	8.37		1.82	NE	24.23	182,943
Germany	DENW071	Background	51.25	6.73	9.24	-61.19	2.96	SW	13.11	188,836
Germany	DENW071	Background	51.25	6.73	8.51	-61.19	2.96	SW	13.11	188,836
Germany	DENW082	Traffic	51.21	6.78	9.81		6.74	S	8.49	395,950
Germany	DENW082	Traffic	51.21	6.78	11.43		6.74	S	8.49	395,950
Germany	DENW116	Industrial	51.34	6.67	11.71		7.72	NW	12.91	192,655
Germany	DENW430	Traffic	51.20	6.78	9.48		7.83	S	8.49	395,950
Germany	DENW247	Background	51.41	6.97	8.80		16.85	NE	24.23	182,943
Germany	DENW038	Background	51.45	6.87	9.04		17.81	N	16.59	353,272

Table A1.35: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Germany	DENW431	Background	51.28	6.74	53.01		0.12	SW	13.11	676,760
Germany	DENW078	Background	51.30	6.82	50.72	40.69	1.82	NE	24.23	2,124,785
Germany	DENW071	Background	51.25	6.73	48.62	41.07	2.96	SW	13.11	676,760
Germany	DENW042	Background	51.34	6.64	56.74	49.65	8.90	NW	12.91	494,108
Germany	DENW247	Background	51.41	6.97	51.16	65.44	16.85	NE	24.23	2,124,785
Germany	DENW038	Background	51.45	6.87	51.09	43.66	17.81	N	16.59	1,046,830
Germany	DENW080	Background	51.18	7.05	58.04	30.61	21.81	SE	6.54	1,397,830
Germany	DENW034	Industrial	51.52	6.75	48.17	34.93	24.82	N	16.59	1,046,830
Germany	DENW096	Background	51.15	6.43	49.50	31.82	26.12	SW	13.11	676,760
Germany	DENW021	Industrial	51.53	6.98	47.14	40.47	28.19	NE	24.23	2,124,785
Germany	DENW053	Background	51.02	6.88	51.92	45.64	29.40	S	8.49	1,502,922
Germany	DENW114	Background	51.28	7.23	50.15	41.40	30.50	E	11.83	1,015,481
Germany	DENW029	Background	51.40	7.21	50.26		30.98	NE	24.23	2,124,785
Germany	DENW079	Background	51.03	7.00	50.80	60.82	31.84	SE	6.54	1,397,830
Germany	DENW066	Background	51.33	6.20	53.75		38.19	W	3.97	635,729
Germany	DENW405	Background	51.67	6.66	53.48		42.25	N	16.59	1,046,830
Germany	DENW058	Industrial	50.88	6.87	55.81	39.66	44.75	S	8.49	1,502,922
Germany	DENW059	Background	50.89	6.99	46.96	50.56	45.27	S	8.49	1,502,922
Germany	DENW074	Industrial	50.88	6.47	56.28	27.92	47.59	SW	13.11	676,760

Figure A1.40: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Figure A1.41: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 6: W

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available in this wind sector

SPO not available in this wind sector

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available in this wind sector

Figure A1.42: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Table A1.36: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	24.8%	17.4	
E	12.1%		
SE	6.7%		
S	8.7%		30.4
SW	13.4%	18.9	20.7
W	4.1%		
NW	13.2%		26.2
N	17%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	24.8%	-2.3%	
E	12.1%		
SE	6.7%		
S	8.7%		-0.8%
SW	13.4%	-6.3%	11.8%
W	4.1%		
NW	13.2%		32.7%
N	17%		

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	24.8%	10.5		9.7
E	12.1%			
SE	6.7%			
S	8.7%		12.1	
SW	13.4%	10.9	12.3	
W	4.1%			
NW	13.2%		13.2	
N	17%			10.6

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	24.8%	-2.4%		-10.2%
E	12.1%			
SE	6.7%			
S	8.7%		8.0%	
SW	13.4%	3.4%	13.6%	
W	4.1%			
NW	13.2%		8.2%	
N	17%			-3.9%

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	24.8%	54.5		44.2	50.7
E	12.1%				56.4
SE	6.7%				64.6
S	8.7%				53.3
SW	13.4%	58.8	53.7		57.6
W	4.1%				50.1
NW	13.2%			38.9	
N	17%			49.4	39.9

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	24.8%	6.4%		-13.2%	0.0%
E	12.1%				9.2%
SE	6.7%				19.8%
S	8.7%				-0.8%
SW	13.4%	7.7%	7.6%		7.3%
W	4.1%				-7.3%
NW	13.2%			-32.3%	
N	17%			-7.4%	-26.3%

Figure A1.43: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.10: Airport of Frankfurt (FRA)

Figure A1.44: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.37: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Germany	DEHE135	Background	50.08	8.58	14.77		2.50	NE	25.10	67,732
Germany	DEHE018	Background	50.01	8.45	16.75	-36.56	3.68	W	6.30	48,112
Germany	DEHE005	Background	50.10	8.54	27.58	-45.62	5.57	N	22.21	85,222

Table A1.38: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Germany	DEHE135	Background	50.08	8.58	7.00		2.50	NE	25.10	652,967
Germany	DEHE018	Background	50.01	8.45	7.95		3.68	W	6.30	191,241
Germany	DEHE005	Background	50.10	8.54	8.34		5.57	N	22.21	290,380
Germany	DEHE041	Traffic	50.12	8.69	8.95	-65.00	10.39	NE	25.10	652,967
Germany	DEHE008	Background	50.13	8.75	7.43	-67.69	13.22	NE	25.10	652,967
Germany	DEHE008	Background	50.13	8.75	8.51	-67.69	13.22	NE	25.10	652,967
Germany	DEHE159	Background	50.17	8.63	7.89		13.65	N	22.21	290,380
Germany	DEHE116	Traffic	50.10	8.78	7.83		14.25	NE	25.10	652,967
Germany	DERP009	Background	49.99	8.27	8.12	-49.92	15.87	W	6.30	191,241
Germany	DERP009	Background	49.99	8.27	8.21	-49.92	15.87	W	6.30	191,241
Germany	DEHE040	Traffic	49.87	8.65	7.88		16.39	SE	4.74	158,386
Germany	DEHE001	Background	49.87	8.66	7.66		16.58	SE	4.74	158,386

Table A1.39: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Germany	DEHE135	Background	50.08	8.58	45.29		2.50	NE	25.10	1,125,800
Germany	DEHE018	Background	50.01	8.45	49.84	23.82	3.68	W	6.30	765,996
Germany	DEHE005	Background	50.10	8.54	43.99	36.87	5.57	N	22.21	548,976
Germany	DEHE008	Background	50.13	8.75	49.52	32.95	13.22	NE	25.10	1,125,800
Germany	DEHE159	Background	50.17	8.63	51.48		13.65	N	22.21	548,976
Germany	DEHE001	Background	49.87	8.66	50.69	26.30	16.58	SE	4.74	410,622
Germany	DEHE022	Background	50.05	8.24	49.04	30.73	17.39	W	6.30	765,996
Germany	DEHE043	Background	49.83	8.52	53.62	19.59	18.64	S	10.67	544,366
Germany	DERP007	Background	50.02	8.22	51.11	25.01	19.43	W	6.30	765,996
Germany	DEHE052	Background	50.22	8.45	74.44	2.75	20.08	N	22.21	548,976
Germany	DEHE011	Background	50.14	8.92	50.33	45.46	24.71	NE	25.10	1,125,800
Germany	DEBY005	Background	49.99	9.12	50.72	41.16	37.46	E	7.56	658,569
Germany	DERP023	Traffic	49.63	8.36	50.27	36.03	42.12	S	10.67	544,366
Germany	DEHE028	Background	49.65	8.82	67.59	5.74	43.05	SE	4.74	410,622
Germany	DEBY004	Background	49.87	9.17	52.17	24.63	44.93	E	7.56	658,569

Figure A1.45: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 8: N
Frankfurt-FRA, Wind sector 8 (1 SPOs)

Wind sector 1: NE
Frankfurt-FRA, Wind sector 1 (1 SPOs)

Wind sector 6: W
Frankfurt-FRA, Wind sector 6 (1 SPOs)

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 4: S

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.46: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 8: N
Frankfurt-FRA, Wind sector 8 (2 SPOs)

Wind sector 1: NE
Frankfurt-FRA, Wind sector 1 (5 SPOs)

Wind sector 6: W
Frankfurt-FRA, Wind sector 6 (3 SPOs)

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 4: S

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 3: SE
Frankfurt-FRA, Wind sector 3 (2 SPOs)

Figure A1.47: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 8: N

Frankfurt-FRA, Wind sector 8 (3 SPOs)

Wind sector 1: NE

Frankfurt-FRA, Wind sector 1 (3 SPOs)

Wind sector 6: W

Frankfurt-FRA, Wind sector 6 (3 SPOs)

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

Frankfurt-FRA, Wind sector 2 (2 SPOs)

Wind sector 5: SW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 4: S

Frankfurt-FRA, Wind sector 4 (2 SPOs)

Wind sector 3: SE

Frankfurt-FRA, Wind sector 3 (2 SPOs)

Table A1.40: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	26.4%		10.6
E	7.9%		
SE	5%		
S	11.2%		
SW	16.6%		
W	6.6%		20.5
NW	2.8%		
N	23.4%		29.4

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	26.4%		-18.7%
E	7.9%		
SE	5%		
S	11.2%		
SW	16.6%		
W	6.6%		62.8%
NW	2.8%		
N	23.4%		21.1%

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	26.4%		4.7	5.4
E	7.9%			
SE	5%			7.6
S	11.2%			
SW	16.6%			
W	6.6%		8.7	9.9
NW	2.8%			
N	23.4%		6.3	5.7

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	26.4%		-27.1%	-27.7%
E	7.9%			
SE	5%			16.1%
S	11.2%			
SW	16.6%			
W	6.6%		36.7%	54.5%
NW	2.8%			
N	23.4%		-12.6%	-16.3%

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	26.4%		53.3	48.7	53.8
E	7.9%				60.2
SE	5%			56.6	68.5
S	11.2%				51.7
SW	16.6%				
W	6.6%		45.3		48.7
NW	2.8%				
N	23.4%		33.5	40.7	61.2

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	26.4%		13.8%	-3.9%	9.0%
E	7.9%				17.2%
SE	5%			13.2%	7.6%
S	11.2%				-0.6%
SW	16.6%				
W	6.6%		-12.9%		-7.6%
NW	2.8%				
N	23.4%		-28.9%	-26.1%	-15.5%

Figure A1.48: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.11: Airport of Hamburg (HAM)

Figure A1.49: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.41: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Germany	DESH030	Traffic	53.68	10.00	25.68		3.00	N	7.73	68,764
Germany	DEHH068	Traffic	53.59	10.05	35.52	-41.67	4.56	SE	13.86	271,610
Germany	DEHH008	Background	53.56	9.97	16.88	-44.96	5.62	S	3.13	301,204
Germany	DEHH064	Traffic	53.56	9.94	31.32	-47.84	5.63	S	3.13	301,204
Germany	DEHH026	Traffic	53.56	9.96	32.65	-58.47	5.98	S	3.13	301,204
Germany	DEHH070	Traffic	53.56	9.94	30.39	-61.26	6.61	S	3.13	301,204
Germany	DEHH047	Background	53.63	10.11	10.30	-38.74	6.66	E	17.09	140,261
Germany	DEHH079	Background	53.55	9.94	21.33		7.74	S	3.13	301,204

Table A1.42: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Germany	DEHH068	Traffic	53.59	10.05	9.82		4.56	SE	13.86	530,138
Germany	DEHH008	Background	53.56	9.97	9.24	-42.09	5.62	S	3.13	442,826
Germany	DEHH064	Traffic	53.56	9.94	9.49	-60.90	5.63	S	3.13	442,826
Germany	DEHH015	Industrial	53.52	10.02	8.49	-41.38	10.65	S	3.13	442,826
Germany	DEHH059	Background	53.51	9.99	8.50	-44.33	12.02	S	3.13	442,826

Table A1.43: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Germany	DEHH008	Background	53.56	9.97	51.72	28.24	5.62	S	3.13	647,028
Germany	DEHH047	Background	53.63	10.11	49.82	13.71	6.66	E	17.09	394,557
Germany	DESH016	Background	53.57	10.21	54.46	23.67	14.77	SE	13.86	828,407
Germany	DEHH050	Background	53.48	9.86	52.32	12.38	16.26	SW	10.52	479,980
Germany	DENI063	Background	53.52	9.69	55.13	14.12	20.58	SW	10.52	479,980
Germany	DESH001	Background	53.67	9.59	53.76	3.00	25.17	W	9.72	381,179
Germany	DESH015	Background	53.92	9.53	56.97	9.39	41.40	NW	11.13	238,948
Germany	DESH058	Background	53.38	10.54	57.26		44.20	SE	13.86	828,407

Figure A1.50: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 8: N
Hamburg-HAM, Wind sector 8 (1 SPOs)

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E
Hamburg-HAM, Wind sector 2 (1 SPOs)

Wind sector 5: SW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 4: S
Hamburg-HAM, Wind sector 4 (5 SPOs)

Wind sector 3: SE
Hamburg-HAM, Wind sector 3 (1 SPOs)

Figure A1.51: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

Wind sector 8: N

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.52: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Table A1.44: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	24.1%		
E	17.7%		7.4
SE	14.4%		30.7
S	3.3%		22.1
SW	10.9%		
W	10.1%		
NW	11.5%		
N	8%		36.9

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	24.1%		
E	17.7%		-27.6%
SE	14.4%		-7.0%
S	3.3%		-8.2%
SW	10.9%		
W	10.1%		
NW	11.5%		
N	8%		70.6%

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	24.1%			
E	17.7%			
SE	14.4%		7.8	
S	3.3%		8.2	7.6
SW	10.9%			
W	10.1%			
NW	11.5%			
N	8%			

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	24.1%			
E	17.7%			
SE	14.4%		-4.7%	
S	3.3%		-1.7%	4.7%
SW	10.9%			
W	10.1%			
NW	11.5%			
N	8%			

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	24.1%				
E	17.7%		60.9		
SE	14.4%			63.2	64.3
S	3.3%		52.9		
SW	10.9%			52.8	62.0
W	10.1%				41.9
NW	11.5%				48.0
N	8%				

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	24.1%				
E	17.7%		26.1%		
SE	14.4%			17.7%	13.4%
S	3.3%		2.3%		
SW	10.9%			-1.9%	10.7%
W	10.1%				-23.9%
NW	11.5%				-18.2%
N	8%				

Figure A1.53: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.12: Airport of Helsinki (HEL)

Figure A1.54: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.45: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Finland	FI00370	Traffic	60.29	25.04	14.36	-56.47	3.01	SE	11.94	87,346

Table A1.46: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Finland	FI00370	Traffic	60.29	25.04	5.51	-40.84	3.01	SE	11.94	219,893
Finland	FI00841	Traffic	60.22	24.81	5.53	-43.30	10.64	SW	13.37	267,077
Finland	FI00781	Background	60.22	25.10	4.80	-42.92	10.77	SE	11.94	219,893
Finland	FI00208	Background	60.31	24.68	3.87		11.32	W	8.75	24,028
Finland	FI00425	Background	60.19	24.95	4.89	-51.90	13.13	S	10.70	418,326
Finland	FI00564	Traffic	60.17	24.94	6.30	-39.73	15.06	S	10.70	418,326

Table A1.47: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Finland	FI00781	Background	60.22	25.10	50.79		10.77	SE	11.94	219,950
Finland	FI00208	Background	60.31	24.68	51.96	-6.23	11.32	W	8.75	77,904
Finland	FI00425	Background	60.19	24.95	54.40	13.15	13.13	S	10.70	418,327
Finland	FI00339	Background	60.36	25.57	51.95		31.86	E	13.49	120,287

Figure A1.55: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

Wind sector 8: N

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.56: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

Wind sector 8: N

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

Helsinki-HEL, Wind sector 6 (1 SPOs)

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Helsinki-HEL, Wind sector 5 (1 SPOs)

Wind sector 4: S

Helsinki-HEL, Wind sector 4 (2 SPOs)

Wind sector 3: SE

Helsinki-HEL, Wind sector 3 (2 SPOs)

Figure A1.57: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

Wind sector 8: N

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S
Helsinki-HEL, Wind sector 4 (1 SPOs)

Wind sector 3: SE
Helsinki-HEL, Wind sector 3 (1 SPOs)

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Table A1.48: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	20.3%		
E	13.5%		
SE	12%		7.8
S	10.7%		
SW	13.4%		
W	8.8%		
NW	9.4%		
N	11.8%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	20.3%		
E	13.5%		
SE	12%		-31.0%
S	10.7%		
SW	13.4%		
W	8.8%		
NW	9.4%		
N	11.8%		

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	20.3%			
E	13.5%			
SE	12%		4.5	3.1
S	10.7%			5.5
SW	13.4%			5.1
W	8.8%			4.4
NW	9.4%			
N	11.8%			

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	20.3%			
E	13.5%			
SE	12%		-7.8%	-17.7%
S	10.7%			21.6%
SW	13.4%			22.5%
W	8.8%			51.4%
NW	9.4%			
N	11.8%			

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	20.3%				
E	13.5%				57.0
SE	12%			50.9	
S	10.7%			46.6	
SW	13.4%				
W	8.8%			44.2	
NW	9.4%				
N	11.8%				

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	20.3%				
E	13.5%				7.8%
SE	12%			-4.5%	
S	10.7%			-18.0%	
SW	13.4%				
W	8.8%			-17.9%	
NW	9.4%				
N	11.8%				

Figure A1.58: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.13: Airport of Lisbon (LIS)

Figure A1.59: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.49: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Portugal	PT03071	Background	38.77	-9.11	22.11	-43.89	1.38	SE	32.95	46,672
Portugal	PT03072	Traffic	38.75	-9.15	30.96	-45.36	1.58	S	15.88	220,445
Portugal	PT03097	Traffic	38.80	-9.18	20.44	-37.61	3.96	NW	1.79	130,516
Portugal	PT03085	Background	38.83	-9.16	14.97	-50.04	4.51	NW	1.79	130,516
Portugal	PT03075	Traffic	38.72	-9.15	46.09	-38.14	4.70	S	15.88	220,445
Portugal	PT03100	Traffic	38.75	-9.20	29.77		5.18	SW	12.60	225,143
Portugal	PT03082	Background	38.74	-9.21	21.82		5.97	SW	12.60	225,143
Portugal	PT03084	Background	38.75	-9.23	17.80		7.43	W	5.79	252,029

Table A1.50: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Portugal	PT03071	Background	38.77	-9.11	7.97	-46.30	1.38	SE	32.95	207,168
Portugal	PT03072	Traffic	38.75	-9.15	7.19	-44.04	1.58	S	15.88	512,596
Portugal	PT03083	Background	38.66	-9.16	4.96	-38.51	11.05	S	15.88	512,596
Portugal	PT03063	Industrial	38.62	-9.08	8.91		16.56	S	15.88	512,596
Portugal	PT03089	Background	38.78	-9.35	8.20	3.10	17.48	W	5.79	604,547

Table A1.51: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Portugal	PT03071	Background	38.77	-9.11	55.48	12.77	1.38	SE	32.95	385,509
Portugal	PT03085	Background	38.83	-9.16	56.37	1.94	4.51	NW	1.79	259,500
Portugal	PT03084	Background	38.75	-9.23	55.82	-1.11	7.43	W	5.79	755,376
Portugal	PT03087	Background	38.70	-9.21	57.14	-6.08	8.51	SW	12.60	504,113
Portugal	PT03070	Background	38.89	-9.12	59.50	10.75	10.61	N	3.10	188,771
Portugal	PT03083	Background	38.66	-9.16	62.55	15.51	11.05	S	15.88	615,047
Portugal	PT03095	Background	38.66	-9.07	62.42	14.10	12.86	SE	32.95	385,509
Portugal	PT03101	Background	38.90	-9.04	56.94	1.43	13.08	NE	13.51	297,239
Portugal	PT03063	Industrial	38.62	-9.08	55.56	8.69	16.56	S	15.88	615,047
Portugal	PT03091	Background	38.70	-9.32	65.40	4.35	17.02	SW	12.60	504,113
Portugal	PT03089	Background	38.78	-9.35	72.09	2.43	17.48	W	5.79	755,376
Portugal	PT03104	Background	38.70	-9.43	68.72		25.53	W	5.79	755,376
Portugal	PT03093	Background	38.53	-8.89	62.96	4.12	33.09	SE	32.95	385,509
Portugal	PT03092	Background	38.53	-8.87	60.79		34.12	SE	32.95	385,509
Portugal	PT03099	Background	38.64	-8.69	59.45	-7.81	40.45	E	9.43	74,722

Figure A1.60: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Figure A1.61: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

Wind sector 8: N

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

Lisbon-LIS, Wind sector 6 (1 SPOs)

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 4: S

Lisbon-LIS, Wind sector 4 (3 SPOs)

Wind sector 3: SE

Lisbon-LIS, Wind sector 3 (1 SPOs)

Figure A1.62: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Table A1.52: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	14.2%		
E	9.9%		
SE	34.7%	12.7	
S	16.7%	16.0	47.9
SW	13.3%		33.7
W	6.1%		24.8
NW	1.9%	20.5	19.8
N	3.3%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	14.2%		
E	9.9%		
SE	34.7%	-20.1%	
S	16.7%	-41.4%	14.9%
SW	13.3%		88.3%
W	6.1%		143.1%
NW	1.9%	39.5%	100.0%
N	3.3%		

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	14.2%			
E	9.9%			
SE	34.7%	6.1		
S	16.7%	4.7		3.4
SW	13.3%			
W	6.1%			8.9
NW	1.9%			
N	3.3%			

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	14.2%			
E	9.9%			
SE	34.7%	-15.3%		
S	16.7%	-21.7%		-24.4%
SW	13.3%			
W	6.1%			29.0%
NW	1.9%			
N	3.3%			

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	14.2%			47.0	
E	9.9%				60.0
SE	34.7%	65.0		71.0	70.0
S	16.7%			64.0	
SW	13.3%			49.0	
W	6.1%		51.0	77.0	67.0
NW	1.9%		46.0		
N	3.3%			65.0	

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	14.2%			-23.0%	
E	9.9%				1.7%
SE	34.7%	18.2%		14.5%	16.7%
S	16.7%			4.9%	
SW	13.3%			-24.6%	
W	6.1%		-12.1%	5.5%	-5.6%
NW	1.9%		-23.3%		
N	3.3%			6.6%	

Figure A1.63: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.14: Airport of Madrid (MAD)

Figure A1.64: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.53: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Spain	ES1942A	Background	40.46	-3.58	28.89		0.00	S	28.25	139,889
Spain	ES1645A	Background	40.47	-3.58	33.52		0.04	S	28.25	139,889
Spain	ES1946A	Background	40.47	-3.61	21.79		1.85	SW	7.48	433,275
Spain	ES1869A	Traffic	40.43	-3.54	28.42	-46.34	2.38	S	28.25	139,889
Spain	ES1752A	Background	40.45	-3.48	20.22	-12.62	4.26	SE	9.04	103,515
Spain	ES1564A	Traffic	40.54	-3.65	21.50	-55.25	4.78	NW	8.87	182,687
Spain	ES0124A	Background	40.44	-3.64	27.26	-48.33	4.99	SW	7.48	433,275
Spain	ES1944A	Background	40.49	-3.66	24.01		5.02	W	4.50	183,758

Table A1.54: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Spain	ES1869A	Traffic	40.43	-3.54	10.75		2.38	S	28.25	357,504
Spain	ES1752A	Background	40.45	-3.48	9.02		4.26	SE	9.04	168,694
Spain	ES1944A	Background	40.49	-3.66	8.47		5.02	W	4.50	604,342
Spain	ES1838A	Background	40.60	-3.50	8.69	-6.22	7.83	NE	16.92	32,065
Spain	ES1940A	Traffic	40.47	-3.69	8.17	-32.50	7.92	W	4.50	604,342
Spain	ES1938A	Traffic	40.44	-3.69	10.18	-6.40	9.09	SW	7.48	2,261,850
Spain	ES0118A	Traffic	40.42	-3.68	9.65	-38.99	9.13	SW	7.48	2,261,850
Spain	ES1525A	Traffic	40.45	-3.71	9.92	-43.00	10.05	SW	7.48	2,261,850
Spain	ES1937A	Background	40.40	-3.69	9.28	-31.69	10.77	SW	7.48	2,261,850
Spain	ES1563A	Traffic	40.48	-3.38	10.84		12.62	E	8.63	267,229
Spain	ES1943A	Traffic	40.38	-3.72	12.36		13.84	SW	7.48	2,261,850
Spain	ES1193A	Background	40.42	-3.75	7.62	-13.57	14.52	SW	7.48	2,261,850

Table A1.55: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Spain	ES1645A	Background	40.47	-3.58	52.37		0.04	S	28.25	579,367
Spain	ES1946A	Background	40.47	-3.61	61.67		1.85	SW	7.48	3,763,188
Spain	ES1869A	Traffic	40.43	-3.54	47.51	44.56	2.38	S	28.25	579,367
Spain	ES1752A	Background	40.45	-3.48	58.29	20.36	4.26	SE	9.04	262,072
Spain	ES1564A	Traffic	40.54	-3.65	61.68	42.34	4.78	NW	8.87	418,215
Spain	ES0124A	Background	40.44	-3.64	56.63	27.13	4.99	SW	7.48	3,763,188
Spain	ES1947A	Background	40.50	-3.69	58.31		7.49	W	4.50	1,088,267
Spain	ES1838A	Background	40.60	-3.50	74.43	7.04	7.83	NE	16.92	179,935
Spain	ES0118A	Traffic	40.42	-3.68	53.28	79.62	9.13	SW	7.48	3,763,188
Spain	ES1941A	Background	40.37	-3.61	53.37		9.15	S	28.25	579,367
Spain	ES1521A	Traffic	40.48	-3.71	57.43	38.02	9.57	W	4.50	1,088,267
Spain	ES1939A	Background	40.41	-3.69	56.22		9.99	SW	7.48	3,763,188
Spain	ES1807A	Background	40.36	-3.54	61.33	31.56	10.24	S	28.25	579,367
Spain	ES1422A	Background	40.42	-3.70	57.15	56.50	10.88	SW	7.48	3,763,188
Spain	ES1563A	Traffic	40.48	-3.38	57.24	30.33	12.62	E	8.63	352,115
Spain	ES0126A	Background	40.39	-3.73	54.64	37.30	14.23	SW	7.48	3,763,188
Spain	ES1193A	Background	40.42	-3.75	57.90	10.88	14.52	SW	7.48	3,763,188
Spain	ES1945A	Background	40.52	-3.77	59.75		14.71	W	4.50	1,088,267
Spain	ES0125A	Background	40.35	-3.71	51.88		15.79	SW	7.48	3,763,188
Spain	ES1801A	Industrial	40.30	-3.46	60.77	33.90	18.10	SE	9.04	262,072
Spain	ES2028A	Traffic	40.31	-3.72	54.55		19.22	SW	7.48	3,763,188
Spain	ES1567A	Traffic	40.34	-3.75	53.77	28.24	19.32	SW	7.48	3,763,188
Spain	ES1613A	Traffic	40.66	-3.77	76.05	2.60	21.63	NW	8.87	418,215
Spain	ES1612A	Background	40.45	-3.87	65.04	0.72	23.35	W	4.50	1,088,267
Spain	ES2133A	Background	40.57	-3.27	53.24		24.30	E	8.63	352,115
Spain	ES1890A	Background	40.34	-3.83	58.85	13.32	24.62	SW	7.48	3,763,188
Spain	ES1565A	Industrial	40.28	-3.80	59.92	32.11	26.65	SW	7.48	3,763,188
Spain	ES1568A	Background	40.32	-3.88	55.26	20.57	28.77	SW	7.48	3,763,188
Spain	ES1805A	Background	40.78	-3.70	62.60	20.13	28.93	N	12.27	104,711
Spain	ES1809A	Background	40.19	-3.68	55.58	37.67	30.79	S	28.25	579,367
Spain	ES1806A	Background	40.29	-3.22	80.88	3.13	31.99	SE	9.04	262,072
Spain	ES1537A	Background	40.63	-3.17	62.40	-8.38	33.94	NE	16.92	179,935
Spain	ES1803A	Traffic	40.63	-4.01	57.11	26.95	37.62	W	4.50	1,088,267
Spain	ES1811A	Traffic	40.17	-3.28	70.02	16.77	38.49	SE	9.04	262,072
Spain	ES1802A	Background	40.91	-3.47	81.82	-2.27	41.39	N	12.27	104,711
Spain	ES1963A	Background	40.12	-3.83	55.70		42.78	SW	7.48	3,763,188
Spain	ES2093A	Background	40.83	-3.96	89.00		45.42	NW	8.87	418,215

Figure A1.65: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Figure A1.66: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 8: N

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 1: NE

Wind sector 6: W

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

Figure A1.67: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Table A1.56: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	17.6%		
E	9%		
SE	9.4%		19.0
S	29.4%	37.0	33.0
SW	7.8%	12.0	15.0
W	4.7%		20.0
NW	9.2%		20.0
N	12.8%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	17.6%		
E	9%		
SE	9.4%		26.7%
S	29.4%	85.0%	83.3%
SW	7.8%	-14.3%	-21.1%
W	4.7%		33.3%
NW	9.2%		42.9%
N	12.8%		

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	17.6%			7.0
E	9%			8.0
SE	9.4%		9.0	
S	29.4%		11.0	
SW	7.8%			7.0
W	4.7%		8.0	6.0
NW	9.2%			
N	12.8%			

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	17.6%			0.0%
E	9%			-20.0%
SE	9.4%		12.5%	
S	29.4%		37.5%	
SW	7.8%			-12.5%
W	4.7%		14.3%	0.0%
NW	9.2%			
N	12.8%			

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	17.6%			79.0	69.0
E	9%			71.0	67.5
SE	9.4%		43.5		68.0
S	29.4%	29.0	23.0	41.0	39.0
SW	7.8%	70.0	65.0	63.0	63.0
W	4.7%			55.0	59.0
NW	9.2%		55.0		82.0
N	12.8%				76.0

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	17.6%			8.2%	16.9%
E	9%			29.1%	35.0%
SE	9.4%		-26.3%		-5.6%
S	29.4%	-51.7%	-56.6%	-33.9%	-36.1%
SW	7.8%	14.8%	16.1%	12.5%	10.5%
W	4.7%			-8.3%	-7.8%
NW	9.2%		-14.1%		-3.5%
N	12.8%				0.0%

Figure A1.68: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.15: Airport of Milan (LIN)

Figure A1.69: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.57: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Italy	IT1692A	Background	45.48	9.24	28.01	-55.09	2.67	NW	10.41	451,247
Italy	IT1290A	Traffic	45.40	9.28	31.11		4.12	S	10.80	70,253
Italy	IT0706A	Background	45.48	9.33	27.96	-36.21	4.15	NE	11.47	74,882
Italy	IT1016A	Traffic	45.47	9.20	34.81	-49.11	4.89	NW	10.41	451,247
Italy	IT0705A	Traffic	45.46	9.20	31.86	-45.97	4.97	W	13.84	389,837
Italy	IT0761A	Traffic	45.45	9.18	37.64		6.07	W	13.84	389,837
Italy	IT0477A	Traffic	45.50	9.19	43.79	-47.13	6.57	NW	10.41	451,247

Table A1.58: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Italy	IT1692A	Background	45.48	9.24	15.97	-44.52	2.67	NW	10.41	985,571
Italy	IT1016A	Traffic	45.47	9.20	21.17		4.89	NW	10.41	985,571
Italy	IT0477A	Traffic	45.50	9.19	18.25		6.57	NW	10.41	985,571
Italy	IT0480A	Traffic	45.53	9.24	16.29		8.05	N	9.79	562,337
Italy	IT1743A	Background	45.58	9.27	17.99	-57.65	12.69	N	9.79	562,337

Table A1.59: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Italy	IT1692A	Background	45.48	9.24	48.12	13.58	2.67	NW	10.41	2,201,750
Italy	IT0706A	Background	45.48	9.33	52.59	32.95	4.15	NE	11.47	1,074,256
Italy	IT0705A	Traffic	45.46	9.20	54.53		4.97	W	13.84	1,215,909
Italy	IT2232A	Background	45.55	9.17	48.08		12.01	NW	10.41	2,201,750
Italy	IT1743A	Background	45.58	9.27	46.20	47.76	12.69	N	9.79	1,417,145
Italy	IT2098A	Background	45.60	9.28	51.70		15.04	N	9.79	1,417,145
Italy	IT1464A	Background	45.50	9.56	52.56	34.19	21.53	E	15.80	386,547
Italy	IT1965A	Background	45.30	9.50	52.13	34.73	22.15	SE	4.70	297,599
Italy	IT1650A	Background	45.63	9.02	52.24	25.94	26.00	NW	10.41	2,201,750
Italy	IT1288A	Background	45.31	9.59	43.16	-2.89	27.54	SE	4.70	297,599
Italy	IT0912A	Background	45.19	9.16	52.57	9.56	27.91	S	10.80	344,663
Italy	IT1174A	Background	45.28	8.99	52.15		27.91	SW	9.28	338,569
Italy	IT1876A	Background	45.68	9.47	57.98	15.49	28.22	NE	11.47	1,074,256
Italy	IT1463A	Background	45.62	9.61	57.65	32.99	31.05	NE	11.47	1,074,256
Italy	IT1648A	Background	45.73	9.13	56.52	82.60	31.20	N	9.79	1,417,145
Italy	IT1203A	Background	45.55	8.85	54.34	-2.52	33.42	W	13.84	1,215,909
Italy	IT0839A	Background	45.37	9.71	47.27	2.31	33.82	E	15.80	386,547
Italy	IT1459A	Background	45.58	8.83	43.83		35.79	NW	10.41	2,201,750
Italy	IT1964A	Background	45.23	9.67	51.00	11.27	37.35	SE	4.70	297,599
Italy	IT0707A	Background	45.69	9.64	55.52		37.83	NE	11.47	1,074,256
Italy	IT2007A	Background	45.81	9.22	64.51		38.30	N	9.79	1,417,145
Italy	IT0771A	Traffic	45.80	9.08	55.24		40.39	N	9.79	1,417,145
Italy	IT1734A	Background	45.84	9.35	63.43	14.94	41.94	N	9.79	1,417,145
Italy	IT1873A	Background	45.62	8.75	47.01	10.51	43.31	NW	10.41	2,201,750
Italy	IT1826A	Background	45.85	9.40	59.06	-1.28	43.51	N	9.79	1,417,145
Italy	IT1746A	Industrial	45.11	8.88	55.50		47.29	SW	9.28	338,569

Figure A1.70: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Figure A1.71: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Table A1.60: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ³) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	13.3%		28.3
E	18.3%		
SE	5.5%		
S	12.5%		33.2
SW	10.8%		
W	16.1%		27.3
NW	12.1%	17.6	30.2
N	11.4%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	13.3%		24.5%
E	18.3%		
SE	5.5%		
S	12.5%		25.7%
SW	10.8%		
W	16.1%		-11.0%
NW	12.1%	-29.0%	-14.4%
N	11.4%		

SPOs with hourly concentrations
not available for PM_{2.5}

SPOs with hourly concentrations
not available for PM_{2.5}

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ³) wind from airport					Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport						
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km	WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	13.3%		46.1		52.5	NE	13.3%		-8.5%		-2.8%
E	18.3%				42.1	E	18.3%				-11.5%
SE	5.5%				45.3	SE	5.5%				-0.5%
S	12.5%				40.8	S	12.5%				-16.8%
SW	10.8%				47.1	SW	10.8%				-8.3%
W	16.1%		60.7		57.1	W	16.1%		10.6%		5.2%
NW	12.1%	62.4		65.7	66.1	NW	12.1%	29.1%		46.7%	51.2%
N	11.4%			53.9	67.3	N	11.4%			29.3%	20.5%

Figure A1.72: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.16: Airport of Paris (CDG)

Figure A1.73: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.61: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
France	FR04319	Background	48.96	2.58	19.50	-31.33	3.85	S	14.28	163,367
France	FR04024	Background	48.99	2.44	18.16	-37.05	4.02	W	4.70	61,853

Table A1.62: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
France	FR04024	Background	48.99	2.44	9.82		4.02	W	4.70	446,446
France	FR04156	Background	48.90	2.45	9.00	-62.82	10.54	SW	12.97	1,354,664
France	FR04058	Traffic	48.93	2.36	12.71	-73.79	13.62	SW	12.97	1,354,664
France	FR04048	Background	49.10	2.34	7.43		14.09	NW	7.32	60,848

Table A1.63: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
France	FR04319	Background	48.96	2.58	49.74	34.29	3.85	S	14.28	2,472,701
France	FR04142	Background	49.03	2.75	57.97	14.22	9.23	E	13.93	174,767
France	FR04100	Background	48.88	2.51	51.51	28.97	11.50	S	14.28	2,472,701
France	FR04048	Background	49.10	2.34	61.49	21.27	14.09	NW	7.32	256,826
France	FR04004	Background	48.89	2.35	52.19	56.38	16.52	SW	12.97	6,224,079
France	FR04098	Background	48.84	2.64	53.55	40.39	16.94	S	14.28	2,472,701
France	FR04101	Background	48.82	2.52	52.81	29.12	18.67	S	14.28	2,472,701
France	FR04055	Background	48.86	2.34	51.32		18.88	SW	12.97	6,224,079
France	FR04037	Background	48.83	2.36	52.80	36.91	21.08	SW	12.97	6,224,079
France	FR04017	Background	48.88	2.28	50.34	62.51	21.15	SW	12.97	6,224,079
France	FR04034	Background	48.78	2.38	54.40		25.64	SW	12.97	6,224,079
France	FR04149	Background	48.71	2.46	52.77	35.07	31.31	S	14.28	2,472,701
France	FR04023	Background	49.05	2.04	57.84	22.85	32.93	W	4.70	1,582,892
France	FR04029	Background	48.80	2.13	53.68		35.29	SW	12.97	6,224,079
France	FR04324	Background	48.76	3.06	53.66	15.50	40.92	SE	8.19	353,799
France	FR04049	Background	48.68	2.17	60.87	28.96	42.89	SW	12.97	6,224,079

Figure A1.74: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

Wind sector 8: N

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.75: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 4: S

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.76: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Table A1.64: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	25.2%		
E	13.9%		
SE	8.2%		
S	14.3%		16.7
SW	13%		
W	4.7%		24.2
NW	7.3%		
N	13.4%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	25.2%		
E	13.9%		
SE	8.2%		
S	14.3%		12.8%
SW	13%		
W	4.7%		91.7%
NW	7.3%		
N	13.4%		

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	25.2%			
E	13.9%			
SE	8.2%			
S	14.3%			
SW	13%			11.7
W	4.7%		9.6	
NW	7.3%			7.8
N	13.4%			

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	25.2%			
E	13.9%			
SE	8.2%			
S	14.3%			
SW	13%			41.0%
W	4.7%		23.7%	
NW	7.3%			41.8%
N	13.4%			

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	25.2%				
E	13.9%			58.7	
SE	8.2%				53.7
S	14.3%		49.3	54.5	53.7
SW	13%				57.8
W	4.7%				44.9
NW	7.3%			46.6	
N	13.4%				44.4

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	25.2%				
E	13.9%			3.3%	
SE	8.2%				-0.8%
S	14.3%		-1.8%	7.1%	0.4%
SW	13%				7.2%
W	4.7%				-23.8%
NW	7.3%			-24.9%	
N	13.4%				-19.7%

Figure A1.77: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.17: Airport of Paris (ORY)

Figure A1.78: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.65: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
France	FR04034	Background	48.78	2.38	20.08	-43.15	3.27	N	13.84	319,680
France	FR04149	Background	48.71	2.46	14.39	-45.74	4.20	E	14.54	140,336

Table A1.66: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
France	FR04034	Background	48.78	2.38	9.28	-50.60	3.27	N	13.84	2,946,715
France	FR04180	Traffic	48.64	2.27	12.91		8.89	SW	14.53	177,710
France	FR04329	Traffic	48.84	2.41	13.25		10.48	N	13.84	2,946,715
France	FR04055	Background	48.86	2.34	10.38		13.00	N	13.84	2,946,715
France	FR04031	Traffic	48.87	2.31	10.35		14.25	N	13.84	2,946,715
France	FR04131	Traffic	48.87	2.33	9.49		14.40	N	13.84	2,946,715
France	FR04004	Background	48.89	2.35	10.46		16.25	N	13.84	2,946,715

Table A1.67: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
France	FR04034	Background	48.78	2.38	54.40		3.27	N	13.84	4,870,530
France	FR04149	Background	48.71	2.46	52.77	35.07	4.20	E	14.54	465,865
France	FR04037	Background	48.83	2.36	52.80	36.91	9.17	N	13.84	4,870,530
France	FR04049	Background	48.68	2.17	60.87	28.96	11.33	W	5.52	621,814
France	FR04101	Background	48.82	2.52	52.81	29.12	12.41	NE	27.92	2,004,925
France	FR04055	Background	48.86	2.34	51.32		13.00	N	13.84	4,870,530
France	FR04029	Background	48.80	2.13	53.68		15.87	NW	4.52	2,354,860
France	FR04004	Background	48.89	2.35	52.19	56.38	16.25	N	13.84	4,870,530
France	FR04017	Background	48.88	2.28	50.34	62.51	16.41	N	13.84	4,870,530
France	FR04100	Background	48.88	2.51	51.51	28.97	17.54	NE	27.92	2,004,925
France	FR04098	Background	48.84	2.64	53.55	40.39	20.70	NE	27.92	2,004,925
France	FR04319	Background	48.96	2.58	49.74	34.29	27.13	NE	27.92	2,004,925
France	FR04069	Background	48.54	2.66	48.99	20.42	27.66	SE	8.49	609,499
France	FR04038	Background	48.58	1.88	61.45	24.75	34.69	SW	14.53	308,582
France	FR04181	Background	48.63	1.83	58.46		36.35	W	5.52	621,814
France	FR04048	Background	49.10	2.34	61.49	21.27	39.40	N	13.84	4,870,530
France	FR04066	Background	48.36	2.24	59.30	19.09	39.49	S	9.90	402,746
France	FR04023	Background	49.05	2.04	57.84	22.85	40.77	NW	4.52	2,354,860
France	FR04142	Background	49.03	2.75	57.97	14.22	41.16	NE	27.92	2,004,925
France	FR04328	Background	48.35	2.65	56.21	17.06	44.39	SE	8.49	609,499

Figure A1.79: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 8: N

Paris-ORY, Wind sector 8 (1 SPOs)

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

Paris-ORY, Wind sector 2 (1 SPOs)

Wind sector 5: SW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 4: S

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.80: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 8: N
Paris-ORY, Wind sector 8 (6 SPOs)

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW
Paris-ORY, Wind sector 5 (1 SPOs)

Wind sector 4: S

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.81: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Table A1.68: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	28.1%		
E	14.6%		11.1
SE	8.6%		
S	10%		
SW	14.6%		
W	5.6%		
NW	4.6%		
N	13.9%		19.8

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	28.1%		
E	14.6%		4.2%
SE	8.6%		
S	10%		
SW	14.6%		
W	5.6%		
NW	4.6%		
N	13.9%		32.0%

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	28.1%			
E	14.6%			
SE	8.6%			
S	10%			
SW	14.6%			12.4
W	5.6%			
NW	4.6%			
N	13.9%		7.1	9.7

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	28.1%			
E	14.6%			
SE	8.6%			
S	10%			
SW	14.6%			19.2%
W	5.6%			
NW	4.6%			
N	13.9%		6.0%	11.5%

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	28.1%			52.7	53.4
E	14.6%		54.2		
SE	8.6%				50.3
S	10%				58.6
SW	14.6%				63.5
W	5.6%			64.8	68.8
NW	4.6%			52.0	50.3
N	13.9%		41.3	39.6	50.2

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	28.1%			-0.6%	-0.2%
E	14.6%		1.8%		
SE	8.6%				-5.3%
S	10%				-0.2%
SW	14.6%				6.7%
W	5.6%			8.0%	17.3%
NW	4.6%			-6.2%	-14.5%
N	13.9%		-27.4%	-26.5%	-20.3%

Figure A1.82: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.18: Airport of Prague (PRG)

Figure A1.83: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.69: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Czechia	CZ0ABRE	Background	50.08	14.38	17.54		6.15	E	12.82	103,136

Table A1.70: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Czechia	CZ0ASTO	Background	50.05	14.33	10.40	-46.12	5.07	SE	10.04	356,979
Czechia	CZ0SKLM	Background	50.14	14.10	10.13	-20.90	9.62	NW	8.79	59,488
Czechia	CZ0ALEG	Traffic	50.07	14.43	12.10		9.86	E	12.82	734,904
Czechia	CZ0ARIE	Background	50.08	14.44	10.20	-44.51	10.62	E	12.82	734,904
Czechia	CZ0AHOL	Traffic	50.11	14.44	13.68		10.66	E	12.82	734,904
Czechia	CZ0ALIB	Background	50.01	14.45	9.58	-43.68	13.88	SE	10.04	356,979

Table A1.71: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Czechia	CZ0ASTO	Background	50.05	14.33	56.03	15.14	5.07	SE	10.04	517,341
Czechia	CZ0ASUC	Background	50.13	14.38	57.32	12.58	7.08	E	12.82	1,037,634
Czechia	CZ0SKLM	Background	50.14	14.10	61.80	22.11	9.62	NW	8.79	127,587
Czechia	CZ0ARIE	Background	50.08	14.44	52.71		10.62	E	12.82	1,037,634
Czechia	CZ0AKOB	Background	50.12	14.47	57.11	17.42	12.58	E	12.82	1,037,634
Czechia	CZ0ALIB	Background	50.01	14.45	59.98	9.86	13.88	SE	10.04	517,341
Czechia	CZ0AVYN	Traffic	50.11	14.50	44.47	38.02	14.90	E	12.82	1,037,634
Czechia	CZ0STCS	Background	49.92	14.09	66.33		21.98	SW	5.87	110,557
Czechia	CZ0UDOK	Background	50.46	14.17	49.97		38.26	N	9.28	135,639
Czechia	CZ0SONR	Background	49.91	14.78	67.86	2.74	39.80	SE	10.04	517,341
Czechia	CZ0ULTT	Background	50.54	14.12	51.84	3.70	47.92	N	9.28	135,639

Figure A1.84: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

Wind sector 8: N

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.85: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 8: N

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 4: S

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.86: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Table A1.72: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	33.4%		
E	12.9%		11.5
SE	10.1%		
S	11.5%		
SW	5.9%		
W	8%		
NW	8.8%		
N	9.3%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	33.4%		
E	12.9%		-21.8%
SE	10.1%		
S	11.5%		
SW	5.9%		
W	8%		
NW	8.8%		
N	9.3%		

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	33.4%			
E	12.9%			7.0
SE	10.1%		9.0	9.0
S	11.5%			
SW	5.9%			
W	8%			
NW	8.8%			12.0
N	9.3%			

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	33.4%			
E	12.9%			-30.0%
SE	10.1%		0.0%	12.5%
S	11.5%			
SW	5.9%			
W	8%			
NW	8.8%			50.0%
N	9.3%			

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	33.4%				
E	12.9%		62.8	57.7	
SE	10.1%		60.0	60.4	65.0
S	11.5%				
SW	5.9%				79.0
W	8%				
NW	8.8%			59.1	
N	9.3%				32.0

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	33.4%				
E	12.9%		11.5%	14.3%	
SE	10.1%		7.7%	2.2%	-0.6%
S	11.5%				
SW	5.9%				24.6%
W	8%				
NW	8.8%			-2.8%	
N	9.3%				-39.0%

Figure A1.87: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.19: Airport of Rome (FCO)

Figure A1.88: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.73: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Italy	IT2247A	Background	41.77	12.24	23.52		0.87	S	11.94	91,813
Italy	IT2246A	Industrial	41.77	12.22	13.29		1.40	SW	18.41	10,443
Italy	IT0952A	Background	41.89	12.27	8.09	-65.35	4.23	N	8.80	3,071

Table A1.74: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Italy	IT2247A	Background	41.77	12.24	10.71		0.87	S	11.94	91,813
Italy	IT0952A	Background	41.89	12.27	10.42	-41.47	4.23	N	8.80	17,685
Italy	IT2012A	Background	41.87	12.35	12.43		7.28	NE	11.28	378,023
Italy	IT1836A	Background	41.91	12.45	12.37	-44.73	16.13	NE	11.28	378,023

Table A1.75: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Italy	IT2247A	Background	41.77	12.24	51.60		0.87	S	11.94	91,813
Italy	IT0952A	Background	41.89	12.27	67.13	32.31	4.23	N	8.80	156,353
Italy	IT2012A	Background	41.87	12.35	53.96		7.28	NE	11.28	1,650,270
Italy	IT1836A	Background	41.91	12.45	44.30	35.58	16.13	NE	11.28	1,650,270
Italy	IT1906A	Background	41.89	12.48	34.55		17.49	NE	11.28	1,650,270
Italy	IT0953A	Background	41.93	12.51	40.88	5.32	21.85	NE	11.28	1,650,270
Italy	IT1176A	Background	41.89	12.54	45.01	18.60	22.31	E	15.26	1,756,495
Italy	IT0956A	Background	41.86	12.57	46.99	17.07	23.83	E	15.26	1,756,495
Italy	IT1835A	Background	41.95	12.53	43.39	37.08	24.61	NE	11.28	1,650,270
Italy	IT0957A	Background	41.93	12.66	53.73	43.51	33.02	NE	11.28	1,650,270
Italy	IT2258A	Background	42.04	11.83	66.76		40.46	NW	10.71	168,175
Italy	IT0884A	Background	42.16	11.91	83.27		44.69	NW	10.71	168,175
Italy	IT2265A	Traffic	42.09	11.81	57.65		45.33	NW	10.71	168,175
Italy	IT2254A	Background	42.16	11.90	80.52		45.43	NW	10.71	168,175
Italy	IT0885A	Background	42.09	11.80	53.53		45.93	NW	10.71	168,175

Figure A1.89: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 8: N

Rome-FCO, Wind sector 8 (1 SPOs)

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Rome-FCO, Wind sector 5 (1 SPOs)

Wind sector 4: S

Rome-FCO, Wind sector 4 (1 SPOs)

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.90: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Table A1.76: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	11.5%		
E	15.5%		
SE	4.6%		
S	12.2%	23.7	
SW	18.7%	17.8	
W	17.5%		
NW	10.9%		
N	9%		4.5

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	11.5%		
E	15.5%		
SE	4.6%		
S	12.2%	23.3%	
SW	18.7%	90.3%	
W	17.5%		
NW	10.9%		
N	9%		-30.1%

SPOs with hourly concentrations
not available for PM_{2.5}

SPOs with hourly concentrations
not available for PM_{2.5}

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport						
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km	WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	11.5%			67.0	64.1	NE	11.5%			41.9%	63.9%
E	15.5%				80.0	E	15.5%				95.4%
SE	4.6%					SE	4.6%				
S	12.2%	45.2				S	12.2%	-22.4%			
SW	18.7%					SW	18.7%				
W	17.5%					W	17.5%				
NW	10.9%				69.4	NW	10.9%				2.0%
N	9%		79.6			N	9%		18.1%		

Figure A1.91: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.20: Airport of Vienna (VIE)

Figure A1.92: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.77: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Austria	AT90LOB	Background	48.16	16.53	10.31	-37.95	3.42	NW	16.91	31,636
Austria	AT32701	Background	48.15	16.48	14.27	-51.17	3.98	NW	16.91	31,636
Austria	AT900KE	Background	48.16	16.48	17.45	-44.73	4.73	NW	16.91	31,636

Table A1.78: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Austria	AT90LOB	Background	48.16	16.53	8.99		3.42	NW	16.91	909,349
Austria	AT90LOB	Background	48.16	16.53	7.94		3.42	NW	16.91	909,349
Austria	AT32701	Background	48.15	16.48	9.11	-47.72	3.98	NW	16.91	909,349
Austria	AT900KE	Background	48.16	16.48	9.61		4.73	NW	16.91	909,349
Austria	AT90LAA	Background	48.16	16.39	8.49		10.28	NW	16.91	909,349
Austria	AT90A23	Traffic	48.20	16.43	10.28		10.64	NW	16.91	909,349
Austria	AT9STAD	Background	48.23	16.46	10.80		11.94	NW	16.91	909,349
Austria	AT30407	Background	48.23	16.64	8.65		12.16	N	10.96	47,799
Austria	AT9BELG	Background	48.17	16.36	10.20		13.01	NW	16.91	909,349
Austria	AT90TAB	Traffic	48.22	16.38	10.61	-60.51	14.44	NW	16.91	909,349
Austria	AT31413	Background	48.08	16.33	9.10	-55.15	15.04	W	4.88	210,367
Austria	AT9GAUD	Background	48.19	16.34	9.40		15.10	NW	16.91	909,349

Table A1.79: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Austria	AT90LOB	Background	48.16	16.53	54.63	9.55	3.42	NW	16.91	1,752,505
Austria	AT32701	Background	48.15	16.48	57.84	12.55	3.98	NW	16.91	1,752,505
Austria	AT30302	Background	48.05	16.68	62.52	-1.14	6.78	SE	25.93	70,651
Austria	AT30603	Background	48.09	16.43	57.91	4.56	8.08	W	4.88	458,406
Austria	AT9STEF	Background	48.21	16.37	59.20	29.85	14.24	NW	16.91	1,752,505
Austria	AT9LIES	Background	48.14	16.30	57.02		16.53	W	4.88	458,406
Austria	AT31401	Background	48.09	16.30	59.89	9.11	16.99	W	4.88	458,406
Austria	AT900ZA	Background	48.25	16.36	60.27	15.96	18.25	NW	16.91	1,752,505
Austria	AT9JAEG	Background	48.27	16.30	69.60	3.04	23.03	NW	16.91	1,752,505
Austria	AT30601	Background	48.30	16.31	64.82	16.72	24.86	NW	16.91	1,752,505
Austria	AT30401	Background	48.33	16.73	60.42	4.83	25.51	NE	3.30	90,908
Austria	AT10001	Background	47.84	16.53	55.58	10.75	26.94	S	18.71	157,637
Austria	AT30301	Background	48.14	16.96	60.25	-1.75	27.47	E	14.15	472,893
Austria	AT30403	Background	48.39	16.52	61.93	1.02	29.02	N	10.96	133,099
Austria	AT30065	Background	48.20	16.14	48.32	7.06	29.08	W	4.88	458,406
Austria	AT30201	Background	47.96	16.21	62.52	3.36	29.92	SW	5.04	262,780
Austria	AT10003	Background	48.11	17.07	59.56	9.35	35.20	E	14.15	472,893
Austria	AT0ILL1	Background	47.77	16.77	64.22	2.61	36.64	S	18.71	157,637
Austria	AT32401	Background	47.81	16.25	59.05	7.96	38.60	SW	5.04	262,780
Slovakia	SK0048A	Background	48.17	17.11	64.82	2.34	38.76	E	14.15	472,893
Slovakia	SK0001A	Background	48.12	17.13	49.66	-0.30	39.45	E	14.15	472,893
Austria	AT31901	Background	48.33	16.06	52.39	12.98	40.79	NW	16.91	1,752,505
Hungary	HU0035A	Background	47.69	16.57	56.42	-19.79	42.99	S	18.71	157,637
Austria	AT30202	Background	48.11	15.92	70.41	-2.89	44.81	W	4.88	458,406

Figure A1.93: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 8: N
SPO not available in this wind sector

Wind sector 1: NE
SPO not available in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W
SPO not available in this wind sector

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E
SPO not available in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW
SPO not available in this wind sector

Wind sector 4: S
SPO not available in this wind sector

Wind sector 3: SE
SPO not available in this wind sector

Figure A1.94: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Figure A1.95: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Table A1.80: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	3.3%		
E	14.2%		
SE	26%		
S	18.7%		
SW	5%		
W	4.9%		
NW	16.9%		10.7
N	11%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	3.3%		
E	14.2%		
SE	26%		
S	18.7%		
SW	5%		
W	4.9%		
NW	16.9%		-1.4%
N	11%		

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	3.3%			
E	14.2%			
SE	26%			
S	18.7%			
SW	5%			
W	4.9%			9.7
NW	16.9%		9.5	10.3
N	11%			9.3

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	3.3%			
E	14.2%			
SE	26%			
S	18.7%			
SW	5%			
W	4.9%			31.7%
NW	16.9%		36.3%	34.7%
N	11%			31.2%

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	3.3%				53.3
E	14.2%				59.4
SE	26%			59.6	
S	18.7%				64.9
SW	5%				62.9
W	4.9%			46.0	54.3
NW	16.9%		59.0	56.0	61.4
N	11%				60.2

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	3.3%				-11.3%
E	14.2%				2.6%
SE	26%			-5.5%	
S	18.7%				9.6%
SW	5%				0.5%
W	4.9%			-23.2%	-11.5%
NW	16.9%		3.3%	-5.8%	-1.2%
N	11%				-1.0%

Figure A1.96: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.21: Airport of Vilnius (VNO)

Figure A1.97: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.81: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Lithuania	LT00001	Background	54.68	25.29	15.71		2.84	N	20.96	186,810
Lithuania	LT00004	Industrial	54.67	25.25	16.75	-21.29	3.70	NW	13.26	103,700
Lithuania	LT00002	Background	54.69	25.21	13.85	-11.39	6.31	NW	13.26	103,700
Lithuania	LT00003	Traffic	54.72	25.29	27.83	-13.15	6.92	N	20.96	186,810

Table A1.82: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Lithuania	LT00002	Background	54.69	25.21	62.14	-1.94	6.31	NW	13.26	191,220
Lithuania	LT00003	Traffic	54.72	25.29	42.26	17.77	6.92	N	20.96	345,939

Figure A1.98: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

SPO not available in this wind sector

SPO not available in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available in this wind sector

SPO not available in this wind sector

SPO not available in this wind sector

Figure A1.99: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

SPO not available in this wind sector

SPO not available in this wind sector

SPO not available in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available in this wind sector

SPO not available in this wind sector

SPO not available in this wind sector

Table A1.83: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	14%		
E	15%		
SE	12.9%		
S	9.3%		
SW	7.2%		
W	7.3%		
NW	13.3%	11.9	12.2
N	21.1%	15.3	27.3

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	14%		
E	15%		
SE	12.9%		
S	9.3%		
SW	7.2%		
W	7.3%		
NW	13.3%	-15.5%	14.3%
N	21.1%	29.1%	2.1%

SPOs with hourly concentrations
not available for PM_{2.5}

SPOs with hourly concentrations
not available for PM_{2.5}

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport						
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km	WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	14%										
E	15%										
SE	12.9%										
S	9.3%										
SW	7.2%										
W	7.3%										
NW	13.3%		-10.5%								
N	21.1%		-5.3%								

Figure A1.100: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.22: Airport of Warsaw (WAW)

Figure A1.101: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.84: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Poland	PL0141A	Background	52.16	21.03	16.85	-23.80	3.27	E	26.28	174,726
Poland	PL0739A	Background	52.21	20.91	19.31		4.40	NW	19.07	136,677
Poland	PL0140A	Traffic	52.22	21.00	42.65	-36.79	4.67	NE	12.04	247,329
Poland	PL0134A	Background	52.19	20.84	18.01	-1.53	7.27	W	9.54	59,683

Table A1.85: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Poland	PL0141A	Background	52.16	21.03	12.53	-58.69	3.27	E	26.28	261,198
Poland	PL0141A	Background	52.16	21.03	12.39	-58.69	3.27	E	26.28	261,198
Poland	PL0739A	Background	52.21	20.91	17.11		4.40	NW	19.07	182,772
Poland	PL0140A	Traffic	52.22	21.00	16.04	-56.93	4.67	NE	12.04	630,258
Poland	PL0134A	Background	52.19	20.84	16.29		7.27	W	9.54	160,579
Poland	PL0308A	Background	52.29	20.93	14.60		11.36	N	10.78	709,534
Poland	PL0308A	Background	52.29	20.93	13.91		11.36	N	10.78	709,534
Poland	PL0821A	Background	52.08	21.12	12.86		11.75	SE	8.99	134,369
Poland	PL0717A	Background	52.19	21.18	17.76		13.25	E	26.28	261,198
Poland	PL0539A	Background	52.12	21.24	19.56		17.37	E	26.28	261,198

Table A1.86: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Poland	PL0141A	Background	52.16	21.03	48.18	-4.19	3.27	E	26.28	436,033
Poland	PL0739A	Background	52.21	20.91	45.81		4.40	NW	19.07	258,913
Poland	PL0134A	Background	52.19	20.84	46.15		7.27	W	9.54	362,350
Poland	PL0787A	Background	52.28	20.96	46.37		10.78	N	10.78	879,533
Poland	PL0143A	Background	52.29	21.04	47.48		12.95	N	10.78	879,533
Poland	PL0539A	Background	52.12	21.24	48.06		17.37	E	26.28	436,033
Poland	PL0129A	Background	52.41	20.96	49.83	1.67	24.83	N	10.78	879,533
Poland	PL0128A	Background	52.29	20.45	51.94	-3.15	35.35	W	9.54	362,350
Poland	PL0014A	Background	51.84	20.79	55.29	-1.58	36.84	S	5.40	159,052

Figure A1.102: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Figure A1.103: Distribution of PM_{2.5} hourly concentrations around the airport

PM_{2.5} concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Figure A1.104: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Table A1.87: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	12.2%		46.8
E	26.5%	12.1	
SE	9.1%		
S	5.4%		
SW	7%		
W	9.6%		17.9
NW	19.3%		22.4
N	10.9%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	12.2%		23.3%
E	26.5%	-6.9%	
SE	9.1%		
S	5.4%		
SW	7%		
W	9.6%		34.2%
NW	19.3%		62.3%
N	10.9%		

PM _{2.5} concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	12.2%		13.4	
E	26.5%	8.9		12.2
SE	9.1%			7.8
S	5.4%			
SW	7%			
W	9.6%		13.0	
NW	19.3%		17.6	
N	10.9%			13.5

Changes in PM _{2.5} concentrations (%) wind from airport				
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km
NE	12.2%		-0.4%	
E	26.5%	-16.8%		-19.7%
SE	9.1%			-26.9%
S	5.4%			
SW	7%			
W	9.6%		-0.8%	
NW	19.3%		27.5%	
N	10.9%			11.6%

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	12.2%				
E	26.5%	48.5		49.4	
SE	9.1%				
S	5.4%				58.6
SW	7%				
W	9.6%		42.6		44.5
NW	19.3%		32.5		
N	10.9%			39.1	40.2

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	12.2%				
E	26.5%	6.6%		13.9%	
SE	9.1%				
S	5.4%				9.6%
SW	7%				
W	9.6%		-4.5%		-11.2%
NW	19.3%		-29.1%		
N	10.9%			-14.0%	-15.9%

Figure A1.105: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

Annex 1.23: Airport of Zurich (ZRH)

Figure A1.106: Air quality SPOs around the airport

Table A1.88: List of NO₂ SPOs within 10 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 10 km from airport
Switzerland	CH0044A	Traffic	47.44	8.57	24.93		0.33	SE	16.03	85,780
Switzerland	CH0058A	Traffic	47.40	8.53	32.71		5.30	S	10.37	185,023
Switzerland	CH0005A	Background	47.40	8.61	16.74		5.47	SE	16.03	85,780
Switzerland	CH0013A	Traffic	47.39	8.54	18.82		5.85	S	10.37	185,023
Switzerland	CH0059A	Background	47.38	8.57	8.47		6.33	S	10.37	185,023
Switzerland	CH0010A	Background	47.38	8.53	17.56		7.02	S	10.37	185,023

Table A1.89: List of PM_{2.5} SPOs within 20 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 20 km from airport
Switzerland	CH0005A	Background	47.40	8.61	7.21		5.47	SE	16.03	191,405
Switzerland	CH0010A	Background	47.38	8.53	8.04		7.02	S	10.37	449,314

Table A1.90: List of O₃ SPOs within 50 km from the airport

Country	Station code	Station type	Latitude	Longitude	Concentration (µg/m ³)	2005-2023 trend (%)	Distance from airport area (km)	Wind sector (WS)	Wind frequency in WS (%)	Population in WS and 50 km from airport
Switzerland	CH0044A	Traffic	47.44	8.57	44.90		0.33	SE	16.03	514,918
Switzerland	CH0058A	Traffic	47.40	8.53	42.09		5.30	S	10.37	838,866
Switzerland	CH0005A	Background	47.40	8.61	51.79		5.47	SE	16.03	514,918
Switzerland	CH0013A	Traffic	47.39	8.54	54.16		5.85	S	10.37	838,866
Switzerland	CH0059A	Background	47.38	8.57	66.83		6.33	S	10.37	838,866
Switzerland	CH0010A	Background	47.38	8.53	57.63		7.02	S	10.37	838,866
Switzerland	CH0021A	Traffic	47.37	8.52	51.21		7.88	S	10.37	838,866
Switzerland	CH0060A	Background	47.51	8.72	50.90		12.09	E	14.15	390,988
Switzerland	CH0003R	Background	47.48	8.90	59.36		24.64	E	14.15	390,988
Switzerland	CH0053R	Background	47.19	8.18	74.41		39.88	SW	12.41	549,167
Switzerland	CH0005R	Background	47.07	8.46	80.52		41.82	S	10.37	838,866
Switzerland	CH0022A	Background	47.07	8.30	54.56		45.50	SW	12.41	549,167

Figure A1.107: Distribution of NO₂ hourly concentrations around the airport

NO₂ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

Wind sector 8: N

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Figure A1.108: Distribution of O₃ hourly concentrations around the airport

O₃ concentrations when wind is blowing from the airport

Wind sector 7: NW

Wind sector 8: N

Wind sector 1: NE

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 6: W

Wind frequency by sector

Wind sector 2: E

SPO not available
in this wind sector

Wind sector 5: SW

Wind sector 4: S

Wind sector 3: SE

Table A1.91: Mean hourly NO₂, PM_{2.5}, and O₃ concentrations when wind blows from the airport vs. other directions, by wind sector and distance

NO ₂ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	19%		
E	14.3%		
SE	16.2%	23.0	19.2
S	10.5%		16.5
SW	12.6%		
W	4.6%		
NW	11.2%		
N	11.6%		

Changes in NO ₂ concentrations (%) wind from airport			
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km
NE	19%		
E	14.3%		
SE	16.2%	4.4%	68.0%
S	10.5%		13.9%
SW	12.6%		
W	4.6%		
NW	11.2%		
N	11.6%		

SPOs with hourly concentrations
not available for PM_{2.5}

SPOs with hourly concentrations
not available for PM_{2.5}

O ₃ concentrations (µg/m ₃) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	19%				
E	14.3%			61.1	66.7
SE	16.2%	34.6	36.9		
S	10.5%		55.0	50.5	80.1
SW	12.6%				67.1
W	4.6%				
NW	11.2%				
N	11.6%				

Changes in O ₃ concentrations (%) wind from airport					
WIND SECTOR	WIND FREQUENCY	0-5 km	5-10 km	10-20 km	20-50 km
NE	19%				
E	14.3%			25.3%	13.7%
SE	16.2%	-21.7%	-32.9%		
S	10.5%		-0.7%	-2.8%	2.0%
SW	12.6%				3.5%
W	4.6%				
NW	11.2%				
N	11.6%				

Figure A1.109: Annual mean NO₂, PM_{2.5} and O₃ peak concentrations and distribution for airport and surrounding region

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